

**The Impact of Human Resource Management
Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested
Enterprises on Human Resource Development:
A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone**

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Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Declaration of Authentic Output

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Acknowledgments

First and foremost,

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Abstract

Purpose/objectives: This research deals with measuring the influence of SEZ in Laos on the development of human resources at the Macro/zone and Micro/firm level. The systematic measurement of the impact of Laos SEZs on human resource development at both levels shall be categorized and utilized to recommend comprehensive policies and incentives to enhance human resource development in Laos SEZs and the rest economy. The purpose is to show how Laos SEZ created job opportunities to the locals and how HRM programs and activities of foreign-invested companies influence human resource development.

Design/methodology/approach: The objective of this study has been directed in a mixed approach over two years. The information and data were analyzed at the macro and micro level.

At the macro level, mixed methods were applied that included secondary research and semi-structured interview. The secondary study examines the impact of SEZ on employment in Laos in three different ways, such as direct, non-direct, and gender employment. A free zone in Laos was selected to be a case study. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews involving relevant management authorities of Laos SEZs were conducted to explore current management incentives and policies encouraging the development of HR, opportunity, and challenge of such development in Laos SEZs.

At the micro level, mixed methods were also conducted, such as semi-structured interviews and survey research. The firm-level research investigates the effectiveness of HRM programs and activities of foreign-invested companies located in Laos SEZ. Three case studies were conducted. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore the efficacy of HRM programs and activities involving hiring and training staff, rewards and compensation, retention, career evaluation, and labor union and relation, semi-structured interviews were established.

Also, the way national cultural impact on HRM of FIEs were also explored through semi-structured interview HR managers. Moreover, survey questionnaires confirmed the validity of the interview and examined the relationship between the HRM policies and practices and HR development, which are based on the quality of life, working and living conditions, earning career prosperity, and knowledge and skill development.

Outcomes/Findings: The outcome represents a significant contribution to policies and incentives that encourage human resource development of Laos special economic zones. They will help policymakers an in-depth understanding of the current opportunities and challenges of human resource development in Laos SEZs, and establish the policies based on the way employment was generated. Also, they shall assist the policymakers in developing incentives to investors based on the significance of the contribution of each element involving HRM programs and activities of foreign-invested enterprises.

The findings from macro-level analyses demonstrated that:

- The case study zone named Savan-Seno SEZ contributed a small fraction of employment within the province where the zone is located. Yet, numbers of employment have been soaring in the last five years (2012-2017).

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- Evidence from sub-contract between foreign-invested enterprises and local businesses appeared to be significant evidence of indirect employment generate outside the zone. Also, the interview zone economic board and developer revealed significant development of small-medium enterprises outside the territory as well as infrastructure activities.
- The zone impact on gender employment since a significant number of employees at managers and non-managers are female between 18-35 years old.

The findings from Micro-level analyses demonstrated that:

- The results of the within-case analysis and the cross-case analysis of each company validated that foreign-invested companies implemented formal HRM policies and practices. Yet, informal practices usually occur during the recruitment and selection process of operational employees.
- National culture played a significant role on HRM management since norms and beliefs of major Laotian people are strongly rooted from a single religion. To help Laotian workers become familiar with the new working system, foreign directors should be the one designing system and let their subordinates work with operational employees.
- The results from the previous and current case studies were then used in formulating survey questionnaires. The number of six hypotheses was postulated to explore the correlation amid HRM policies and practices and the employees' insights on HR development. After the pilot study, questionnaires were disseminated to 78 correspondents. There were 76 responses to the survey. Since a suitable sample size was 75, the response rate is 100 percent.
- The relationship among each controlled variable and the response variable of human resource development's perception revealed positive results. A model that projected human resource development from six independent variables of HRM policies and practices was generated using regression analysis. The model suggested that three predictor variables (training and development, retention, and labor union and relations in trade) meaningfully presented to a perception of human resource development while the other three factors (recruitment and selection, prize, and work assessment) refused to do so.

Research contribution and limitations: This research contributed to both the theory and practices of international human resource management policies and implementation. In theory, the thesis added knowledge on the global human resource management's impact on human resource development. The new method derived from various findings and analyses of SEZs benefits at the macro and micro levels leads to new practices that are implied at the end of this study.

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Abbreviations and keywords

“AEC: Asian Economic Committee

ASEAN: The Association of South East Asia Nations

FDI: Foreign direct investment

FIEs: Foreign-invested enterprises

FTZs: Free trade zones

GVC: Global value chain

HID: Human resource development indicator

HRM: Human resource management

MNEs: Multi-national enterprises

SEZ: Special economic zones

SMEs: Small-Medium enterprises

WTO: World Trade Organization”

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Chapter 1: Introduction of Thesis

1.1 Background of the Thesis

The last two decades saw a time of fierce competition for overseas investment inflows since the worldwide economic recession encouraged reform in paradigm. States have attempted to continue to be competitive in the global market by proposing favorable investment surroundings at the central and regional levels which support the level of foreign direct investment (FDI), job opportunities, and hasten industrial chain, and modernization in the economic expansion (Dirlik, 2017). The innovative trend of globalization in economies have assuaged tariff and trade obstacles and made the global value network (GVN) a custom for corporations that sequentially further broaden tensions in international competitiveness.

According to the globalization trend, the concept of the free zone is presented. In 2015, the number of free zones had continuously grown since the first comprehensive free zone called “special economic zone” or SEZ was established at Shannon airport in 1959 (Zeng, 2015). Up to date, approximately 3,500 free zones of various types have been developed in more than hundreds of nations across the globe. It is estimated that more than 65,980,763 people have been employed within the zones across the world. More than 900 zones were located in a low-income country and developing countries, including “Lao People’s Democratic Republic” (Laos).

With a long history of war with Thailand, France, and America, the new Laos led by the Lao revolutionary party was formed in 1975 and proclaimed its freedom. “Human resource development indicators” (HDI) demonstrated that Laos is a low-income country in the world, and still, its GDP growth account for seven to eight percent each year, which is considered to be a fast-growing country in the region (Sims, 2018). Even though Laos’ economy has improved during the last two decades, the state initially benefits from its considerable reserves of natural resource such as mining and hydropower. Yet, relying on those resources alone is not sustainable and could cause drawbacks to the environment and the citizens. Therefore, the country started to explore alternative economic opportunities.

According to this, in line with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the passage leads the country out of poverty, one of the strategies of the MDGs is to attract FDI. The formation of SEZs on clustered industries was one of the highly significant attractions to the granting of FDI (Martin et al., 2018). The potential for the most emerging economies and low-income countries such as Laos is expected not only in bringing foreign capital but also on access to suitably skilled labor at various standards, as the new basis for growth and development. Although Laos possesses enough young workforce to supply the necessary quantity of workers, those workers are low-skilled and lack industrial working experience compared with neighboring countries (World bank report, 2018).

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In general, the results of SEZs have been mixed globally since some of the countries are successful in SEZs development while some are struggling. Indeed, since there are pieces of evidence of SEZs' achievement in many countries, SEZs might be useful in boosting industrialization and structural transformation if it is well-managed (Zeng, 2015). Yet, this depends on various development conditions in the country. In some countries, SEZs cannot address all economic challenges, nor enable the country to seize all commercial opportunities. Therefore, the following sections have been used to carefully examine Lao's financial background and conditions to determine the reason why Laos utilize SEZs as instruments for economic and social progress.

1.2 Macro-Economic Condition in Laos

1.2.1 Economic Background of Laos

Laos is a non-coastal country situated in the middle of South-East Asia surrounded by Thailand, China, Vietnam, Cambodia, and Myanmar (Map 1). Currently, there are approximately 6.8 million Laotians living in 18 provinces covering an area of 236,800 square kilometers.

Map 1: Lao PDR (Laos' People Democratic Republic)

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After becoming independent in 1975, Laos adopted a state-owned enterprise system, which was supported by the former Soviet Union and its neighboring communist countries. Under the centrally planned economic system, the country experienced problems from financial crises, which was the primary cause of the destruction of the state-owned enterprise system. In response to the challenge, the Laos government decided to employ a market-based economic system in 1986 (Elson, 2016). The government is managing the multi-sectoral market economy with a socialist orientation, establishing dissimilar types of markets, enhancing favorable conditions for domestic and foreign enterprises to do business.

For decades, although it is considered a low-income country, Laos has a fast-growing economy (World Bank, 2015). Since 2000, GDP growth has averaged 8 percent per year. Natural resources such as mining, hydropower, and forestry, which accounts for 44 % of overall capital in 2014, helped grow the economy during this period. Nevertheless, after the economic structure has changed during the last few years, Laos' GDP grew slightly low to 6.9 percent in 2017 (Figure 1). Yet, while GDP growth between 2016-2019 fell below the historical average, economic expansion remains firm and levelled as the best performing country in the region (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Laos GDP Growth Rate fell below historical average as of 2016-2019 (Laos statistical Bureau, 2018)

Figure 2: GDP Growth Rate remain soaring Comparison to peers as of 2010-2019 (ASEAN development report, 2018)

1.2.2 Major Economic Sectors in Laos

During the last couple of years, mining and agriculture have been replaced by the industry and the service sector. Development on the production side was propelled by a strong performance on the industry (Figure 3), particularly an expansion in generating electricity, as well as reliable construction. Inside the industry, the power sector is evaluated to develop by 15 percent year-on-year in 2018, in contrast to more than 30 percent the earlier year. Notwithstanding this control, the power sector is a significant driver, contributing 1.9 rate purposes of all-out genuine GDP development. Construction applied 1.3 percentage points aided by the ongoing construction of projects in the pipeline and power sector, as well as infrastructure projects including the Kunming-Singapore railway's Lao section.

The travel industry is assessed to bounce back somewhat in 2018 after the local patterns, which are enhanced by the Government of Lao PDR's advertising efforts (Visit Laos Year 2018). Complete traveler entries expanded by 3 percent in the initial 75% of 2018, as the decrease in the number of guests from neighboring nations and Europe was repaid by an eminent increment of guests from non-ASEAN countries. Furthermore, farming production, particularly for rice, vegetables, rubber, and banana, has decreased due to the lower price of world commodities and the floods in the Southern part of Laos in July 2018.

Furthermore, within the industrial sector, partially reinforced by developing electronic parts and components, manufacturing added 0.9 percentage points, mostly from the Special Economic Zones. Cement production increased as a result of new reserves, which achieved demand locally, particularly outside the energy sector. Despite a very low base, cement is exported to Thailand while the output for agriculture remains mixed: only 0.6% is added to the growth in GDP while other products such as rubber, vegetables, and other crops yielded more production in terms of better pricing.

Figure 3: Major economic sectors in Laos as of 2014-2018 (World Bank report, 2019)

1.2.3 Significance and Challenge of Human Resource Development in Laos

The human asset or human resource (HR) is a notable driver of feasible development and poverty reduction, especially as the idea of work has advanced. Creating jobs, animating productivity development, and improving the nature of employments in the non-ranch part are vital to diminishing poverty in Lao PDR. One approach to diminish destitution is for the individuals to achieve a more elevated amount of education, which enables them to progress into better-paid occupations and additionally increment their profitability in their present place of employment.

What's more, a more beneficial society takes into account a progressively productive economy, which builds family unit work salary and empowers families to change out of neediness. If human resource development is centered around the last 40 percent of the populace, this would furthermore bring about advancing fairness of chance, subsequently diminishing pay imbalance and the weakness of people living simply over the poverty line.

Despite the change of economic structure and new economic opportunity, Laos lacks skilled-workers to fulfill the requirement of the new economy. The country has a highly favorable demographics from a labor market perspective. 61.8% of the population is at the working age (15 to 64), and the country has the fastest population growth in the ASEAN with a 1.7% average annual rate of change. Yet, the Lao workforce is heavily made up of low-skilled workers. The formal

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urban labor workforce is around 700,000 to 1 million workers. A further 3 million people work in the agricultural sector and 300,000 to 400,000 Lao expatriates work in Thailand. Of the 700,000 to 1 million formal urban workers, approximately 200,000 jobs are in manufacturing. The two largest employment subsectors are the garments industry and construction, which employ roughly 25,000 to 30,000 each (Vilavong et al.; 2016).

Labor productivity relative to wages is low compared with neighbors like Vietnam and is estimated to be about half of the expected level of development for a country. Indeed, almost no growth has been observed in labor productivity for over a decade. Certain officials at the S-NCSEZ and the Savannaketh Governor's Office have also noted perceived concerns with the work ethic and worker loyalty. Cambodia, with its 12-million-person labor pool, may be more attractive for labor-intensive employers if these concerns are not addressed. There are positive aspects to the Lao labor market.

For instance, internal labor mobility is reportedly relatively healthy, with numerous reported cases of workers migrating from Thakhek to Vientiane, or even from Northern to Southern Laos included Savannakhet province. Workers are also moving from agricultural sectors to industrial and service sector positions—between 2005 and 2015, the percentage of workers in agriculture and forestry has dropped from 78.5% to 65%, while the rate of workers in the industrial sector has risen from 4.8% to 11.5% and the percentage of workers in services has risen from 16.7% to 23.4% (World Bank; 2019).

Additionally, the widespread belief that Lao workers are expatriating themselves to Thailand principally to take advantage of the 30% gross wage differential is, according to numerous interviewed sources, mostly unfounded. Indeed, the adequate living wages for Lao expatriate workers in Thailand usually are not any higher than they are at home -- considering job brokers' commissions, limitations on net remittances per worker of just 1,000-3,000 baht/month on average, and outweighed by a lower quality of life, distance from families and communities of origin, etc.

Yet, despite the availability of labor, inadequate skill levels may be hurting both productivity and foreign investment. Over 17% of firms report that the lack of an educated workforce is their top challenge in investing in Laos. Laos ranks below Vietnam and China in adult literacy -- 64% of the rural population and 33% of the urban population did not pass the reading comprehension exam. Inadequate labor skills levels appear to be more detrimental for SMEs, which have a low ability to invest in training.

1.2.3.1 Differences in Skill (Agricultural and Manufacturing)

Differences in skills, however, are most likely not the most difficult challenge to greater productivity and attracting industrial and service-oriented industries. Most Lao workers, if they desired, could be trained to perform low-wage jobs in manufacturing, and, thus, many more trades could be attracted. A more difficult barrier is instead a lack of desire, stemming from the relative

advantages of agricultural work from the perspective of the Lao. In other words, there are not enough manufacturing and service sector jobs that are sufficiently attractive to convince farmers to give up farming (Asian Development Bank; 2019).

Manufacturing jobs require longer working hours and the difference in salary between manufacturing and agricultural work is not as high as in other countries. Widespread land and livestock ownership, agriculture-oriented skills and seasonal work culture, family and community bonds, greater long-term job security in family-owned businesses than in industry, the ability to avoid regulatory & fiscal compliance burdens in a rural setting, and quality-of-life perceptions are also persuading many Laos to stay in agriculture.

1.2.4 Special Economic Zones as a Human Resource Development Strategy

According to the requirement of the human asset for poverty reduction, capacity-building of the public and private sectors is demonstrated in the economic plan of the Laos government. It enables the Laotians towards the acquisition of the required skills to achieve a diversified economy. Excelling in human resources is inherently strategic in preparing the labor force for the economy that is high-value and knowledge-driven. Such an economy needs attracting considerably skilled workers and well-developed human resources.

Along with the change of economic dependency and policy that focuses on the value-added sector, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) is distinguishably important in realizing such a goal. Nonetheless, the country recognizes that FDI has to be directed to cluster-specific industries with the right strategies. The FDI provides the notion that clustered free trade zones dominate each strategy in transforming the economy. “Industry skills, technical know-how, innovation, and modern technologies are believed to be transferred to the domestic market utilizing various channels of interaction with multinational companies” (Iom.int; 2019).

Internationally, the term “special economic zone” (SEZ) can be used to describe a wide range of special-status areas created by countries around the world, including “export processing zones,” “free economic zones,” “free trade zones,” “free ports,” “maquiladoras,” and a variety of other zones. Under this broad understanding of the term, an SEZ can be defined as a geographically delimited area that offers distinct laws, regulations, administration, and/or procedures, as well as infrastructure, facilities, and services from the rest of the country to promote economic development. The focus is typically on offering a superior business environment in the zones to attract FDI to the area and catalyze structural reforms to the broader economy.

Laos SEZs is expected to be a useful tool for helping to address not only boost investment of FDI but, more importantly, to resolve the challenge of the inadequate low-skill workforce. It is expected that the establishment of foreign-invested enterprises (FIEs) in SEZs could generate more

jobs, bring knowledge and technology which shall be transferred to the domestic economy. Furthermore, for countries at relatively low stages of development such as Lao PDR, SEZs can help with technological catch-up by attracting more advanced industries to facilitate knowledge transfer and higher productivity and efficiency. Zones have, in this connection, being particularly useful when used as one component of a national strategy to diversify and industrialize. South Korea and Taiwan, for example, rapidly moved from primary-sector economies to modern industrialized countries through the help of zones as one instrument in an overarching industrialization strategy.

1.3 Problem Statement and Rationale of Research

The major problem is that Laos SEZs have no comprehensive management regulations that focus on human resource development. This research is rational since the development of human resources is considered the main driver of economic growth by both developed and emerging countries, and it's more critical for low-income countries, including Laos. Today, human resource investment bringing in invention and advancement in technology is highly pondered. It drives an increase in productivity.

Laos is known for using aggressive efforts to establish many SEZs in the region for almost 20 years. Yet, there are various challenges due to limited resources and implementation capacity, a low-income country such that Laos cannot form an ideal commercial setting so often or create a capable nationwide infrastructure simultaneously. Therefore, a more liberal legal and regulatory framework, especially the human resource context, is critical to enhancing the management of Laos SEZs. To capture the benefits of SEZs, Laos requires a serious academic inquiry on the effects of its structural changes through the formation of free zones and on the expansion of human resources. This thesis explores the impacts of SEZs on human resource advancement in Laos.

1.4 Research Aim and Focus

This paper aims to seal the above “gaps” in research, in Laos’ context, and contributes to current studies that explore the effect of SEZs in Laos on the development of the human resource. This paper is relevant in proposing methods to capitalize on free zones so that the ideal level of development of the human resource is reached. In due course, this will attract the consideration of politicians who will focus on suitable ways of achieving the desired economic growth. This study attempts to measure the benefits of Laos SEZs in the context of human resource development to reach the aim of the study. This research focuses on two essential aspects derived from SEZs human resource benefits at the Macro and Micro level.

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At the macro level, employment generation is focused on measuring human resource development in Laos SEZs. Employment generation is a standard benefit that many low-income countries expect from the development of their SEZs. Since SEZs include manual labor, businesses in SEZs significantly establish a new employment source. Because of the high supply of low-wage laborers, emerging countries commonly entice capital into blue-collared jobs. The market for blue-collared employment within the zone increases. As SEZs grow, the demand shifts towards higher value-added activities and becomes high for skilled labor.

At the micro-level, human resource management policies and practices will be focused. Typical SEZs are comprised of foreign-invested enterprises, which have likely to have formal human resource management policies and implementation. Based on existing literature, foreign-invested enterprises tend to bring and adopt their official regulations and activities of HRM to their plant and, therefore, encourage labor market outcomes and human capital of the host country. This study delves into adopting and implementing international human resource policies in foreign-invested companies in Laos SEZs. According to the facts, the aim of this study is detailed in the following section.

1.5 Research Objectives

The research has the following objectives:

- To conceive an in-depth understanding of existing literature regarding three interconnect perspectives such as HR development, international HRM regulations/activities, and the impact of SEZs, especially Laos SEZs.
- To examine the way Laos SEZ generates employment opportunity to local worker
- To explore the opportunity and challenge of human resource development in Laos SEZs
- To discover current incentives, policies or regulation offered by the government to encourage human resource development in Laos SEZs
- To explore the environment and level of HRM policies and activities in foreign-invested businesses located within Laos SEZs
- To explore the way national cultural influence HRM of FIEs
- To survey the contribution of the policies and activities of the management of human resources to insights into human resource development.

1.6 Research Questions

Questions in the research are formed such as:

1. How does a Laos SEZ generate employment?
2. What are the opportunities and challenges of human resource development within Laos SEZs?

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3. What are the current incentives and policies offered by the Laos government to encourage human resource development within Laos SEZs?
4. How are the rules and activities of the supervision of human resources of the businesses of foreign investors implemented within Laos SEZs?
5. How does national culture influence HRM of FIEs in Laos SEZs?
6. What are the relationships between the rules and activities of the supervision of human resources of the business of foreign investors located in Laos SEZs and the perceptions of human resource development?
7. What incentives and policies can be recommended to enhance human resource development from Laos SEZs?

1.7 Structure of Thesis

According to the above analyses of the Laos economy and the way SEZs can serve as a policy tool in resolving human resource development challenges in Laos, research aim, objectives, questions/hypotheses, and research methodology are derived. To succeed the aim and to fulfill the expected contribution of the research, the following chapters are structured and organized based on research objectives.

The introduction is presented in **Chapter 1**. The chapter provides a research background, macroeconomic condition of Laos, significance, and challenges of HR development and justification of the study regarding special economic zones and HR development. Subsequently, to gain an in-depth understanding of three interconnected aspects such as HR development, SEZs, and HRM regulations and activities, **Chapter 2** presents critical analyses of existing literature regarding the three dimensions. Existing empirical shreds of evidence on measuring the effect of SEZs in the host country in a global context were carefully reviewed on its methods, approach, and research outcomes.

According to the burdens of existing papers, research challenges, concepts, questions, and hypotheses were elaborated in Chapter 3. **Chapter 3** also describes justifications for choosing a mixed-method approach and the research plan. Next, **Chapters 4 and 5** are core chapters and their outcomes answer research questions 1-5. While Chapter 4 is an analysis at the Macro or zone level and Chapter 5 is an analysis at Micro or firm level, both chapters appointed mixed methods.

To answer *research question 1, 2 and 3*, Chapter 4 focus on a case study of a free zone in Laos to examine the way it generates employment in various ways such as direct/indirect employment and gender employment. Also, Semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore current incentives, opportunities, and challenges of HR development in Laos SEZs.

Chapter 5 helps the researcher to answer *research question 4 and 5*. In this chapter, micro-level analyses are conducted to examine the way three case study firms located within Lao SEZs implemented and regulated their HRM. Additionally, the way national cultural influences HRM of FIEs were explored. *Research question 6* examines the relationship between HRM of the firms and perceptions of HR development is investigated.

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Outcomes of the research were discussed in **Chapter 7**. Also, policies recommendations on improvement of HR development in Laos SEZs are discussed in the chapter. The policy suggestions are based on macro and micro level analyses findings from previous chapters 4 and 5. Lastly, **Chapter 7** summarizes chapter 1-6. Discussions on limitations and concluding remarks are implied for further research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to Chapter 2

Chapter 1 represents the introduction of the research which included the overall economic condition of Laos. Also, the analysis of the way SEZs able to resolve the HR development challenge in the country by attracting FDI is presented. FDI from SEZs is expected to bring advanced technology, modern management knowledge, and enhance employment condition to the rest economy. Nevertheless, the outcomes of SEZs are hardly unique, and therefore, Chapter 2 is developed to understand what current knowledge and burdens of the research are. A retrospection of the sources helps the researcher to develop an understanding of what is already known about the chosen research area.

Furthermore, a literature review is where the researcher illustrated engagement ability in the academic study based on the comprehension of the works of fellow researchers. It provides the basis on which to justify the research concept, building research questions, and design. Systematic reviews help researchers reduce bias and are a cornerstone of an evidence-based approach. Such evaluation is considered crucial to decision-makers in an area where is conflating evidence concerning the best ways to do things (Bell et al., 2018).

Labaree (2009) implied that a literature review usually consists of three layers. The first layer is the initial studies of published scholars. The second layer is the investigations of peers. The last layer is the perceptions and opinions that the reviewer shares informally. The third layer is the essential layer and is cited as a “true knowledge” conceived from reviewing the literature. Based on that literature in this research is a systematic review in the three layers and is critically analyzed in several aspects such as HR development, HRM regulations, and activities and SEZs in the global and Laos context.

Chapter 2 is comprised of nine sections. It starts with section 2.1 to introduce the way literature will be reviewed and demonstrate the structure of the chapter. The second section 2.2 discusses the purpose of HR development in a country’s progress. Following this, the literature was narrowed down to section 2.3 reviewing the impact of MNEs on HR development in the host country. Later, section 2.4 discusses the rules and practices of HRM of MNEs. Section 2.5 explains the relationship between SEZs and HR development, and section 2.6 discusses SEZ in a global context. In section 2.7, measuring the benefits of SEZs were discussed. Also, the macroeconomic condition was analyzed in section 2.8. Following this section, 2.9 concluded Chapter 2.

2.2 Literature on Special Economic Zone in Global Context

2.2.1 Concept of Special Economic Zone

Most developing countries are encouraging the creation of free zones to succeed in ideal economic advancement. Since the significant purpose of SEZs' establishment is to entice foreign ventures through foreign-invested enterprises (FIEs) that are typically characterized by ownership advantage and skills and knowledge in management and production. Meanwhile, these firms are equipped with resources that allow them to spread machinery and equipment acquisition costs. All of these will set up a robust host country platform for learning, imitating, and accumulating HR. Therefore, as Romer (1986) contends, the accumulated HR is always connected to the economy of the host nation.

In general, an SEZ is a place where different laws apply with a view to promote the growth or development of the economy. While it has become accustomed to the idea that economic development means adding to gross domestic product (GDP) in an aggregate way that may or may not involve the equitable distribution of the proceeds, SEZs in history have been driven by very different forms of economic logic. In England, under the rule of the Normans and Angevins, extensive tracts of land were declared "forest" SEZs, that is, that was for the exclusive use of the monarch and for which the economy depended on non-timber forest products like deer and wild boars (Morris, 2015).

The slave markets at Penang and elsewhere are forms of SEZ in which the economy depended on the ability to enslave people by violence and exchange them for money (Reid, 2015). For religious communities, the economy is one of the spiritual enlightenments of some description and the imposition of specific forms of social relations. Large cities, such as those of the Lagos' megachurches in Nigeria (Maclean, 2017), have become semi-autonomous zones with voluntary legal regimes, and these may become SEZs with the agreement of the state. The sanction of the country is required, that is, for an area that aims to be beyond the reach of the state to have a formal, recognized status. Of course, there are situations in which the nature of the country is disputed.

In the north of Myanmar, for example, various ethnic minority groups have sought to enact their own independent states by employing the Maoist strategy of replacing the state's agencies and institutions with one's own (Marks, 2007). These zones are not recognized by the Myanmar government, but they have their own communities of international business people taking advantage of products in which the area may have a comparative advantage, for instance, in jade and opium (Gluckman, 2015). These zones might exist as SEZs within the country overall, or they might have designated areas within them that have specific economic regulations in place. For example, in Jiegao, an SEZ exists as a form of the small island within Myanmar that operates

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according to Chinese rules from the cross-border neighbor and mainly for the benefit of its traders (not because the rules are enforced differentially but because of its remoteness) (Meng, 2012).

SEZ status need not be enforced and guaranteed by the state but could not be put into place by private sector interests. The Boten Golden Land SEZ in northern Laos, for example, was once a site devoted to gambling and its ancillary activities and governed by the zone's investors, with the (initial) acceptance of the Lao government (Ku, 2016). Although that zone has been recreated along with more conventional business lines and is open to investment from around the world, there is still a de facto sense of governance by the leading investors. Yet, the situation was changed significantly since the establishment of the SEZ had been giving challenges for the Laos government rather than an advantage for economic development. The zone has been transferred to a logistic and eco-tourism zone called Boten-Mohan SEZ, developed by a new developer from China.

However, the dominant neoliberal logic of capital accumulation by the manufacturing and related services has brought about a wave of SEZ construction across mainland Southeast Asia, powered by the success of the policy in China, where more than 740 million people have been lifted out of poverty from 1978 to 2017 without any yielding of political power (Xinhua, 2018). Indeed, it is possible to argue that people will be less interested in protesting for political change if they can become rich or, at least, more capable of participating in good consumer consumption. For this to occur, governments will take the precaution of cordoning off SEZs from the general population.

In the past, this would involve erecting walls and barbed wires around the zone with guards to ensure that no unauthorized entry is permitted – indeed, in Cambodia, similar provisions are included in the recently introduced SEZ legal regime. Now, with better transportation infrastructure linking large cities with peripheral and regional centers, it is possible to locate SEZs in remote regions or in the border wherein economic experimentation can take place with the insignificant risk of contaminating the country. To be successful, this involves creating city-like effects in areas that are not cities.

Jacobs (1985) argued that the two principal activities of economic development to take place, i.e., import substitution and then innovation, can only take place in cities because these have the assemblage of labor. Markets, capital, skills, managerial know-how, and so forth are required but cannot found elsewhere. The contemporary SEZ must have incentives in place that will encourage both domestic and international investors to create this assemblage in the desired location.

An ersatz city requires organizations and facilities like health, education, and leisure and so it is no surprise that SEZs are now likely to have vocational schools and universities, hotels, restaurants, and golf courses present within their limits. When the SEZ is designed to take advantage of non-industrial comparative benefits, such as the Lijiang Yulong Snow Mountain

Tourism Zone and the Yangzonghai Lake Tourism and Vacation Zone SEZs, it is a hotel, tourist support facilities and experience economy creation institutions that are most commonly found.

2.2.2 Expansion and Types of Special Economic Zone

A corporate and competitive investment environment is an essential policy initiative that governments must pursue in the era of globalization. In 2015, The Economist reported that the SEZs has continuously grown since the earliest up-to-date SEZ was founded at Shannon airport in 1959. Currently, approximately 3,500 Export Processing Zones (EPZs) and SEZs have been worked out in 120 countries. More than 900 zones are located in Asia. In 2015, The Economist estimated that more than 65,980,763 people had been employed within EPZs across the world.

The term "special economic zones" has different names and characteristics, including "free trade zones, export-processing zones, industrial parks, economic and technology-development zones, high-tech zones, science and technology parks, free ports, and business zones, among others" (Figure 6). Though these zones vary, they all possess similar characteristics. Broadly speaking, the SEZ concept is defined by four components: "(1) it is a geographically defined area, usually highly secured; (2) it operates a single management or administration; (3) it offers the investor advantages within the zone physically; and (4) it has a separate customs area (duty-free benefits) and simplified procedures" (Zeng, 2015).

Meanwhile, Wang (2013) defined SEZs at different angles. These zones share features that contribute to the "special" nature of the SEZ. These are: "(1) a special regulatory regime: zones normally operate under more liberal economic laws than those that typically prevail, regarding issues such as labor, land use, and foreign investment; (2) public services: zones are normally serviced with efficient customs, fast-track registration and licensing, often through one-stop-shop services; (3) infrastructure: zones have much better and more reliable infrastructure such as roads, power, and water, compared to the domestic economic environment; and (4) fiscal incentives: the zone's investors, particularly its anchor investors, often enjoy capital freedoms and certain levels of tax incentives and subsidies" (Zeng, 2015).

However, not every SEZs have all certain conditions. Types and characteristics of the zones might depend on its development stage.

Figure 4: Types of SEZs (Adapted from Zeng, 2015)

These are the wide zones objectives, yet there is no all-inclusive standard equation for estimating their prosperity. Normally, the "achievement" of a prearranged program depends to a

great extent on whether it accomplishes the objectives indicated upon the foundation (for the most part for a period skyline of 10 to 15 years) and whether it is possible as far as the all-out interest in the endeavor (Zeng, 2016). Such objectives are commonly connected with quantitative proportions of financial improvement impacts, for example, venture, work, foreign trade, or potentially send outage, and in different cases, related with monetary and political changes, contingent upon the program's underlying targets.

In short, if implemented correctly in the right situation, the zones can be powerful tools to promote industrialization. Some emerging economies are offering examples of success, especially those in East Asia. Such areas, however, are costly, risky undertakings that need a comprehensive development strategy.

2.2.3 The expectations of Special Economic Zone on Human Resource Development

Free zones are usually established in emerging economies to enhance economic activities. The principal aim of the establishment is to entice FDI through MNEs when free zones are created. The foreign venture should bring skills and knowledge in modern management and production from ownership benefits. Meanwhile, these companies are equipped with resources that will allow them to spread the cost of foreign machinery and equipment acquisition. All of these will provide the host countries with a reliable platform for learning, imitating, and accumulating human capital. Therefore, accrued HR has a direct positive effect on economic growth (Romer, 1986).

In a broader sense, it is believed that FDI brings innovation, such as expertise in goods/services, production and management know-how, and the source of a new market. Those new skills and knowledge usually occur through direct and indirect channels through “spillover effects.” Traditionally, SEZs or free trade zones bring MNCs. Compared to local foreign firms, importing capital, advanced and proprietary technology can affect the standard productivity level of the host economy. Gugler and Brunner (2007) implied that MNEs could, therefore, transfer technology directly, for instance, through licensing, supplier networks, or sub-contracting arrangements, and such relationships appear to be positively related to the level of subsidiaries’ autonomy.

Although SEZs are expected to bring new technology, advanced skills, and knowledge to the host country and cluster-specific industries create spillovers effects to the rest economy, many scholars such as Madini (1999) argued that impacts of MNCs in SEZs on human resource development are not visible. Hamada (1974) supports the argument that firms outside SEZs might have externalities or knowledge creation effects that become more competent after the overseas investment has been introduced. The statement is out of date and might not be applied to other countries, since Japan is more-self productive and have not relied much on foreign innovation.

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Furthermore, Creskoff & Walkenhorst (2009) and Wang (2013) found that SEZs have a significant impact on the labor market and social welfare through the movement of labor and spillover effects. This occurs typically within early-established free zones. In some cases, foreign ventures established a research and development center in the host country. At a later stage of the zone's development, modern technique and innovation are spilled outside the zones.

In the meantime, several investigations of Alder et al. (2013) and Wang (2013) demonstrate that general relief payments can be enhanced beneath specific conditions, for example, drawing in the remote direct venture and upgrading of fares. Exact investigation shows numerous free zones enticed overseas ventures, made occupations and trades, and illustrated a possibly constructive outcome on money-saving advantage (Jayanthakumaran, 2003; Chen, 1993; Monge-Gonzalez et al., 2005; Fuller and Romer, 2012). Models are very self-evident, particular in the encounters of East Asia.

Be that as it may, the understandings on SEZs are very blended. SEZs are seen by a significant number of researchers as an imperfect system for economic advancement. Some mentioned a couple of advantages of free zones and the contort of the distribution of assets (Engman et al., 2007). Others accept the accomplishment of the zones is bound to a restricted skyline to specific conditions (Hamada, 1974; Madani, 1999). Several investigators, including Hamada (1974), stated that free zones reducing social security and benefits. Meanwhile, other research has raised concerns that SEZs might become "enclaves" (Kaplinsky, 1993). In sum, literature regarding the advantages of SEZs or EPZs focuses on HR development seems to be out of date and contains mixed results.

2.2.4 Measuring Benefits of Special Economic Zone on Domestic Economy: Empirical Evidences

Measuring the impact of SEZs on the domestic economy is not new and has been studied for decades. Nevertheless, the outcomes of the research have been mixed. Based on existing literature, the benefits of SEZs can be measured at the Macro and Micro level. The following paragraphs review the documentation.

2.2.4.1 Measuring Benefits of SEZs in Macro-Level

Research on the impact of SEZs in Macro-level included employment generation, the contribution of national GDP, investment, and export diversification. These econometric data are flows occurring within a specific period and can be measured relatively easily. All existing pieces of evidence have been analyzed using econometric shreds of evidence, mostly from World Bank Group reports.

a. Gross domestic products

It is expected that the achievement of SEZs could lead to the improvement of the GDP of the host country. Most of the scarce evidence found from the World Bank reports have been mixed results. In terms of GDP, Chinese SEZs demonstrated outstanding outcomes. An investigation of Zheng (2010) showed that after post-reform in China, an average GDP increased 12 percent in more than two hundred provinces over the past 23 years of developing free zones. An SEZ's long-term (cumulative) effect could be a growth in GDP of about 20% (Alder, S. et al., 2013).

A recent report on SEZs projects being planned under the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) was expected to raise Pakistan's GDP by 2%. EEMC (2018) reports that is SEZs in Poland were estimated to contribute to GDP growth; for instance, the analysis indicated a nominal value of a financial surplus of PLN 171.8 billion (€41 billion) in 2013 (Pastusiak et al., 2014). The fundamental sources of the fiscal surplus, which are the costs of remuneration paid to employees of companies operating in SSE, exports of these enterprises, and the demand for production, mean that they are purchased on the domestic market by companies operating in Polish SEZs. However, GDP seems to be an ultimate outcome of SEZs development and might need time to be discovered for many countries.

b. Foreign investment

All free trade zones have a universal expectation, which is to attract foreign investment by eliminating binding investment constraints. All types of free zones have similar essential standards. This included enabling financial specialists to import and fare obligation-free and trade controls, encouraging authorization and other administrative systems, and regularly liberating them from corporate expense commitments, VAT, or additional nearby charges. To look after control, EPZs were frequently shut in bequests with stringent traditions controls at landing, and deals are generally restricted to fare advertisements specifically. Acquiring reports indicated a diverse degree of interest in various nations.

Most likely, in pulling in speculation through SEZs, China is at the highest priority on any rundown of examples of overcoming adversity. An examination (Wang 2013) on 321 prefecture-level urban areas somewhere in the range of 1978 and 2008 outlines: a) all things considered, the SEZ program raises the per capita FDI level by 21.7% and the FDI development rate by 6.9%; b) the SEZ program produces massive mixture of economies; it builds mechanical advances in recently treated districts by 1.6 rate focuses contrasted with before ones, and c) The average compensation of the treatment gathering is 8% higher than that of the control gathering (The typical cost for essential items increments by 5 percent during the assessment time frame).

Africa has a place with the base of the rundown, including Mauritius, while Kenya, Lesotho, and Madagascar are halfway fruitful. In the interim, most practices in zoning have fizzled (Farole, 2011). An examination by Farole (2011) on African zones (Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho,

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Nigeria, Senegal, and Tanzania) contrasted with four non-African nations (the Dominican Republic, Honduras, Vietnam, and Bangladesh) demonstrated accomplishment in African zones is limited to a couple of nations with very high execution, for example, Kenya, Ghana, and Mauritius. In terms of investments, the African zones are generally lagging from their counterparts in other continents. The weak business environment could be an essential reason (Farole, 2011).

Several other countries are in the middle of the list and have been demonstrating significant progress in attracting investments through their SEZs' establishment. In Bangladesh, only the last decade experienced a phenomenal growth of the country's garments. In fact, there were only 50 garment factories in Bangladesh in the early 1980s, employing only a few thousand people. The EPZ program was established during this time, a move that would prove to have a substantial impact in facilitating the creation of the garment sector over the coming decades. Bangladesh now has almost 4,500 units to produce clothing, placing half of the industrial workforce in the country (Bangladesh Bank 2009).

Research of Pastusiak et al. (2018) used P. Warr's enclave model to analyse the effectiveness of SEZs in Poland. Poland was selected for study due to an excessive network of SEZs that have a local influence on the Polish economy and develop national and international economic relations. They concluded that the effect of SEZs on the Polish economy is optimistic and they are the market's source of added value. In Poland, 14 SEZs are attracting around 1,100 companies. As of 31 December 2013, 55 billion Polish Zloty New (PLN) were invested by companies operating in the zones.

c. Export generation and diversification

SEZs are expected to fill the gap of export for the country that has a low base for manufacturing and industry. In sum, it seems like export outcomes have been mixed. SEZs have not positively influenced exports in some countries. The Dominican Republic, for instance, developed a rationale for SEZs and formed what most regarded as successful SEZs with catalyst effects, increasing employment and productivity levels (Rhee et al., 1990). However, free zones have not had an outstanding positive impact on exports in the Dominican Republic. The country prevailed in pursuing import substitution rules and maintained several trade barriers, arguing that stunted export impacted SEZs (Rhee et al.). SEZs are still largely isolated from the rest of the economy in the Dominican Republic today (Carneiro et al., 2015).

In 2005, Aggarwal used econometric results which were recorded for forty years and found that "India's SEZ exports accounted for only 5% of total exports. On the other hand, SEZ exports accounted for almost one-fifth and one-third of exports in Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, respectively, in a short period." India undertook a significant expansion of its SEZ policy at the time of these findings; however, modern literature such as a survey by "the Comptroller and the office of the

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Auditor-General in India,” continues to emphasize the considerable achievement of India's free zones policy (CAG, 2014).

In addition, zones in China have also observed the diversity of export outcomes. For example, Schminke and Van Biesebroeck (2013) compared “the Science and Technology Industrial Parks (STIPs)” of export-trade development zones (ETDZs) in China. They find the two types of significant differences. Higher export values were achieved by companies located in an ETDZ, driven by higher trade volumes and more destinations. STIP-based firms performed best on quality dimensions, attract higher export prices, and exported to high-income nations more successfully.

More established research showed that SEZs affect send-outs in Malaysia, Mauritius, and Sri Lanka. Johanson and Nilsson (1997) suggested that SEZs are bound to affect send-outs positively. Their examination likewise underlines the "impetus impact" of Malaysia on potential residential exporters by filling the market with a "thoughts hole." In Malaysia by the mid-1990s, SEZs drew the consideration of FDI who expedited information on acing trade, creating merchandise, showcasing, and disseminating.

On the highest point of that, the portion of local product trades in eco-zones in the Philippines expanded from 22% in 1995 to 76% in 2003, and the proportion of locally direct interest in eco-zones grew from 30% in 1997 to over 81% in 2000 (FIAS, 2008). In synopsis, as Aggarwal et al. (2008) likewise calls attention to, the jobs SEZs played in fare enhancement have contrasted by nation crosswise over segments and items.

Enormous fares from SEZs have been noted in certain parts, which were at that point outward-situated before SEZs developed available, making it hard to straightforwardly ascribe send out the execution to the nearness of SEZs; Southern India's data innovation contains a valid example. In different cases, nonetheless, for example, Bangladesh's clothing industry, has even more expressly comprehensible linkages between the advancement of SEZs and the expanded profitability of fares. It creates the impression that the fare commitment in nations additionally relies upon the mechanical foundation of the nations.

d. Employment generation

Additional to the above static macroeconomic benefits, an SEZ is expected to behave like “pressure valves” to relieve widespread unemployment. Based on recent reports, employment within the zone is evitable and has been occurring in various forms. Aggarwal (2011) implied that jobs within SEZs could be created direct and indirect ways and have an impact on gender employment structure.

- *Direct employment*

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Firstly, employment opportunities in the zones were created indirectly. To the extent that SEZs involve labor-intensive activities, SEZ companies are, a priori, an essential source of new careers. Low-income nations generally entice investment in simple processing labor-intensive industries due to the availability of inexpensive labor. This increases demand within the zone for unskilled workers. As SEZs grow, shifting to higher value-added activities could also increase demand for skilled labor. Numerous reports demonstrated a significant amount of jobs had been created within SEZs of countries around the world.

To date, the impact of EPZ on employment generation can be found in reports of the International Labor Organization. This type of zones established approximately sixty-eight million direct jobs as of 2007 (FIAS, 2007). By analyzing econometric evidence, SEZs in many countries demonstrated a significant amount of jobs created within SEZs. Still, SEZs in China are also some famous examples of SEZ development in terms of job creation. Based on the World Bank report (2016), estimates in China show that SEZs governed by the central government created employment for over 30 million people and 46% of foreign direct investment.

A \$165 million World Bank venture in Madagascar added to a ten-fold increment in informal business stocks and an about sevenfold increment in the number of formal occupations in Fort Dauphin and Nosy Be's development posts, notwithstanding a confounded political condition. To improve the business atmosphere and make employments around these development shafts, the task effectively coordinated a few changes (World Bank Group, 2016). Farole (2011) likewise discovered that Tunisia's and Dominican Republic's SEZ projects are usually announced as enclave projects and did not invigorate an exceptionally fundamental change; however, they stayed strong, working on many programs.

By using the same research strategy, Jensen and Winiarczyk (2014) confirmed the positive impact of SEZs on employment generation the evidence implied that SEZs in Kenya has supported in establishing more than 40,000 jobs in manufacturing and increased work efficiency by some 20% in 2006. In another word, the employment rate has been increased by 2% annually. This showed that it is highly possible in principle that SEZs could prolong forever to be the effects of both job generation and productivity improvement.

Furthermore, Kingombe and Velde (2016) also include new econometric proof suggesting that SEZs in Kenya have created some 40,000 jobs in manufacturing and increased productivity by around 20% (or 2% annually) over the decade to 2006. This demonstrates that SEZs can be both job creation and productivity enhancement in principle, although questions are also raised as to whether the transformative consequences of efficiency can be maintained forever.

In Dubai, the more than 7,000 firms currently employ 170,000 people at the Jebel Ali Free Zone in Dubai or 13% of the workforce. By 2012, 10,000 jobs were generated by the Aqaba SEZ in Jordan. Eight Bangladesh zones drew 412 companies that made \$ 2.6 billion in investment and employed 350,000 people (IFC, 2016). Employment in industrial-free zones in the Dominican Republic increased from 500 in 1970 to nearly 200,000 in 2007.

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- Non-direct employment

Raheem (2011) and Aggarwal (2008) implied that the implicit effect is reflected as ancillary job opportunities created by SEZ operations in sectors of the economy. Included are transportation, communication, car, civil aviation, shipping, tourism, hospitality, packaging, banking, and insurance. Cizkowicz et al.'s recent research (2015) reinforces the point. Their study attempts to approximate the set of employment and investment panel and spatial panel data models for 379 Polish countries throughout 2003-2012.

They benefit from a unique company-level dataset for Polish SSEs, which includes around 30,000 observations. Results reveal that SSEs have significantly positive effects on employment: jobs in certain SSEs generate employment in host countries outside the SSE and even more in surrounding countries. Direct and indirect impact estimates indicate that every 100 posts in certain SSEs generate, on average, about 72 jobs in a host country outside the SSE and 137 jobs in surrounding countries.

An older analysis by Jensen and Winiarczyk (2014) conducts an ex-post assessment of where the SEZs adopted in Poland in 1994 were effective in achieving the objectives of regional development. They analyze the strategy for as many of its goals as possible: job creation, business formation (including gaining foreign direct investment), effects on income or wage, and environmental sustenance. Their estimation of SSEs' regional economic impact with using panel data models based on dummy variable model reveals that SEZs in Poland have been able to succeed in some of their goals, such as private business formation, thus enhancing non-SEZ employment rates.

Most evidential analyses on SEZs were based on the formal econometric analysis in other countries, in the US, France, and the UK. Their findings are hardly credible, regardless of the country being studied. There is an estimated range of positive effects (Givord et al. 2013 or Gobillon et al. 2012). Givord et al. (2012), for example, supply new causal inference on the effectiveness of locally targeted tax incentives in revitalizing troubled areas. The assessment concentrates on the zone's effort of the genesis of French companies, which was implemented in Continental France in 1997.

Over twelve years, they use new georeferenced panel data at the firm level. During the first year of the policy, their results showed a significant impact on company zones policy on employment and business location. However, this desirable assessment appears to be openly discussed as it may be due mostly to firms that are less likely to stimulate either local employment or economic activity. Furthermore, the early positive results are reduced after a few years as the increase in business locations is partially offset by more frequent discontinuations of business.

In the UK, more than twenty years of regulatory board information on program cooperation and firm execution from the Census Bureau are coordinated by Criscuolo et al. (2007) to assess

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the circumstances and logical results of the work, speculation, profitability, and section-and-leave approach. Utilizing an instrumental variable methodology, they discover the program has positively affected the two employments and speculation, which is disparaged by credulous estimators. Be that as it may, there is no measurably critical impact on the efficiency of the complete factor. There is additionally some proof that the program can hinder reallocation from less effective plants by supporting less proficient endeavors, antagonistically influencing total profitability development.

While there are certain confirmations on the effect of SEZs, a few outcomes are impartial. A paper by Gobillion et al. (2012) presents an effective appraisal of the French venture zone program propelled in 1997 to enable jobless specialists to discover work by allowing a generous pay charge exclusion (around 33% of total work costs) to organizations locally contracting at any rate 20% of their workforce. In view of a novel geo-referenced dataset of long-haul joblessness spells in the Paris area (1993-2003), their discoveries show that while the undertaking zones program tended to "pick champs," it is slanted not to be financially savvy. It slightly affected the rate of getting a new line of work for jobless laborers (which is expanded by a low 3 %). This impact is confined and just critical in the short-run (for example, best-case scenario during the three years following the arrangement begin).

Then again, Neumark and Kolko (2010) gave a negative audit on business results in America. They utilize new information and geographic mapping strategies at the foundation level to improve assessments of the adequacy of state-claimed endeavor zones, concentrating on the program of California. The proof demonstrates that business zones don't build occupations inside and outside the zone. They likewise secure no position move to low-wage laborers focused by impetuses from the enterprises' zone. Their study concludes that in achieving its primary objectives, the program is ineffective. In addition, some authors suggest that both pre-existing regional economic conditions depend on the strength of SEZ functioning effects.

Furthermore, Mayneris and Py (2014) propose a critical survey of the literature on urban enterprise zones in America, France, and the UK. They discovered that the findings of the papers published over the past twenty years vary considerably across studies. These seemingly conflicting results can be accounted for by several explanations. Since the 1990s, technical tools and empirical methods have greatly improved in evaluating such policies. Moreover, the efficiency of urban business zones seems to depend on the characteristics of the zone, the industrial sector, and the design of policies.

They also suggested that further research in this area should be attempted to take better account of the general effects of the equilibrium and provide a more accurate measure of the welfare implications of these policies. Besides, the same research stream, Bondonio (2003), implied that the effect of SEZ's functions relies on pre-existing regional economic conditions. Based on the on-research papers, the result of indirect employment effects has been mixed and even demonstrated negative results for some advance zones in rich countries.

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- Gender employment

Interestingly, numerous pieces of evidence implied that the total number of women employed in SEZs is predominantly higher than men. A recent study from World Bank (2011) suggested the way special economic zones impact women in eight developing countries, including Bangladesh, China, Costa Rica, Egypt, Jordan, Kenya, and the Philippines. This scenario comes from a combination of interviews with stakeholder organizations, factory-based qualitative research, and desk research. This research interviews a group of stakeholders (including international buyers and factory managers) with civil society groups, workers' organizations, government, and private sector stakeholders.

It is discovered that female laborers accounted more than 70 percent of all-out changeless specialists in each SEZs situated in the nations. The investigation additionally found that ladies utilized in EPZs and SEZs are observed to be more youthful and unmarried or, are probably going to have fewer kids, whenever wedded, than ladies in different enterprises. Ladies are utilized in dress and gadgets workshop, while men are discovered all the more generally in offices for materials and knitwear. Occupations are additionally frequently isolated by sexual orientation, ladies regularly syndicate the sewing floor, while men are bound to iron and cut (Aggarwal, 2011).

The examination likewise discovered that while the predominance of ladies in reviewed endeavors is higher by and substantial and ladies will, in general, have a similar length of administration as men (8.1 and 8.6 years, individually), they are still to a great extent underrepresented in supervisory positions and work for councils. There are additionally uniquely various explanations behind turnover, with men leaving for better-paid employments, regularly abroad, while ladies quit principally to address family and childcare needs (World Bank, 2011). This clarifies interest in some sexual orientation activities, for example, improved childcare may help zones hold female specialists.

Evidence from new SEZs such as Cambodia suggests a similar result. A study by Warr and Menon (2016) examined the role of SEZs within Cambodia's trade policy by using econometric data from 2005 to 2015. It begs whether the organization of SEZs by Cambodia since late 2005, based on the economic evidence to date, has been successful. Results showed that while SEZs in Cambodia enhance significant employment rates, women make up more than 90 percent of non-management workers were employed in Cambodia free zones. Comparing with adjoining countries such as Laos established free zones since the 2000s, Cambodian SEZs perform the most in terms of investment, employment generation, and encourage innovation. Yet, the country has relied heavily on Chinese investment, which accounted for more than 70 percent of total SEZs investment, and that might lead to political challenges in the future.

A study of Farole (2011), which synthesizes the results from two types of research: investors in SEZs participating in firm-level surveys and SEZ programs undergoing country case studies, explained the reason behind the intensive female employment within SEZs. His study

mentioned that women make up more than 50% of the workforce in SEZs in developing countries, which sometimes reach 90% in other countries. The female staff is considered to work more earnestly and progressively restrained. They likewise have the deft fingers and determination with routine assignments required by the work serious capacities, for the most part, happening during the zones and are more averse to strike or upset creation in different ways than men. Businesses hence favor female laborers to male specialists in the conviction that manual expertise are of more noteworthy control and tolerance makes ladies increasingly unfit for semi-qualified exercises during the zones. Also, for high wages and better working conditions, they are less inclined to apply weight.

Besides, through fittingly organized polls, Aggarwal (2007) gathered information through two essential reviews: one for the business people and the other for the workers during the zones. Her examination uncovered that most of the ladies originate from the country with weak foundations and are youthful and single. In any case, they might not have been ingested into formal work for SEZs by any means, so SEZ business can be thought to give them an autonomous wellspring of pay that would have been denied something else. In this way, SEZs are relied upon to make a significant commitment to enabling ladies. Given these remarkable degrees of work of ladies in SEZs and the critical job of SEZs in fares-creating nations, it tends to be genuinely inferred that an unmistakably gendered procedure has been sending out situated industrialization in recent years (Farole and Akinci, 2011).

2.2.4.2 Measuring Benefits of SEZs in Micro-Level

a. Firms' performance

The first research stream attempted to study the impact of SEZs through firms' achievement. The relationship between SEZs and company-level performance is less known. Few pieces of research have tried to look closely at the connection. Through observations, domestic firms are able to enhance their export through imitation of the production process and market of enterprises invested by foreigners in SEZs. For example, the local company can observe how an enterprise invested by foreigners produce a product and then use the same technology to get their production more efficient. The spillover can come either voluntary through technology transfer or involuntary by knowledge leakage.

A study by Zhang (2017) examined the way FDI influences sophistication and enhancement of export in developing economies. His article seeks to bridge the gap by using data from the 2005 to 2013 manufacturing panel of Chinese and foreign joint ventures. Zhang estimates that FDI has definite sophistication and enhancing effects on China's manufactured exports, and such gains from FDI largely depend on China's human capital-measured absorptive capacity.

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Jiang et al. (2016) used organizational data from 1998 to 2007 on all international joint ventures in China, about a quarter of all international joint ventures worldwide. They discover that Chinese companies selected as foreign investor partners tend to be more significant, more productive, and more likely to be subsidized than other Chinese companies. Subsequently, significant international technology transfer is taking place not only to the joint venture itself but also to the Chinese joint venture partner. Furthermore, with technology spillovers normally outpacing adverse effects on competition, joint ventures yield net positive externalities in the same industry to other Chinese firms.

Relying on complete transactions and observations of customs in China throughout 2000-2006, Li and Liu (2014) found that Chinese EPZs drew in foreign firms to establish operations on exporting. In both export and import patterns, Chinese firms rapidly imitated these firms. Products shipped from EPZs have grown across the province, with the city's most substantial gains containing the EPZ, and the next largest in the towns adjacent to the EPZ. Chinese firms also replicated the importation of equipment in EPZs, suggesting copying technology. Finally, companies that replicated EPZs enjoyed more significant productivity gains than non-imitating peers, showing that imitation can lead to substantial technological benefits. They surmise that a critical element of China's trade success was its ability to attract foreign firms and its subsequent copying ability.

Several earlier research papers on product imitation in China have been linked to the research by Li and Liu (2014). For instance, Brambilla et al. (2009) used a mix of industry-level FDI flow data and firm survey data to reach that FDI flows to China are related to the new product introduction probability. They found that increased FDI presence in a given industry leads to be more imitation, but not necessary to be more innovation by domestic firms. Zhou (2006) employs a cross-industry survey of Chinese enterprises to prove that superior financial performance is related rather than imitating innovating firms.

Manova and Zhang (2012) publish another related study, which shows exporters are using imports of higher quality to produce exports of more top quality. They enhance these results by showing how to import selection can lead to increased exports and increased productivity among imitating Chinese firms by imitating foreign firms. A relevant strand of studies shows FDI spillover effects. Empirical evidence was inconclusive despite numerous theoretical models outlining different channels. In China, Swenson and Chen (2014) analyze how the presence of multinational companies in the city-industry affects the quality, frequency, and survival of private companies' new export transactions and finds evidence of spillovers.

In 2011, an investigation of Ali et al. was conducted to discover the influences of technology spillovers on the overall efficiency of the manufacturing sector in Pakistan and to verify the impact of growth in capital stock, staff employment, partnership with the academe and transfer of technology on the overall efficiency and technology spillovers. Using "descriptive statistics," correlation, regression and reliability testing on "SPSS-17", findings revealed that

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spillover of used physical equipment and machinery from zones enhances productivity growth of local companies. They also found that the textile sector is less productive, although it is the largest manufacturing sector, while the tobacco sector is the most productive. Other potential industries are the automotive, petroleum, and manufacturing of machinery and equipment. The study also realized the presence in all sectors of horizontal and vertical spillovers with varying intensities and their positive effect on productivity.

However, some researchers argued that FDI does not bring any technical change but only enhances technical efficiency. For instance, a study of Thang (2013), which used data from firms in Vietnam (enterprise census, 2000-2005), reveals more of that inside. The study used a time-varying stochastic frontier approach to decompose the change in productivity into technical change, changes in technical efficiency, and changes in scale efficiency.

The proof from forecasting the spillovers in each corresponding component suggests that horizontal FDI leads to negative spillovers, primarily to technical change, but positive spillovers to functional effectiveness. Vertical FDI also has mixed effects on the productivity of domestic-owned firms. This point of view seems to make more sense in many developing countries since imitating the local company might not be able to conceive the secret of production that makes the foreign firm unique, but the only uncomplicated process of the production.

The similar argument of Vater (2011) found if FDI involves activities for knowledge sourcing, innovation, the domestic firms' productivity. This study uses data from the manufacturing sector in Estonia at the firm-level panel to investigate various channels through which FDI affects domestic firms. He finds no evidence of an impact of overseas ventures on the output rate of local incumbents based on the instrumental variables approach. There is, however, a positive connection between entry of overseas venture and spillover measures. Inflows of the overseas venture to a sector are associated with increased knowledge flows to domestic firms and increased innovation activities.

Apart from measuring firms' performance through export impact, Aggarwal (2005) asks how the cost-decrease estimates recognized in zonal approaches influence firm execution in Bangladesh, India, and Sri Lanka, concentrating on fare broadening and only on EPZs. Her examination of her study is principally founded on three kinds of cost decrease measures gave to organizations by EPZs: framework, area, and administrative/administration measures. Zeng (2016) claimed that her research couldn't effectively display how having a place with an SEZ affects the firm's execution, given that she has no counterfactual to assess firms outside of zones.

In a consequent paper, nonetheless, the creators note Aggarwal et al. (2008), utilizing similar information: Although information impediments make it try to assess the institutional attributes and exchange execution crosswise over zones and nations, the relative evaluation endeavored in this examination yields a few discoveries. The zone area, access to and nature of

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foundation, and the administrative structure of the zones appear to impact the exhibition of SEZs (Aggarwal, 2007).

Nevertheless, evaluating the direct bearing of special economic zones at the firm level and the impact on domestic enterprises is a challenge, partly due to a lack of data and partly due to the difficulty of finding suitable enterprises that can serve as “controls” for making valid comparisons. While there is no excellent or appropriate comparison amid companies inside and outside the zones, some studies attempted to focus on the behavior of firms within SEZs. Yet, the study is out of date.

b. Firms’ HRM Policies and Activities

One of the principally intended contributions from the SEZs is to provide technology, knowledge, and skills to the host country's HR. However, it has not been determined to what extent this takes place (Madani, 1999). Experimental investigations have additionally demonstrated that the effect of MNEs on group-specific businesses isn't apparent, even though bunches can create noteworthy overflows of efficiency from FDI. This happens basically in previous groupings, and now and again, where MNEs bring R&D to the host nation and have assumed a significant job in current innovation. The curiosity will be moved to the neighborhood economy at a later stage to assemble the nation's human capital ability to enhance and set up its focused edge (Gugler and Brunner, 2007).

Ding et al. (1997) referenced that HRM practices were portrayed by arranged occupation assignment, lifetime employments ensured, and an unlimited pay framework before China's economic change in 1978. Occupation distribution was put together not to justify, yet on political thought. Workers were not able to start with one employment then onto the next or even development dependent on reasonableness through their vocation stepping stool. The concentrated compensation framework depended on uniformity, making it hard to discover contrasts among workers regardless of the weight holes in their assignments or jobs.

In this stream of thinking, HRM techniques, including recruitment methods, remuneration grades and programmers, production assessment, advancement metrics, and training and development, were reviewed in Shenzhen SEZ firms. FIEs have played a critical role in developing HRM activities within SEZs. Empirical results showed that the management of HR was inclined to adopt certain Western manner practices while maintaining other existing practices; according to the free market rule, job allocation tended to be de-centralized; and job movement occurred too often, and salary is inclined to be based on merit rather than a political choice. Surprisingly, empirical data showed that FIEs introduced their modern management techniques and ultimately influenced the HRM practices of the host country (Ding et al., 1997).

A similar research stream of Ying and Malcolm (2002) demonstrated the evaluation of HRM of enterprises in Hainan island, China. According to fieldwork interviews in eight enterprises, including two state-owned enterprises and six own foreign enterprises. The research

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attempts to study HRM characteristics such as employment relation, job design, employee involvement, and industrial relation vis-s-vis the economic reform in China in an SEZ. The research outcomes demonstrated that the evaluation of such enterprises depends on the market, vocational, cultural, and ownership variables.

Moreover, Warner (2008) also conducted a study to advance the perception of theoretical and definitive challenges HRM face as a growing field. In the wake of covering a broad scope of both political and observational proof, including contextual analyses, the creator asserted that assuming HRM is adequately implanted as Chinese practice is exceptionally untimely, in spite of good faith that there is a focalized course between universal HRM and Chinese administration. Those researches illustrated a similar result that most of the Chinese firm inside and outside SEZs embraces modern HR management from foreign-invested enterprises while maintaining Chinese characteristics.

As to HRM arrangements in SEZs or EPZs, the connection among SEZs and distinctive work showcase results, running from the impact of SEZs on employment creation to working conditions and unionization, has been impressively examined. Cirera and Lakshman (2017) gather an informational index of 59 such examinations to research the connection among SEZs and the states of business and wages. In creating nations, they center explicitly around the opportunity of affiliation, wellbeing and security, and working hours. The aftereffects of the examination suggested that there are no reliable confirmations that activity creation in the zone is included.

A study by Ver Beek (2001) identifies information on 12 factors, including both economic and social factors, which both provide an overview of the maquiladora workers' situation in Honduras' EPZs. Second, it uses the maquiladoras' first-time applicants for an alternative control group. Finally, this article introduces collected data in 1998 in Honduras, offering perspectives into the industry as it operates in post-NAFTA and non-Mexican environments. In 1998, the research found less unionization within the EPZs in Honduras.

Zohir (2001) compiled data from two surveys of readymade garment workers (RMG) from the Bangladesh Institute for Development Studies (BIDS) conducted in 1990 and 1997. The article, over time, compared not only men and women workers in the garment industry but also compared workers in RMG units in EPZ and Non-EPZ areas. The results in this article claim that women have been empowered by employment in the garment industry, their mobility increased, and their individual choice expanded.

But at the cost of their health and increased risk of harassment, they have achieved this. The assessment in this paper also demonstrates that overall worker well-being has improved over the period 1990-1997, although unionization is prohibited within the EPZs of Bangladesh, but not outside. Hence, except for those cases in which unionization is legally banned in EPZs, it is difficult to conclude whether restrictions on union rights can be attributed to EPZs or general failures in domestic labor institutions.

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Comparative research stream, Islam, and Siengthai (2009) embraced insightful research on the effect on employment fulfillment and hierarchical execution of laborers' nature of work-life (QWL). QWL is conjectured to impact the exhibition of the association straightforwardly or by implication. Inside the EPZ organizations, a poll review was led with non-administrative workers who are principally associated with the generation procedure. A basic strategy for random testing has been utilized, and roughly 216 example reactions have been returned and utilized. Information was examined using engaging insights, chi-square tests, and relapse investigation to examine the defined theory. While QWL is decidedly identified with hierarchical execution, the findings recommend that it isn't significant as speculated. There is, be that as it may, a positive and considerable connection among QWL and the activity fulfillment of representatives.

In 2015, Sviatschi conducted an investigation that examined the relation between female career and the establishment of free trade zones in every province of the Dominican Republic. Her research revealed that young women received higher education during the initial period of the zones' development. After the 2000s, the education rate among young women in the free zones has gradually declined due to the end of the US Trade Agreement and higher competition with Asian countries. She also found that the opening of those free zones also impacts on the marriage market. Those educated young female married later found better matches and had a better child and financial plan.

2.3 Literature on Special Economic Zone in Laos Context

2.3.1 Background and Management of Laos SEZs

Since the sixteenth century, the idea of regions with exceptional benefits, generally called free zones, has been introduced, yet the first SEZ was established in Ireland in 1959 (Guangwen, 2005). The world still had just 79 SEZs in 1975 (ILO, 2007). SEZs increased universal prevalence after China's monetary changes during the 1980s, and by 1995, there were around 500 SEZs around the world. This number was assessed to be somewhere in the range of 3,000 and 5,000 zones just 10 years after the fact. In low/medium-income nations, most SEZs are found (Carter and Harding, 2010).

Laos SEZ was presented in 2001 to enhance the investment climate. The main objective of establishing Laos SEZ in that time was to promote foreign investment in the country by eliminating investment barriers such as tax, duties, and investment procedures. It is believed that SEZs will contribute to national GDP and HR development in the country.

In 2003, the first pilot zone was established in the Southern part of Laos, namely 'Savanh-Seno SEZ.' Later, the other two SEZs were built in the Northern provinces, including Golden Triangle SEZ and Boten-Mohan SEZ. Until 2010, to implement and actively operationalize the

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new investment promotion law, alongside sectoral development in the 7th Five-Year, the Lao government has set the targets to develop further the new and existing SEZs that have been established (8th NSEDP, 2016). Map 2 demonstrated Laos SEZs across the country.

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Project Calling Listed, 2016.

Map 2: 12 Laos special economic zones (Adapted from Project Calling Listed, 2016)

The main Laos SEZ Decree No.443/PM reported in October 2010, portrays the capacity of the National Committee for Special Economic Zone (NCSEZ). Article 2 characterizes NCSEZ as a legislature specific office and helps the administration in driving and dealing with the SEZs. The seat is a Deputy Prime Minister, pursued as appointee seats or board of trustees' individuals by the

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related priests. NCSEZ has a Secretariat (S-NCSEZ) as the NCSEZ's standing organization. However, NCSEZ is a non-standing. It is connected to the Prime Minister's Office's authoritative structure.

Until recently, the management of Laos SEZs was adjusted to attached to new development policies in Laos. Five-year development plans in Laos are essential guidelines for administration. The plan's support will foster policy implementation. To achieve the development goal based on the 8th National Development meeting in 2016, the Government of Laos has set an average Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth target of more than 8 percent per annum from now until 2017.

To reach this, Laos' government requires a total investment inflow of at least 30 percent of total GDP, or USD 15.8 billion, of which USD 8.9 billion will come from FDI, equivalent to 56 percent of total investment (Oecd.org, 2017). These targets show that FDI will be given priority by the government and focus on receiving “decent quality and sustainable investment.” The Laos government is, therefore, pushing forward to attract foreign investors to invest in different sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, tourism, and services. To peruse the objective and coherent administration and management of Laos SEZs, NCSEZ has moved to the Ministry of Planning and Investment and become Special Economic Zones Management Office (SEZO). Two different investment windows are operating based on types of investment (Figure 7).

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Ministry of Planning and Investment, 2016.

Figure 5: Investment system of Laos (Ministry of Planning and Investment, 2016)

According to figure 7, there general domestic and foreign business licenses can be registered in the Ministry of Industry and Commerce and concession businesses, and enterprises who wish to operate their business within Special Economic Zones can be registered with the

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Ministry of Planning and investment. Until 2018, the new decree 188/GM regarding new management and development of Laos SEZs were established. The history in Laos is short and can be distinguished into three important events summarized in the following Figure 8.

Figure 6: Laos SEZs development time series (Adapted from Laos SEZs strategy and development, 2017)

2.3.2 Macroeconomic Condition of Laos SEZs

2.3.2.1. Export

The World Bank (2018) reported that current investment in SEZs had facilitated exports outside the clothing industry. Over the past five years, the total value of manufacturing exports rose from about US\$ 270 million in 2013 to US\$ 780 million in 2017 (Figure 9), mainly driven by exports of electronics, telecommunications, and electrical equipment from SEZs (Savanh-SENO and VITA Park) and food and beverages. In 2017, the manufacturing industry cover half of total

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export had customarily focused on the processing of clothing and food and beverages, electrical, and electronic parts (Figure 10). This demonstrates that Lao can participate effectively in the regional value chain under an appropriate business environment. Addressing restrictions on doing business outside the zones can create additional export potential.

Figure 7: Rapid growth of electronic parts from SEZs (World Bank, 2018)

Figure 8: Export share of emerging electronics and telecommunication products (World Bank, 2018)

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Laos SEZ development report, 2018.

Table 1: Export from Laos SEZs as of 2013-2017 (Laos SEZs development report, 2018)

Table 1 clearly depicts that physical exports in the year 2013-2017 accounted for 12.1% of the total export within five years. The export growth from SEZs jumped from US\$ 270,000,000 to US\$ 1,850,000,000. The country's increased exports bring more revenue to the state that enhances economic growth. SEZ helps to create a country's balanced economic growth if adequately located and implemented, leading to local talent being exploited and contributing to increased economic activity in the area. The outstanding figure of SEZs export is mainly from electronic and spare parts manufacturing in Savan-Seno SEZ and Vientiane Industrial Park, which foreign manufacturers are starting to get in place on their productions.

Based on the zones' report conducted by the SEZ management and development office, it appeared that imports accounted for US\$ 2,315,546,050, which twice much of export. When looked at more detail, the reason behind the unbalanced amount of trade in SEZs might be due to some of the new other zones that are on the initial stage of infrastructure development and construction. Most of developers and investors are importing heavily on construction materials and other construction equipment, which most of them are exempted from import tax. Although the import amount is more than export, infrastructure and construction development shall provide some genuine benefits for locals surround by the zone. Before that, most of the SEZs located in the area have no or very few roads, water, electricity, and other facilities to support business activities and living in the area.

2.3.2.2. Investment

The number of companies invested within SEZs from 2015-2016 has jumped double from 213 to 410 companies (Figure 11). In 2016, two new zones were established, such as Champasak SEZ and Luangprabang SEZ, located in two major provinces in Southern and Northern part of Laos. The most invested zone is Savan-Seno SEZ, where 105 companies are located. Furthermore, based on table 2, Golden Triangle SEZ, and other several zones developed by Chinese are the major investors in Laos SEZs in terms of investment capital. Golden Triangle SEZ is the biggest investor at all times. The focus of the zone is the service and trading sector cover most of the sectors across Laos SEZs (Figure 12).

Figure 9: Number of companies in Laos SEZs as of 2015-2017 (Laos SEZs development report,2018)

SEZ	Registered Capital	Investment Plan	Real Investment	Percentage to total real investment
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Table 2: Investment amount of Laos SEZs as of 2016-2017 (adapted from SEZ Management and Development Office report, 2018)

Figure 10: Investment Sectors as of 2017 (Adapted from SEZ Management and Development Office report, 2018)

2.3.2.3. Employment and gross domestic products

The numbers of foreign-invested enterprises have increased during the last few years; the total employment created through Laos SEZs has also increased. The SEZs contribute to creating jobs and income, with the potential to increase local workers ' opportunities. Overall work in the zones (foreign and domestic labor) rose by 60 percent from 11,328 in 2015 to 24,891 in 2017 (Figure 13). Lao workers account for nearly half of the zones ' total employment.

The two export processing zones, Savan-Seno and VITA Park represent almost 80 percent of the total number of Lao workers working across Laos SEZs, however. In provinces where labor migration across the border is common, the existence of such zones and progress seems to provide options for local workers.

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at SEZ management and development office report, 2018.

Figure 11: Numbers of domestic and foreign workers within SEZs has increased double from 2015-2017 (Adapted SEZ Management and Development Office report, 2018)

Along with the soaring numbers of export, investment, and employment, SEZs contribute only a small fraction of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Zeng (2015) implied that GDP contribution is significant for the establishment of SEZs and it takes time (typically 15-25 years) to demonstrate results. However, based on Laos SEZs economic report, the contribution of Laos SEZs to GDP is marginal (Less than 1 percent from 2013-2017) and has not seen any improvement during the last couple of years. Yet, measuring the effectiveness of SEZs by GDP is too broad since the recovery of GDP depends on various factors in the zone. A number of investment impact on foreign earnings are an example of dependants. In broader research, GDP can only enhance a basic understanding of the way zone contribute to the domestic economy.

Although its contribution to national GDP is very less, it does imprecise to assume that Laos SEZs have no benefits at all. Based on the above exports, investment, and employment, the results of Laos SEZs have been quite mixed. Additionally, Laos has a brief history of SEZ development comparing with adjoining countries which are composed of an industrial background. While some SEZs were just established a few years ago, some older SEZs are starting to demonstrate results in terms of export, investment, and employment. Therefore, this research must analyze zone by zone regarding its benefits.

2.4 Literature on Human Resource Development (HR Development)

1.1.4.1 Role and Indicator on HR Development

The development of human assets is the foundation for ideal financial progress. Practical studies of Romer (1986), Lucas (1988), and Nelson and Phelps (1966) implied that nations are gradually focusing on this aspect while creating plans for the future growth of the economy. Natural resources are not deemed as the sole contributor to progress anymore. The students are convinced that countries with precious resources generally change their economy to natural resources. Consequently, this may cause “Dutch Disease.” Dutch Disease slows down economic growth compared to countries with limited natural resources. It will create a perception that natural resources are more of “a curse than a gift,” stated by Sachs and Warner (2001).

Coff (2002) reports that “human capital is the set of knowledge, skills, and abilities” or KA where they are categorized as tacit or explicit. Explicit KSA means countries and businesses can replicate effortlessly. It is made inexpensive and accessible for everyone. Meanwhile, tacit KSA means economies and firms can pursue on the specific nature of the business. It is not simple to replicate or transmit it (Crook et al. 2011). In terms of economics, diverse economies, as well as firms, strive to measure human capital. The first research stream seeks to measure the level of human resource development through available human capital or skill and income of individuals.

According to Hanushek (2013), Sir William Petty notes that human capital is for exploring the supremacy of England, the consequences of the economy resulting from migration, and money preexisting as the end of the war. On the other hand, others viewed human capital as the “Father of Wealth,” which is vital in approximating the nation’s capital. Sir William approximates the worth of human capital through a calculation of salary to eternity at the interest rate of the market. Nevertheless, he fails to mention the rate linked to each maintenance cost wherein calculating such charge could be referred to as insufficient estimation of the value of the human capital, (Hull, 1899; Kiker, 1966).

After degrading for over fifty years, the notion of human capital was revived by the standardized and significant contribution of Theodore Schultz (1961), Gary Becker (1964), and Jacob Mincer (1974), and others. Their study resulted in fast development in both the assumption and practicality of human capital to a variety of topics. The ideas of Mincer were fundamental in directing empirical work. In examining the concepts of human capital, it was integrally an evasive idea that required an acceptable rating. Challenging that differences in profit, for example, were brought about by contrasting views on human capital that approximation of human capital may well emerge out of monitored salary disparities.

Mincer maintained that an indispensable encouragement for studies was accelerating the people’s knowledge that it appeared better to quantify human capital by how long people finish

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their education. Critically, completing school was habitually estimated and detailed. Mincer pursued this with an examination of how salary differences could be altogether clarified by educational accomplishment and by investing in “on-the-job training” (Hanushek,2013). His idea was broadly acknowledged and has managed the experimental methodology of a reasonable, more significant part of exact investigations in financial aspects as of the current times.

The second research stream on measuring HR development belonging to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), which is focused on creating a better life for the people, has been publishing a yearly report since 1990 called the Human Development Report (HDR). In the report, “human development” is evaluated using a gauge, which is composed of three mechanisms: the first evaluates the lifespan, which tells about health and living conditions; the second evaluates the level of education, and the third one evaluates income per capita.

It seems like the level of education or skill, and income per capita were indicators derived from the previous research stream. Thus, an indicator was added, such as the gauge of health and living conditions. This marker is intended to be essential and depends on the most utilized monetary factors in estimating human development where those factors are accessible in nations' authentic information. Although this marker gets numerous reactions and ought not to be utilized as the sole pointer of estimation, it is broadly utilized by government lawmakers to create necessary human advancement plans (Wilson et al., 2007).

The third indicator is gender equality, which became an increasingly significant indicator of measuring the level of social civilization during the last few decades. Verick (2018) implied that as more females enter the workforce, economies can become quicker in light of higher work inputs. Females' supply of work expands family unit livelihoods, which enables their families to escape destitution and add utilization of products and services. In the meantime, as nations build-up, the female's capacities regularly improve, while social requirements debilitate, empowering the females to take part in work outside the home. Female employment is both a driver and an outcome of development during the industrial revolution and, as of late, in East and parts of Southeast Asia.

1.4.2 Strain and Confidence of the Political Economy and Ramification of HR Development in SEZs

In the perfect scenario of SEZ, zones could both, directly and indirectly, generate job opportunities by accelerating demand for domestic production. Additionally, new foreign firms that invest there can expand technological expertise beyond the boundaries of the zone (FIAS, 2008). Hence, encouraging HRD in the region. Yet, governments that do not enforce beneficial measures nationally may seem strange instead of restricting them to some regions. There are three reasons worth reflecting on this. One is that zones create clusters that would not otherwise come

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about, due to the limitation of businesses to unify their sectors as effectively as possible (Farole and Akinci, 2011). Second, governments have no idea of the consequences of such measures and SEZs establish experimental areas for trying them out (Sit, 1985). Third, national reforms are impracticable because of opposition from the political upper-class or the public. SEZs can then be a second-best policy choice that is politically feasible.

The concerns of insufficient information and adverse opportunities are at the very core of a stable system for the political economy. The problem of knowledge means that government bureaucracies can not endorse technological advancement by preparing economic production and allocating resources (Lavoie, 1985). Since they can not gather all the required knowledge, they can not determine the most efficient production mechanism or plan the cooperative construction of an organization. It's not just the knowledge they would need to be distributed across society. It is also of the sort that is not usefully communicable to others (Hayek, 1945). A working market relies on insights that businessmen and investors can only acquire through years of practice.

A centralized model stresses the importance of government involvement in education and training given HRD in SEZ and is marked by intense government involvement. This model utilizes a top-down way to develop educational standards in a country. The central government invests in comprehensive education and trains programmers in cooperation with the local government and is often driven by a collectivist philosophy, as in China or Mexico (Gold et al . , 2013). Yang, Zhang, and Zhang (2004) note that the responsibility for preparing, executing, and reviewing HRD programmers and policies lies solely with the central government model. Implementing an HRD is also exclusively the government's responsibility (Wang, 2008).

Sector plays a limited role in the preparation, execution, and assessment of HRD measures. Therefore the void in needed skills in the private sector still needs to be filled. Another result of adopting this model is that, as in France, all administrative responsibilities are imposed on the governments. French companies have raised training costs as every company delivering HRD has been paid a levy by the government. The administration of this system is a cost to the French Government. Since the budget is limited, low-income countries like Laos can not enforce the centralized model.

Meanwhile, democratic policy-making may be how the government can assign such important decisions to citizens with high experience (Moberg, 2015; Farole and Kweka, 2011; Strong and Himber, 2010). One simple reason government should decentralize decision-making is that market forces' drive to engage in HRD programs is to preserve their advantage over their closest business competitors. The bulk of the training and education programs are supported by the private sector.

Lee (2004) contends that the free market model is independent because people have the duty to promote their personal development and growth. Local governments, often well-oriented in local circumstances, may have a clear understanding of the potential of a zone. Local officials may also analyze how conditions on the ground change and agree on policy changes more quickly.

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In this way, they will imitate private investors' reactions to market dynamics. Decentralisation also enables the authorities of the region to check many different models. They can recognize and replicate measures that function elsewhere and so learn from other SEZs. Therefore they are less likely to significantly miscalculate the consequences of various policies. In addition, one mistake committed by a zone regulator affects one SEZ in the country rather than all of them, as in the case of national SEZ policies. Local policy-makers should serve as entrepreneurs and enact policies in a trial-and-error manner, turning SEZs into policy-making test beds.

Canada is one of the progressive countries that has followed this model, according to Cooper (2004). On the national level, however, there are a few assessments for decentralized education. Most experts contend against this because the 'history, politics, and (decentralization) hierarchical frameworks are too idiosyncratic to be studied or discussed' (Rhoten, 2000). However, a superior SEZ program does not suffice to solve the knowledge gap. Like other policies that give preferential treatment, SEZs generate rent-seeking mechanisms and, as such, incentives for policy-makers to use them for their benefits.

Democratically elected politicians seek support from the public and votes in the upcoming election, while administrators, on behalf of their department, want prominent titles, bigger offices, more employees, more leisure and sometimes trips to a fun resort. For example, to prosper from SEZs, their regulators may require contracts to be awarded to those offering the highest bribes, or expect bribes from companies to invest in the zone. Policy makers in the government may receive bribes and favors from local officials who are keen to see a special zone created within their town. Legislators may ask bribes from SEZ operators or grant contracts for zone infrastructure to people willing to pay them for the privilege. An infrastructure created in this manner will likely be of inferior quality.

Unless the SEZs are built to act as a mechanism for corruption, transformation into effective SEZs would be inherently difficult. In the 1990s, the experience with SEZs in Russia demonstrates that zones are at the forefront of corruption and crime. In their SEZs the legal framework ended up becoming much more unstable for investments than the rest of the nation. A 2005 reform aimed at discouraging corruption saw the Russian government create SEZs with more federal regulation and fewer tax advantages. Although corruption appears to have decreased, little success in economic activity has flourished in its place. The changes also did not alter Russia's public view of the zones as centres of corruption (Tuominen and Lamminen, 2008).

Some institutions can tackle the problem on incentives. Public officials also benefit through supporting SEZ schemes in a working democratic and accountable process. If they can take credit for good SEZ initiatives, they will reap public support and electoral votes. If there is a strong connection between politics and economic results, they have a role in developing growth that promotes zone schemes. Political and fiscal decentralization are directly linked to a politician's views with his chance of reelection. In combination, democracy and decentralization also provide the incentive for local officials to ensure that their bureaucracies do not participate in corruption

at the lower level. Unlike a central government, these local officials understand how incentives work to build a clean slate for their agencies. Even in a non-democratic setting, this principle also applies to any system that rewards low-level officials for impressive SEZ results.

1.4.3 Multi-National Enterprises and HR Development

Governments in developing countries have allotted more significant funds on schooling in the previous two decades. But comparing to other nations, “reveal a little relationship between public spending on education and outcomes once country income levels are considered” (Lipsy and Sjöholm, 2004). One cause for this is that spending levels will be spread over an array of quality and distributional outcomes. After limiting labor, an inadequate supply of graduates will result in an undesirable effect on income per capita in many nations (López, 1998).

Concerning FDI, the proof on OECD nations demonstrates that multinational partners of MNEs have advanced work profitability in contrast to local firms. But Cortes et al. (1998) pointed out that Thailand’s TNCs contributed less in the skilled workforce in terms of the total workforce than did firms owned locally throughout various industries like electric and technology. The number of well-trained workforces from American and European associates is 16%, Japanese affiliates are 15%, and in newly industrialized Asian enterprises’ affiliates is 10%, whereas local firms are 18%. These figures are attributed to low-technology used in assembly plants despite being industries in advanced technology (UNCTAD, 1999).

Enhancing human capital can be connected in a number of practices to the matter of transferring specific information. In Thailand, the country has proposed to generally lower the degree of transmission of particular information and management techniques, as well as training, for one or both of these two motives. First, most FDI inflows use low-to-medium technology which need not entail much skill, alongside less obligation for MNCs to capitalize in HR. Second, even in advanced technology firms, the far-reaching gap in technology has limited the skill of the resident workers to acquire knowledge since the burden is either so huge that makes it hard to link, or the seeming gap merely discourages MNCs from trying to tie it.

In Thailand, the training program is run cooperatively by intercontinental chambers of commerce from different nations and its government in an advisory group (Brimble et al., 2002). Singapore has set its course in investing in schooling and training in order to attract FDI and at the same time encouraging FDI to improve (Lall, 1996); for instance, Wong (1997) discloses how the régime has employed the making of jobs in inducing transnational corporation (TNC) upgrades in the industry of hard drive. The relationship amongst the FDI and the enhancement and development of human capital will depend on the TNC’s corporate strategy and market orientation or at least be inextricably linked with it:

For example, a focus on Japanese associates in Brazil discovered that the inception of excellent loops and timely production systems needed workers with superior skills. These companies required employees who attained at least primary education (eight years). If they cannot

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hire enough suitable employees, they capitalized on short-term courses in literacy, math, and group-work methods (Ashforth and Humphrey, 1993). A comparable technique was performed in TNCs in car manufactures in Bangkok, wherein firms needed related training (van Assouw et al.,1999).

In Malaysia's case, Best (2001) distinguishes critical developments as the ability to attract Multinational Corporations from the level of skills, as well as the relation between these two aspects. The links are usually involved with economic and industrial processes. First, to upgrade the skills was needed. On the immediate impact of MNCs on the ability of the labor force in view of the MNCs' very particular endeavors, it is uncertain that such constructive outcome has been moderately constrained, undoubtedly with respect to the size of the assignment on account of Malaysia.

Moreover, overseas ventures might provide several benefits, first, by influencing domestic companies' behavior along with the effect of knowledge transmission through labor turnover. And second by staff in the MNCs transitioning not to prevailing local firms but in establishing their own business. Both of these elements have worked to a certain extent in Malaysia, and government policies have been successful in terms of output and employment, but Best (2001) advises that might be stuck in instead zones they offer low value in return.

Collecting more systematic evidence on these issues would make it possible to draw stronger conclusions and develop more positive political implications. The information gathered by multinational organizations and governments tends to be too comprehensive to permit the essential discrepancies to ascertain the characteristics of the FDI, the bases and results of investing in enhancing human capital, and so on. Testing the underlying procedures definitely necessitates collecting information specifically intended for a particular task. The "Director of Technology Transfer at the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Environment" reported no surveillance of outlay activities in promoting the transfer of technology, source connections, and improvement of skills (OECD, 1999). To investigate these topics, deeper might need collecting such information throughout nations. Doing so will take time.

UNCTAD (2000) determines that TNCs are inclined to capitalize on extra training compared to domestic companies; to become more conscious of a new wave in training and the necessity to create new skills; to become more capable of using up-to-date materials and techniques on training, and of focusing more on training on worldwide markets. In Malaysia, Intel and Matsushita are quoted as instances of TNCs that have set up training facilities in ensuring that the demand for specialized skills is achieved. However, UNCTAD (2000) determines that host nations no longer depend on TNCs in attaining a more comprehensive or evolving need for expertise.

TNCs engage in technologies suitable for domestic graduates and primarily develop competent workers to operate these technologies. They are inclined not to participate in improving the abilities needed for advanced technology as these arise. In general, such capitalization is costlier and require more time, and the needs must be met by educational institutions. In other words, improving the overall level of skills and providing superior training should be pondered by

the host countries. Such upgrades indeed may be utilized in attracting inward FDI of higher quality and inducing existing investors to shift toward more complex activities. (UNCTAD, 2000).

However, the best-case scenario implied that MNEs can play a decisive role in a host economy by giving resources that would otherwise not be available for capital, technology, and management. Such transfer of funds can boost the host economy's economic growth (Hill, 2000). Through knowledge transmission, MNEs enhance the host country's stock knowledge through training, shadowing, and the allocation of new management and executive practice. Skills from expatriates acquired by MNEs can also bring significant advantages to the host countries. Beneficial spin-off effect arises when domestic laborers trained in executive, fiscal, and specialist positions in a foreign subsidiary of MNE resign from the company and aid in establishing local businesses. Parallel advantages will occur when a foreign MNE's superior management skills encourage local providers, traders, and competitions to develop their managerial skills.

Fresh skills are gained through explicit and implicit training. Training in multinational businesses may be considered high quality if only the most active companies deal. When workers rejoin the local workforce, they take these skills with them. Sometimes training received from multinational firms can be deemed under the general title of "organization and management," which means that the host nation will take advantage of MNC's 'superior management.' The following paragraphs discuss further management behavior, including policies and practices of MNEs that might benefit the human capital of the host country.

1.4.4 Theories on Managing and Developing HR

Scholars have suggested several descriptions for HRM, from a short and basic definition to a long and detailed explanation. In short, HRM is better described as the "management method of human resources to achieve the goal of the company." It is said that the method of managing human resources involves the recruiting and selection method, wages and benefits, labor and workplace relations, and even ensuring the protection and health of workers within organizations. At the other hand, the researchers and authors have suggested various meanings for HRD. These other interpretations ranged from an individual researcher or theorist's perspective to a country's perception on HRD.

Moreover, theorists have even attempted to define HRD from both a global and international point of view. Evidently, a lot of definitions have been proposed even before HRD emerged in the 1970s. A 1970s description by Nadler and Nadler characterized HRD as "a set of coordinated practices that are performed within a defined period and intended to bring about behavioral change" through training. Desimone, Werner & Harris (2002) 's latest concept for HRD was described as "a collection of organized and scheduled activities developed by an institution to provide its members with the opportunities to develop the skills required to meet current and future work demands."

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These organized and planned tasks have shown to involve training and development, career planning and development, performance evaluations, and change management. This practice is referred to as continuous professional education and advancement. Continuous professional education and development programs are, to all intents and purposes, the same as in training and development but are labeled separately related to the education and advancement of professionals.

Some writers have historically proposed that HRD is an aspect of HRM in which the former promotes the latter's role in the training and development of employees and the concept of training and development fitting in or integrating with HRM as in the 'HRM's wheel' (Guest, 1987). All four aspects of HRD, namely training and development, performance evaluation and management, career preparation and growth as well as change management elements, were promoted as being placed under HRM's 'umbrella' or role along with other elements such as recruiting and staffing, wages and benefits, workplace and labor relations, as well as safety & health.

However, because of the HRM function's uncertain role and obligations, HRD has been rearranged to define its purpose in supplementing HRM rather than aiding it. Therefore an analogous pathway also known as the parallel nexus of HRM and HRD was implemented. McGoldrick & Stewart (1996) concluded that HRM and HRD, due to their similarities and focus on corporate strategy elements, are parallel paths of HRM and HRD. The analogous pathway as indicated by McGoldrick and Stewart (1996) means that HRM has the purpose of hiring, choosing, encouraging and rewarding, while HRD's role is to offer the chosen and qualified human capital with learning, education and training. Both the HRM and HRD pathways clearly have their own set of plans and strategies, as well as operational support in the business system.

As for HRD, Yorks (2005) portrays the area of HRD as experiencing a similar development. Yorks explores HRD's early roots in adult education, behaviorism, and organizational development, and then delivers ways in which HRD has become largely correlated to both theory and strategy. Yorks (2005) concludes his research by addressing the impacts of technology, globalization, and the complexities of maintaining a strategic orientation on issues of the workforce. There were similar points made by other HRD researchers (Jacobs & Park, 2009; Van Woerkom & Poell, 2010).

The notion that both HRD and HRM have been criticized for their relative lack of theory, lack of policy, and lack of specific consideration or involvement in foreign and global concerns (e.g., Grieses, 2003; McLean & McLean, 2001; Wright & Boswell, 2002; Yawson, 2013) suggests in this direction from a primary emphasis on practice towards a greater focus on theory, policy, and global/international matters. While both leading professional organizations (ASTD and SHRM) are currently addressing the importance of strategic matters, an observer on either organization websites may wonder where, in reality, this strategic focus can be identified.

Both areas continue to discuss semantic and philosophical problems related to their definition as a field and discipline (Chalofsky, 2007; Hamlin & Stewart, 2011; Kaufman, 2008; Keegan & Boselie, 2006; Lee, 2001; Mankin, 2001; Willis, 2011). While development is apparent,

both fields are still on course of being more theoretically and objectively rooted (Kozlowski & Salas, 2010; Wright & Boswell, 2002).

2.5 Literature on Human Resource Management of Multi-National Enterprises

International HRM (IHRM) is the way MNEs manage their HR internationally. In other words, traditionally, IHRM has surveyed how multinational associations manage their human resources across various nationwide backgrounds. The association that foresees people in the different official authorized and communal conditions must be mindful not only on permissible activities and not in other countries in the world, but also of cost-effective practices to the administration (Dowling, 2008). Ideally, strategic planning and strategic management will actively involve a company conducting international business. Even in this ideal world, all of the company's components will be incorporated into this plan and will engage in corresponding vital planning in their specializations. Central management generally reflects the range of competing movements and enterprise methods that managers hire in operating a firm and derive from the company's mission and vision.

In developing a competitive course, the administration says that “among all the paths and actions we could choose, we have decided to go in this direction and rely on these particular ways of doing business.” A plan indicates the commitment of an organization to specific markets, viable methods, and operational practices. The strategy of a business is, therefore, the “game plan” that its administration has to position the company in its selected talent pool, to invest in human capital in developing business capacity, to create sustainable competitive advantages, to please its clients and thus to achieve superior business performance. Strategies developed in most companies are derived from a degree of formality of “recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, performance appraisals, retention and labor union and relations.”

2.5.1 Degree of Formality

The most investigated feature of multinational and relative HRM has probably been the effects of originating and host countries. Typically, this study follows “institutional context” (DiMaggio and Powell, 2012) and “social context” (Hofstede, 2009). Much of this study shows that the HRM rules and practices of MNEs have a country of origin (e.g., Currie and Almond 2011; Bjorkman et al. 2007; Lavelle et al. 2010).

Another point is the farther the “social distances” between the head office and the branches, and the fewer MNEs will transfer operations. Therefore, when the cultural and institutional distance is more similar, more streamlining of activities is likely. Meanwhile, recognizing the

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effects of the presence of MNE methods of human resource management at the originating country, Pudelko and Harzing (2007) contend that global best practices are increasingly being adopted as an outcome of the organizations' desire to improve superiority by imitating leading and outwardly effective methods.

Management practices in MNEs spread worldwide has been argued for some time (Bartlett and Ghoshal, 2002). Referring to Pudelko and Harzing (2007), excessive competition and integration of the world market signify "the importance of learning from best practices defined by dominant economies has increased." Characteristically, due to the strength of these countries and the associated heritage of dominant economies, the impression of "best practices" has been attributed to the strategies used by ventures from the USA, Japan, and Germany (Smith and Meiksins 1995).

The United States of America is generally regarded as the chief model (Edwards and Kuruvilla, 2005). Current pragmatic studies pointed to a proof of a dominant outcome, namely that secondary methods in human resource management of Japanese and German MNEs converged to chief model in the US (Pudelko and Harzing 2007; 2008). The awareness of the effects of spillover, whether the methods of human resource management of multinational MNEs are alike with domestic companies, was also considered by the scholarship. (Turner et al. 1997).

While consistent results have not materialized throughout various research, cautious conclusions propose that human resource management is different from multinational MNEs to domestic companies (McGraw and Harley 2003). To be more precise, multinational MNEs have to observe local rules, regulations, and occasions so that they will look more recognized and cultured than domestic organizations in terms of methods in human resource management (McGraw and Harley 2003).

Geary and Roche's (2001) work is essential here, arguing that local businesses are "increasingly introducing new HR practices that are most often associated with MNCs." Both suggest that this is the influence of multinational companies portraying as examples of HRM to local companies. In 2005, Begley et al. recognized the importance of foreign investors in the United States of America as a training ground for Irish managers to facilitate the progress of a robust management framework and the relevance of US FDI. The research also found that Irish managers learned business and management skills from the US company.

Moreover, McDonnell et al. (2014) suggest that, unlike domestic firms, domestic MNEs are too often ignored as a critical distinction and the likelihood to offer varying perceptions. Compared to companies that only operate on the domestic market, local MNEs are highly likely to face the burdens of global competition it entails. (McGraw and Harley 2003). Therefore, local MNEs are highly expected to install more specialized management methods and activities to address these challenges. While this can be said as a probable scenario, on the ground, proof on MNE's practices in human resource management from minor, recently emerging countries is slightly small.

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Child and David (2001) have previously implied that MNEs can affect the framework of nationwide firms and the strategies implemented within the countries by organizations. Ferner and Varul (2000) emphasized “the positive and negative” capabilities of foreign firms’ innovations as a means of spreading administrative methods across different business systems of the host country.

In summary, it is possible to adopt a point of view that locally owned MNEs’ approach to HRM in a specific country considered as a late industrializer may be very similar to multinational businesses, partly because of burdens. Meanwhile, it can be argued that there would probably be a considerable variation because the formalization and complexity of human resource management were not a high priority to internationalizing local businesses (Monks et al. 2001).

2.5.2 HR Management Activities of FIEs

2.5.2.1 Recruitment and Selection

Employment and selection approaches are central to recruiting overseas (Do urrenba cher and Geppert 2010; Ando 2011). Four overseas recruitment methods are identified, namely “ethnocentric, polycentric, geocentric and egocentric” (Colling and Scullion, 2006). “The ethnocentric method supplies parent-country nationals (PCNs) hold executive levels in subsidiaries overseas, while the polycentric method does so with host-country nationals (HCNs).” “The geocentric method” uses high-quality talent, notwithstanding nationalities, for senior positions. Lastly, the “egocentric method” picks high-quality talent, but within a region. So, some benefits and drawbacks exist in each approach (e.g., Caligiuri and Colakoglu 2007; Dowling et al. 2008).

“Ethnocentric” approach's advantages are effective communication and transfer of knowledge and are easy to control. This method, however, limits opportunities for development for HCNs that can affect their confidence and can cause repatriation problems in the long term. In addition, hiring expats is usually costlier than HCNs, and expats may face issues on adjusting themselves to new working norms. HCNs, on the other hand, are accustomed to local cultures and labor atmosphere. (Do urrenba cher and Geppert 2010; Bruning et al., 2012). However, “the polycentric method” can lead to problems of harmonization and conduct. “The geocentric method” allows MNEs to carry out efficient administration and to enhance knowledge, invention, and implementation of a subsidiary through the facilitation of the process of integral learning (Gong 2003).

However, this method entails superior training and relocation expenses, and more significant problems work permit acquisition in host nations. “The geocentric method” facilitates the transfer of international managers but restricts career progression of a particular location and leads to regional federalism (Dowling et al. 2008). MNEs can implement various methods in recruiting from overseas based on diverse contexts of countries and firms.

2.5.2.2 Training and Development (T&D)

T&D is a critical factor from an economic perspective in advancing sustainable employment and, therefore, creates a competitive advantage for a country (Schultz, 1961; Ward and Kennedy, 1993). Blunch & Castro (2005) implied that at the company level, the requirement for training is considered as imperative “as workplaces become highly integrated with widespread organizational activities.” In the meantime, official and informal training can be given. Formal training is organized, while casual training does not have a foreordained substance or plan (Kessler, 2007). The kinds of official training can go from long haul thinks about under grant and apprenticeships to short workshops, courses, or varying media introductions.

Depending on who provides training content, the official workshop can be led inside or remotely. "In-house training" is a regularly firm-based workshop where the workshop content is established by the company staff to address the requirement of organizations and individual workers (Dawe, 2003). "Internal training" can be named at work and off-the-work. “At work training” usually conduct while the learner is performing standard assignments. One the other hand, off-the-work training, for the most part, happens outside the organization (Dawe, 2003).

Various factors such as size, types, application of technology, education of staff can determine the training activities of a company. It is argued that there is a higher likelihood of training for people with higher learning and more top education skills (Blunch and Castro, 2005). Booth and Snower (1996) found that low-ranking workers (e.g., clerical and manufacturing line workers) with low education tend to be caught in a low-training cycle or “low-skill, bad-job” trap. Aggarwal's (2007) similar arguments implied that labor in SEZs had been trapped in low-skilled jobs since SEZs were made up of low-tech manufacturing industries.

Furthermore, Hu (2004), Shen (2005), and Alalshiekh (2016) have estimated MNCs as making information overflows all through various methods. One of these is through training their overall workers. Moreover, remote responsibility for (outside value) was accounted for to have a positive relationship with additionally preparing in Mexico (Tan and Lopez-Acevedo, 2003), Taiwan, and Malaysia (Tan and Batra, 1996). MNCs in China have discovered the measure of preparing and advancement projects to be decidedly identified with direct remote venture (Shen and Darby, 2004).

2.5.2.3 Rewards

Remuneration and rewards are significant challenges for HR managers in all types of firms including MNEs because it influences and supervises the behavior of managers and employees around the world and has a substantial impact on firm performance, as there is evidence that compensation systems can increase organizational efficiency (Gross & Friedman, 2004). While

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for many decades practitioners as well as scientists have defined rewards as everything provided by the firm that benefits employees in a monetary way, awards today are described by Newman et al. (2016) as all “returns people receive from work,” including direct and indirect, as well as intrinsic and extrinsic, types of rewards (Manas & Graham, 2003) that can be classified into “monetary and non-monetary terminologies.”

Moreover, Newman et al. (2016) implied that "Complete Returns" structure, "financial prizes" comprise of basic pay, living legitimacy/cost, execution-related pay (for example short- and long-haul motivators) and worker advantages, for example, pay security, work-life equalization, and stipends. "Non-money related prizes" incorporate viewpoints, for example, acknowledgment and status, employer stability, work happiness, and opportunities for learning.

With ongoing globalization, MNEs face the challenges of managing rewards globally. Differentiating and integrating their reward rules and activities on a global scale according to the requirements of HQ and their subsidiaries are concerned among MNEs. As Sparrow (2002) states, “We see evidence both of international convergence around best practice coupled with an increasingly sophisticated awareness of the distinctive nature of rewards policies and behavior across countries.”

Considering this “convergence/divergence” debate and aiming at explaining these trends towards global standardization and local distinctiveness, involves the consideration of a variety of factors. The interplay between these factors has been attained by several outlines (e.g., Bloom, Milkovich, & Mitra, 2003; Schuler & Jackson, 2014); for example, according to the meta-framework of global wage by Dowling, Festing, and Engle (2017), the examination of international pay issues falls within two broad literature streams, characterized by a universalist paradigm, assuming global convergence of HRM activities, and a contextualistic paradigm, highlighting the constraints of such an approach (Brewster, 1999).

The stream following the universal paradigm claims that (the same) HRM activities can be applied effectively in different cultural and institutional settings, including compensation and rewards (Chênevert & Tremblay, 2011). This is often explained by the thesis that primarily takes a perspective from the firms themselves, i.e. “the resource-based view (Barney, 2001), resource dependence theory (Drees and Heugens, 2013; Hillman et al., 2019), behavioral theory (Larrazza-Kintana et al., 2007), new institutional economics (Furubotn and Richer, 2010) or knowledge-based perspectives (Fey & Furu, 2008)”.

The second stream of literature focuses on the impact of the context of companies and claims that firms should consider the external environment when designing HRM practices and policies. This approach draws from institutional theory, for example, “the national business system approach (Whitley, 1996) and cultural perspectives (Hofstede, 2003; House et al., 2004) or combinations of various factors in the sense of contextualization (Michailova, 2011)”. Localization and global alignment pressures are antagonistic, and the dominance of localization or alignment

with global reward balance has an impact on the worldwide reward approaches of MNEs (Kang & Shen, 2015).

The recent literature takes a more differentiated view and adds to the discussion on the simple dichotomy of convergence and divergence (Demirbag et al., 2016), suggesting explanations beyond the two dominant paradigms introduced above. For instance, there is evidence that various reward practices, i.e., “different elements of the reward mix, follow different patterns of localization and standardization and lead to higher complexity in the global reward picture (Ferner & Almond, 2013; Yanadori, 2011)”. Furthermore, pay level underlies stronger influences in the local context, resulting in a stronger local adaptation, though this is not necessarily the case for pay combination (the proportion between cash bonus and base salary).

Furthermore, as HRM was perceived as a rather “localized management function (McGraw, 2015), a notion that applies in particular to reward management (Ferner et al., 2001), the organizational context is expected by some researchers to play a less important role than in past discussions (Gomez-Mejia & Welbourne, 1991; Schuler & Florkowski, 1996)”. Overall, research has focused primarily on external HRM standardization constraints and has overlooked factors that emphasize and promote this approach (Brewster, Mayrhofer, & Smale, 2016).

2.5.2.4 Performance Assessment

Like other HRM components, “the universalist versus the contextualist paradigms” drawn to be a significant strategy regarding the global practice PM of foreign firms. “The contextualist paradigm” assumes that HRM activities are contextually unique and seeks to understand the countries' peculiarities, differences, and similarities. “The universalist paradigm,” on the contrary, aims to improve the HRM of organizations by providing strategic approaches or so-called “best practices,” which are supposed to be universally applicable (Brewster, 2004).

Brewster et al. (2011) emphasize the gap between these two paradigms: “Universalism and contextualism are paradigms, that is, they are taken-for-granted truths that the proponents of each simply assume must be correct. The fact that there are people who hold fast to each paradigm indicates that they are intellectual constructs capable of being challenged, but for the proponents of each one, they are ‘obviously’ correct and ‘the only’ way to think about management science and HRM”. “The contextualistic” and universalistic paradigms are linked to a central discussion in global PM research, namely the convergence debate on divergence (Claus & Briscoe, 2008).

“The contextualistic paradigm” is related to the principle of “convergence,” which is described as the adjustment of country-wide management priorities and patterns due to increased global competition (Festing et al., 2012). The theoretical approaches to explaining the idea of “convergence” are “market-driven and neo-institutionalist.” The market-driven viewpoint centers the prerequisite to find the best and effective result in the present exceptionally focused world market, for the most part alluding to US-based benchmarks (Huselid, 1995), though “the neo-

institutionalism" point of view grasps a world spread of US-formed exercises brought about by the US's overwhelming job on the world economy (Smith and Meiksins, 1995).

Conversely, "divergence" is connected to "the contextualistic paradigm" and characterizes dissimilarities in the board exercises that stay stable after some time because of consistent nation explicit impacts (Pudelko, 2006; Pudelko and Harzing, 2007). The hypothetical structures introduced to clarify the idea of "divergence" are "social points of view" (House et al., 2004) and institutional techniques that define social contrasts (Whitley, 1992). The discussion on "convergence and divergences" likewise harmonizes with another centrality exchange in worldwide PM look into the contention on institutionalization and confinement, "the most seasoned discussion in MNC [Multinational Corporations] writing" (Pudelko and Harzing, 2007).

While institutionalized arrangements guarantee similar outcomes in worldwide PM rehearses and a steady corporate culture, some type of adjustment may require nearby conditions (Dowling et al., 2013). The critical difficulties of "localization and standardization" happen at the sound level, as indicated by Pudelko and Harzing (2007), though the relating wonders of "divergence and convergence" can be seen at the logical level, where likenesses and contrasts in HRM exercises happen crosswise over nations. Thusly, "localization approaches" are prescribed if the possibility of "divergence" is pursued, while if more assurance is joined to the combination idea, MNCs ought to endeavor to institutionalize their practices all through the organization (Pudelko and Harzing, 2007).

Although the possibility of "standardization and localization" is established in the custom of global administration, when this choice and its drivers are dissected, the hierarchical point of view is regularly changed by the other two fields of research (culturally diverse and similar administration) (Farndale and Paauwe, 2007). A coordinated option in contrast to the ideas of "convergence and divergence" is adoration (Claus and Briscoe, 2008; Budhwar et al., 2016), which accepts that individual work esteems are molded by national impacts and monetary belief system to make new and one of a kind principles and exercises (Ralston et al., 1997). The idea of worship centers transnational learning and flexibility through adjusting and coordinating world guidelines and nearby eccentricities (Ralston et al., 1997).

2.5.2.5 Staff Maintenance

Retention activities of companies address the issue arising from employee turnover. Campion and Maertz (1998) implied that the propensity of an organization to overcome staff turnover problems concerns with retention schemes that can be used within the organization as well as the drive of the organization to use them. These incentives are also associated with other activities such as "recruitment and selection, training, and internal opportunities" (Reiche, 2008). Shaw et al. (2013), for instance, features the significance of pay and advantages in urging workers to remain inside the association. In 1997, Coff included execution-based rewards just as a feeling of proprietorship as benefit-sharing and stock possession plans. Magner et al. (1996) demonstrated

that expanded inclusion in the necessary leadership procedures of an association could prompt a decrease in turnover.

In 2003, Harzing and Sorge recognized an inclination for backups to apply the HR exercises utilized by their home office as far as global auxiliaries. As a result of the dissimilarities situations where these associations work, this can make troublesome difficulties. Home-nation weights joined with impacts from the host nation may influence the standard of acknowledgment of moved HR rehearses. A conflict between these two impacts can, in this manner, influence the adequacy and productivity of the HR practices utilized (Hofstede, 1998). It is difficult to express from the earlier what might be the impact of MNEs' HR exercises on worker turnover rates given these complexities.

2.5.2.6 Trade Union and Labour Relation

Trade unions are distinct organisations and their functions are interpreted differently and regarded in various ways, depending on the importance of similar groups in any country, according to Tattersall (2010). Trade unions have historically been responsible for safeguarding jobs and protecting workers' real wages, offering them protection and decent working conditions, and combating mistreatment and insecurity to ensure fair treatment and workplace equality.

There is currently a big debate about the intent and functions of the trade unions. The most influential perspective, however, is that which relates to trade unions expanding their positions beyond mere bread and butter matters. Through embracing various methods of industrial action such as strikes and protests and political acts such as influencing government policies, trade unions were able to create fair rates of legal and economic structures. They have also been able to greatly limit labor exploitation in all sectors where work is coordinated. Many consider trade unions as ethical organizations that play an important role in uplifting the poor and the vulnerable and ensuring them with the genuinely deserved status, dignity, and justice.

Yet public sentiment in most countries has been very opposed to trade unions. Although the public is not overwhelmingly opposed to trade unionism, it is opposed to the way unions and union leaders do their jobs. Mostly the union leaders' common perspective is that they are divisive, deceptive, and thoughtless about the public. Recent years have seen a substantial decrease in membership of the union in most of the world's developed nations. Across a significant number of European countries, trade union memberships have declined significantly.

For example, France is the worst hit where membership of the union has plummeted to just 10 per cent of the workforce. Correspondingly, it has fallen to 25 percent in Holland and is currently 44 percent in England. In the US where trade union membership has fallen to 16 per cent, the image is not very optimistic either. It is very small at 25 per cent in Japan while it is just 10 per cent in India. There is, however, a different trend in some countries. Trade unions are highly regarded in Sweden and the membership of 91 per cent is the highest. In addition to engaging in

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the administration of the legal structures, trade unions in Sweden participate in all decision-making activities both at the local and national levels. Trade union membership is very high at 82 and 63 per cent respectively in Denmark and Norway as well (Getman, 2010).

The only trade union group in Laos, one of the few existing slightly communist countries in the world, is closely affiliated with the country's only legal political party, the Lao People's Revolutionary Party (LPRP). A pluralism of trade unions does not occur in Laos. The Trade Union Act of 2008 describes "Lao Trade Unions" as "the mass body of the united leadership under the Lao People's Revolution Party in the political structure of democratic centralism." Labor unions must be associated with the government-sanctioned Lao Federation of Trade Unions (LFTU), which acts as an LPRP-controlled mass organization. While trade unions adhere to one party, each group has trade union representative committees to ensure rights and track employers' and employees' legalization.

Laos' new labor law (2013) was formally approved in January 2014, substituting for the labor law (2006). The new legislation was the outcome of lengthy negotiations between the various Lao authorities, private sector companies, and development organizations, and makes a range of changes to the core employment laws in Laos, including the recruitment of foreign workers. On 1 February 2008 the Trade Union Act came into effect, expanding a labor act passed in 2006. Yet, in Laos, there was no improvement for employees given these new rules.

Work interruptions and strikes are forbidden in law, and no incidents of labor unrest were published during the year. Outsiders contend that a systemic lack of labor law enforcement leaves Lao workers unable to understand their rights in effect, although the Lao government insists it is the correct approach for their small nation. Since HRM is clearly linked to performing worker-related tasks, it must cooperate with trade unions to create an atmosphere of unity and mutual cooperation that contributes to optimizing productivity, as well as enhancing the welfare of the employees.

In the ideal world of SEZs, it is expected that employees welfare included in international HRM policies of FIEs will improve wages, rights of workers, working/living conditions of national workers. This is claimed that while average salaries are higher in some SEZs than outside the zones, this also means longer hours of more demanding work than in non-zone businesses. Hayter (2001) explains how the authorities and SEZ units flouted labor rules, even if limited to zones. ILO reports have also identified multiple breaches of core labor standards in many SEZs. A wide body of literature is available on the working conditions of SEZ workers. One source of literature claims that there is a systematic violation of workers' rights, forced overtime, job instability, poor working conditions, use of coercive techniques to reach deadlines, and ultimately loss of human resources in the zones (ICFTU 2004, Phillips and Xaba 2002).

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In addition, Gereffi et. al. (2001) relate to examples of Haiti, where bad conditions in the SEZs have spurred critics to assert that zones are employment-generating exploitative mechanisms. Since then labor unions and advocates have been exerting intense pressure to implement codes of conduct and control measures. The reports are distinctly mixed and often contradictory. Nevertheless, another body of literature considers that working conditions in the zones are representative of national practice.

Feng (2006) notes that the zones in China are better than the enterprises of the domestic economy in aspects such as working time, overtime wages, and sanitary conditions, but employees note the existence of health hazards and inadequate ventilation. Moreover, most employees in China (from three zones: two in Beijing and one in Guangzhou) say that the EPZ job has solved their problem in aspects such as wages, living standards, and career development (Feng 2006). China is a communist nation and doesn't have pluralism. The role of trade union on human resource development in SEZs might not depending on its structure but the successful bringing quality investment and comprehensive labor policies in the country.

2.5.3 Cultural Insights in HRM

Culture can be defined in many ways. Culture has been described as a shared action and shared social aspects of society (Triandis & Wasti, 2008). Hofstede (2001) describes culture as the mind's quality experience that recognizes the members from one group or category of people from another. Culture is made up of attributes such as demeanour, values, knowledge, behaviors, and beliefs (Thoma, 2008). Owing to the different relations between societies, cultures vary from one community or nation to another.

A lot of studies are attempting to explain cultural differences between countries. Cited by Thomas (2008), Kluckhohn and Strodtbeck (1961) define six dimensions of culture. First, people may tend to control, subjugate, or harmonise by nature. Second, people are fundamentally good, bad, or a combination, depending on the views regarding human nature. Third, people may appear to be individualistic, complementary , or bureaucratic in interpersonal relationships. Fourthly, people may focus on living (being), vying for aims (attainment), or observing (contemplating) in terms of human activities. Fifth, space may be thought of as public, private, or a combination of public and private. Sixth, people may value past, current, or future events in relation to time. Based on these dimensions, a country's culture may establish a trend by accepting a certain attribute in each dimension.

In his research on cultural differences between countries, Hofstede (2001) produced five dimensions of culture, namely individualism-collectivism, power distance, avoidance of uncertainty, masculinity-femininity, and long-term/short-term orientation. He defines individualism-collectivism as dealing with an individual's characteristics that indicate whether a person is a member of the collective or more individualistic. Power distance is the degree to which

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disparities in power within a society are recognized and limited. Avoidance of uncertainty is the manner a society seeks to minimize uncertainty and brings about stability.

Furthermore, masculinity-femininity encompasses the stereotypical masculine orientation of achievement and accomplishment focused on the typically feminine inclination of caring and social harmony. Long-term/short-term awareness was introduced later and corresponds with one's future in the long term and interest toward the past and the present in the short-term, such as reverence for tradition and fulfillment of social responsibilities (Hofstede, 2010). These four dimensions (except for long-term/short-term orientation) are included by rating each dimension from 1 to 100 to classify the cultural differences of over 50 countries. The scores obtained in each dimension highlighted each country's cultural difference.

Western countries such as the United States of America (USA), Australia, and New Zealand have common cultural characteristics in terms of individualism, masculinity, short-term focus, low uncertainty avoidance, and low power gap, based on one Hofstede study (2010). European countries, such as Germany and the United Kingdom (UK), differ in cultural character. They are similar in low power distance, individualism, masculinity and short-term orientation, but differ in avoidance of uncertainty.

On the other hand, Hofstede (2001) implied that Asian countries have parallels in cultural characteristics such as collectivism, high power distance, femininity, low uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation. Only a handful of nations have masculine features, such as Japan and the Philippines, short-term orientation like Singapore and high uncertainty avoidance like South Korea, Taiwan and Thailand. Asian countries are therefore relatively similar and have minor variations in their cultural traits.

Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars (1998) describe seven essential dimensions on which cultures vary, including universality vs. particularism, analyzed specifics vs. integrated wholes, individualism vs. communitarianism, inner-directed vs. outer-directed orientation, time as series vs. time as rhythm, achieved rank vs. Ascribed rank, and equality vs. hierarchy. Universalism is a conviction that what is real and good can be uniformly found and implemented while particularism is a perception that exceptional conditions decide what is right or correct.

Individualism/collectivism is concerned with the degree to which individuals organize their behavior concerning individual gains versus those of the community. Emotion is meant to be kept in check in neutral cultures and it is important to maintain an appearance of self-control whereas in affective cultures it is deemed reasonable to express emotions. Specific/diffuse relates to the way to which individuals require others to have connections to their inner self. Achievement/ascription is about how you assess your rank and power. Yet another two dimensions, namely time and environment, were introduced. The time dimension applies to past vs. future orientation. The environment has to do with the degree to which people believe they are the main inspiration in their lives, or the world has more control over them.

The seven cultural dimensions introduced by Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars (1998) were used to denote the organizational factors anticipated by companies based in specific nations that are ruled by certain nationalities. Western countries like the US and Australia are typically

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characterized by universalist, individualistic, neutral, and unique cultures. They are also described as striving for success, synchronous, and with a cultural focus on power.

Asian countries are regarded as having opposite traits compared to western (e.g., collectivist) nations. Japan is the deviation in Asian societies and has shifted further to be more oriented towards Western society in its cultural characteristics, for instance, the orientation towards accomplishment is on the rise alongside other elements of individualism (Ono & Spindle 2000). The three pillars characterized HRM activities in Japan: lifelong jobs, a seniority-based pay structure, and business unionism, but this is evolving slightly (Vo & Hannif, 2012).

Lewis (2006) classifies cultures of countries into three dimensions: linear-active culture, multi-active culture, and reactive culture. For example, the personality trait with linear active culture is to do one task at a time, to concentrate intensely on that task, and to do it within a defined timeframe. Linear-active societies include Germany, the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia. People with multi-active culture aren't really interested in timetables or timeliness. They find the truth to be more important than man-made appointments and do not want to leave an unfinished conversation.

Examples of countries with multi-reactive cultures are Latin American and Arab countries, India, Pakistan, Spain, Italy, and Polynesia. Generally, people listen before they jump in reactive societies and they prefer a form of communication with a monologue. They have introverted habits and are good at interacting nonverbally. For example, Japan, China, and Taiwan are countries with strong reactive cultures. Some countries have a hybrid society, a combination of two cultural aspects, such as Indonesia and the Philippines, with multi-active and reactive cultures mixing. Countries like Belgium and France combine multi-active and linear-active culture, while Singapore and Hong Kong combine linear active and reactive features.

Concerning the cultural characteristics of South-East Asian countries, including Laos, Lewis (2006) argues that the South-East Asian outlook is fairly relaxed, time is seen as a scarce asset, the importance of productivity is often uncertain, and kindness and goodness are highly valued. They also have a patronage system, and they are characterized not only by stability, peace, and cooperation but also by modesty and tenderness. Strong cultural complexities are ingrained in deeply rooted traditions and customs in Southeast Asians. Chatterjee and Nankervis (2007) contend that all Asian countries have strong family values, regard for their elders, dedication to their country, communities, and kin, and dedication to the preservation of their physical environment and to variable levels have traditional cultures focused on moral, religious, ideological and political structures and ideologies.

2.5.3.1 Cultural Diversity in HRM

Stone and Stone-Romero (2008) suggest that HRM procedures and strategies are affected by individual cultures of group members, as well as the workplace structure of dominant or non-dominant groups. They continue to say that national and ethnic cultures often play a key role in shaping HRM strategies. Sparrow and Wu (1998) require that HRM strategies are situated within an outside factors of country-wide cultural value method, fluid organizational components, national business strategies, framework and labor markets, and reworking in HRM decision-makers' roles and competencies.

Countries with Western culture (US) as the origin of HRM will find Western HRM practices easier to adopt than countries with dissimilar cultures. For example, nations like Australia, the UK, or New Zealand find Western HRM methods much easier to embrace than Asian countries. In addition, large corporations may have embraced Western HRM practices in Asian countries but their traditional culture and traditions still strongly influence them. In addition, Yaw, McGovern, and Budhwar (2000) suggest that the success of HRM activities depends on how well these approaches align with the society they are being applied in.

Some Asian values that define Asian governance such as the importance of family relationships, decision-making by consensus, and respect for authority vary greatly from Western ideals such as a focus on individual accomplishment, political and economic independence, and respect for the rule of law (Chatterjee & Nankervis 2007a). Some scholars conclude that undue dependence on certain features would harm economic growth. For example, valuing the family can cause nepotism, overbalancing consensus about autocracy can lead to corruption, and the importance of conservatism and reverence for authority over individualistic actions can create rigidity and unwillingness to innovate (Nankervis & Chatterjee, 2003). These negative aspects of culture and values are becoming obstacles for Asian managers in their endeavours to integrate Asian values with Western values.

2.5.3.2 Laos' National Culture

National culture is defined within a particular community of the national body. It is shaped by different traits unique to a nation, some of which are political and historical background, social standards, and customary beliefs that are passed down to their descendants in a particular ethnic or racial group (Chew & Sharma, 2005). Hofstede (2001) argues that national cultures arise since nations differ in social, political, legal, educational, labor, and employment relations structures. When contemplating the idea of national culture there is a likelihood that there will be a large number of subcultures within certain countries, and that there will be differences, disputes, and opposition within national cultures (Thomas, 2008).

Laos has a culture that is not quite different from other countries in South East Asia such as Thailand, Burma, and Cambodia. Amid continued modernization, Buddhist thought, behaviors,

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and actions still profoundly influence much of Lao culture. It is difficult to grasp Lao culture without at least getting a clear awareness of the Hinayana Buddhist heritage that went to Cambodia from over 450 years ago.

In the Lao culture, unified tradition affirms itself in the tasks of employment or society. Constructing a local school or somebody's house creates the cheerful participation of the neighborhood as a whole. The atmosphere of the civil service office is often subject to collective bargaining in matters such as cleaning up the office premises, joining political meetings, or hosting a festive party on some event. However, collaborative actions at the workplace should not be misunderstood as actually originating from the concerned individual's candid emotions. These are most commonly directed by the superiors and thus obeyed by personnel.

The Lao people are not as communitarian or obedient in many respects as the rest of their East Asian counterparts. This is due to the country's 49 ethnic minorities each having their language and identity. Even the Lao, the largest ethnic group that comprises nearly half of the population, is considered a minority in their own country. Therefore collectivism and conformity are intellectual impossibilities. The deep Buddhist conviction that each person is accountable for his or her actions is an instrumental force working against the Asian collectivist inclination. This brings people to go their way, and not interfere with another's.

Not all of this is to suggest that the Lao are total individualists. They aren't. At some level, they often seem to be conformist in the larger perspective because of their Buddhist belief in their individual irrelevance. But people prefer to follow their own projects and not try to turn the world around. But there is significant diversity behind the superficial obedient appearance if you take time to discover it. Cultural Laos is where family and friendships are very significant. Relationships between Lao people are focused mainly on family relations with little interest displayed toward outsiders or strangers. Trust is confined within this circle. They resort to family members or close friends, and less often to their colleagues, when the Lao have issues, need support, or need a confidant. As a result, the Lao spend most of their energy on relationships within this circle, rather than among strangers, colleagues at work, or casual acquaintances.

Since Lao people place high importance on family and friendships, there will be commitments and expectations for your Lao colleagues that will allow them to skip work from time to time. Anticipate parents to take time off when a child gets sick unexpectedly. During the day, coworkers may be expected to take meals to family members who are hospitalized.

2.6 Conclusion of Chapter 2

Chapter 2 discussed three related aspects, such as HR development, HRM regulations and implementation, and SEZ in the global and Laos context. Form literature review it can be concluded that:

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- HR development is a sustainable way to enhance the country's economic growth and prevent low-income countries who rely on natural resources such as Laos from Dutch-disease. Since this thesis discusses HR development, its indicators such as education, income, living, and working conditions will be used in this study.
- Scholars discovered that MNEs have a strong influence on HR development since MNEs are a source of knowledge for low-income countries. MNEs bring international HRM regulations such as "recruitment, training, rewards, performance appraisals, retention, and a labor union." Accordingly, there is a relationship between international HRM and HR development. The HRM regulations will be used in this research.
- MNEs can be found in SEZs. Low-income countries established SEZs to attract MNEs by providing various incentives such as tax incentives and improve investment climate through developing infrastructure, reducing paper works and investment procedures.
- In a global context, the advantage of SEZs is hardly unique. Empirical pieces of evidence demonstrated that the benefits of SEZs could be measured at the Macro and Micro level. At the Macro level, most of the literature regarding SEZs are from World Bank studies. The board study usually focused on the level of GDP, Export and employment, and most micro research or firm study focussed on a firm's performance and HRM rules and implementation.
- In Laos context, SEZs are not the first choice of economic transformation of the country. Yet, SEZs have been developed as a tool for attracting FDI. During the literature review, macroeconomic conditions such as export, investment, and employment were analysed. Overall, the outcomes of Laos SEZs are mixed across the country since venture, export, and jobs are gradually increasing in some provinces; others did not. Yet, since Laos SEZs are very young, the benefits of such incentives are hardly demonstrated.
- Cultural perspectives were reviewed along with its influence on HRM. Laos has very strong culture that impacts on Laotian diary's life such as working practices. These negative aspects of culture and values are becoming obstacles for Asian managers in their endeavours to integrate Asian values with the West.

From the above summary of the literature review, research gaps, concepts, frameworks, and hypotheses can be drawn in the paragraphs below.

2.6.1 Research Gaps

Based on the literature review, there are four research gaps found in the literature review.

Firstly, very few studies have been carried out systematically on the effect of SEZs on the domestic economy. While the literature is plagued with the assessment of SEZs benefits at Macro-level, few studies are focusing on measuring micro or firms' benefits. To evaluate if SEZs are a rational strategy, measuring macro benefits alone is not accurate, as the level of GDP, firm-level investment, export, or employment is not fully representative of the overall benefits of SEZs.

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Additionally, most SEZ's critical analysis focuses on their activity as enclaves within the local economy, where rewards are focused exclusively on corporate flows within the area and foreign firms (e.g., tax incentives for import/export). As they benefit the few and distort the allocation of resources (Engman et al., 2007), SEZ is often categorized as economically sub-optimal policies. For instance, while some SEZs employ a significant sum of workers, the unemployment rate of the province where zones are located might be high in the country.

Secondly, significant evidence on the impacts of SEZs on HR development is ambiguous. Their impact on labor standards, labor relations, and human capital are one of the most controversial aspects of free zones. While several groups of studies showed that the free zones are targeted-oriented workplaces, indicators of sustainable HR development were absent. On the other hand, another group argued that the zones could be instrumental in promoting HR development. A review of existing works of literature, however, implies that a comprehensive analysis of SEZs' HR effects is anecdotal.

Thirdly, national culture is believed to influence the ways companies run their businesses. Understanding cultural differences leads to the need for adjustment in HRM practices. Laos has a unique culture that is blended from many ethnic cultures and yet, influenced by Buddhism believes. Furthermore, the development of HRM practices is also influenced by economic, political, and demographic factors. However, most literature regarding Laos culture does not focus on its influence on modern HRM that FIEs brought to Laotian workers.

Lastly, only a few empirical types of research regarding outcomes of SEZs focus on low-income countries such as Laos. Most of the existing literature regarding Laos SEZs is from the World Bank reports, where several macro benefits of Laos SEZs such as export, employment, and investments, were analyzed. In other words, evidence of Micro-level impacts is scarce. The lack of development experiences and strong policy background accounted for slowing development and many challenges of Laos SEZs. Furthermore, Zeng (2015) alleged that low-income countries, including Laos, are often unable to create a business environment or build infrastructure nationwide at all once because of limited resource and implementation capacity.

Therefore, relying on incentives, legal, and regulatory framework is necessary for those countries to achieve outcomes from SEZs (Zeng, 2015). According to the research gaps, this research aims to recommend policy and strategic framework encourage HR development in Laos SEZs. In addition, since it is not enough to measure the impacts of Laos SEZs at the macro level, this research takes a comprehensive approach by also looking at the micro or firm level.

2.6.2 Research Concept and Questions

Financial analysts and specialists see HR as a noteworthy mainstay of commercial development in a nation and thusly as the reason for accomplishing the focused way of life. Low-pay countries like Laos are concentrating on the advancement of HR to change their economies from farming while overwhelmed economies into modernly prevailing economies. SEZs are an

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essential apparatus not exclusively to advance fares and procure foreign trade, yet additionally, their effect on work benchmarks, work relations, and the improvement of HR. The concept in this research is to look at the benefits of SEZs on HR development from two different angles.

Initially, a standard advantage from the foundation of SEZs in low-income countries is to make business changes to the neighborhood workforce. SEZs incorporate work serious exercises, organizations in SEZs are, from the earlier, a noteworthy wellspring of new employments. Low-income countries massively draw in an interest in basic handling of work escalated enterprises because of the accessibility of low-wage work. This drives up interest inside the zone for inadequate work. As SEZs develop, moving to higher worth included exercises could likewise build interest in talented work.

Secondly, it is expected that HRM regulations and activities of businesses of foreign investors influence the accumulation of HR in the host country. Under the concept of cluster-specific industries, the establishment of SEZs is one primary vehicle for attracting foreign-invested enterprises. Since foreign-invested enterprises have generally been found to bring their modern HRM policy and practice to their overseas new plants, it is expected that the new management behavior can improve the quality, productivity, and living condition of the local workforce. Significant shreds of evidence from China implied the shift towards new HRM policy and practice in SEZs and the rest economy accounted for the establishment of FIEs within SEZs.

In sum, the impacts of SEZs in the context of HR development can be examined; by looking at the way, it creates employment opportunities and policy and practice of HRM of FIEs located within SEZs. To overcome the research gap, testing the employment generation of Laos SEZ is conducted at the macro or zone level, and the impacts of HRM regulations and activities of businesses of foreign investors are assessed at the micro or firm level. In addition, to gain an in-depth understanding on international HRM, a cultural perspective is added at micro-level. The cultural perspective is critically reviewing the application of Hofstede's work in the field of national cultural for HRM in FIEs.

The comprehensive analyses shall enhance the achievement of the research aim to come up with a considerable incentive and policy recommendation to improve HR development in Laos SEZs. Therefore, below research questions shall be answered.

Research Questions:

- 1. How does a Laos SEZ generate employment for the Laotian workforce?**
- 2. What are the opportunities and challenges of human resource development within Laos SEZs?**
- 3. What are the incentives and policies offered by the Laos government to encourage human resource development within Laos SEZs?**
- 4. How are human resource management regulations and activities of businesses of foreign investors implemented within Laos SEZs?**
- 5. What are the relationships between human resource management regulations and activities of businesses of foreign investors located in Laos SEZs and perceptions of human resource development?**

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- 6. How does national culture influence HRM of FIEs in Laos SEZs?**
- 7. What incentives and policies can be recommended to enhance human resource development from Laos SEZs?**

2.6.3 Research Framework and Hypothesis Testing

According to the above research questions, the study will focus on analyzing the benefits of SEZs on human resource development in Laos context to suggest favorable policies and incentives. The study will start from macro-level or zone analysis to examine the way Laos SEZ generates employment to the local workforce. The zone level study will be conducted to understand the way Laos SEZ makes employment in various perspectives such as direct employment, gender employment, and indirect employment (evidence on sub-contract). Furthermore, exploring challenges and opportunities regarding human resource development in the zone and current policies and incentives offered by the Laos government to enhance HR in SEZs are established at the zone level analyses.

Subsequently, research at the micro or firms' level will be conducted in exploratory and survey research. HRM policy and practice of three selected Foreign Invested Enterprises (FIEs) operated within Laos SEZs, such as "recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, performance appraisals, retention, and union, and labor regulations" will be explored through interview. Later, the relationship between HRM policy and practice of the FIEs and HR development was examined through survey questionnaires to enhance research outcomes and the validity of the research. Moreover, cultural perspectives are discussed to explore the way national cultural influence HRM activities of FIEs.

To conduct the investigation, justifications for HR development include quality of life, income, skill and knowledge formulation, demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities, working/living conditions, career prosperity, and gender equality. Perceptions of employees at management and non-management level towards the factors will be examined during the survey. Based on the findings obtained in the previous analysis, policies, and incentives to enhance HR development in Laos SEZs will be designed and suggested to policymakers. A parametric study will be conducted to test the following hypotheses.

H_1 = A positive correlation between the policy and activity of recruitment and selection processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

H_2 = A positive correlation between the policy and activity of training and development processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

H_3 = A positive correlation between the policy and activity of remuneration and rewards processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

H_4 = A positive correlation between the policy and activity of performance appraisals processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

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H₅= A positive correlation between the policy and activity of retention processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

H₆= A positive correlation between the policy and activity of union and labor relation processes and perceptions of human resource development exists.

The framework of this research exemplified in following figure 14:

Figure 4: The Research framework

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction of Chapter 3

Chapter 2 reviewed existing knowledge regarding human resource development, human resource management of foreign firms, and SEZs in the global and Laos context. From the review, research gaps, concepts, frameworks, and hypotheses were developed. The previous section already discussed gaps, concept, and framework of the research examining the impacts of SEZs on HR development at the Macro and Micro level.

3.2 Reason for selecting the study's pragmatic realism paradigm

Five paradigms are identified, namely: “positivism, constructivism, critical theory, realism and pragmatism” in a management research context. Positivism relies upon quantifiable perceptions that lead to numerical examinations. Collins (2010) implied that “as a philosophy, positivism is in accordance with the empiricist view that knowledge stems from human experience. It has an atomistic, ontological view of the world as comprised of discrete, observable elements and events that interact in an observable, determined, and regular manner”.

“The constructivist paradigm” shows multiple constructed realities by sharing meaning and explanation (Spencer et al., 2014). Constructivism uses a different procedure and set of assumptions to claim knowledge (Lincoln et al., 2011). This satisfies one of the central presumptions hidden subjective research, to be specific that the truth is developed socially and abstractly instead of being resolved unbiasedly (Ticehurst and Veal, 2000). This implies from the perspective of the individuals who live in it, and the specialist should attempt to comprehend the unpredictable universe of lived involvement.

The underlying hypothesis worldview recognizes methods for impacting convictions, conduct, and involvement in material conditions (Snape and Spencer, 2003). Some scholars announce that the material world comprises structures verifiably arranged that really affect people's life possibilities (Hatch, 2002). Research examinations are in this manner frequently long and haul ethnographic and chronicled investigations of authoritative procedures and structures (Golafshani, 2003).

“Realism” is an undeniably valuable perspective for some social researchers. Healy & Perry, 2000 suggested that “realism impacts numerous conceptions of a single reality that is mentally independent. The researchers considered that they were part of the process and are trying to find the probable truth depending on the triangulation of different phenomena views”.

The last paradigm is the “pragmatic approach,” which is used in this research. “The pragmatism philosophy says researchers should make use of the approach or mix of approaches

that work best in a real-world situation.” To put it plainly, whatever works is helpful and ought to be utilized, independent of any philosophical theories, paradigmatic presumptions, or different suppositions. Teddlie and Tashakkori (2010) point out that the development of "pragmatism" and the proposal of similarity happens in the postmodern period or the present minute. Maxcy (2003) shows that sober-mindedness seems to have developed as both an analytical technique and a gadget for settling fights between perfectionist analysts and progressively useful researchers.

Logical HRM is completely reliable with the "pragmatic, realistic" perspective, as indicated by Boxall, Purcell, and Wright (2007) and Watson (2010). These creators depict investigative HRM as an action whose essential undertaking is to assemble a hypothesis and gather preliminary information to represent the way the executive's behaviors work in the association and with the individuals the board considers over various occupations, operating environments, organizations, enterprises, and social orders. There are three analytical HRM features. The first feature concerns HRM's "what and why," the second feature involves HRM's "how" and the third feature concerns "who and how well" in evaluating HRM's outcomes. Each of these concerns invites research and analysis in a social science style.

The challenge of the study is to determine the impact of Laos SEZs on the domestic economy. The study focuses on employment relations and HRM of FIEs within the zones. Understanding HR development influence involves a closer look on employment policies in Laos SEZs and how the policies change employment structure among the Laotian people as a whole. The study also aims to discover HRM policies and activities in FIEs and how modern HRM is vital to HR development in the free zones.

This includes both qualitative and quantitative ways to deal with revealing patterns and topics of information gathered in specific organizations and to investigate the complexities of these issues and to sum up the discoveries and affirm the outcomes in the more extensive Laos setting. These theoretical frameworks are best suited to the paradigm of pragmatism because "pragmatism accommodates the use of qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide the best solution."

3.3 Research Approach: Justification of mixed-method

Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) explained that a mixed-method approach is a research strategy, in which both qualitative and quantitative are introduced during the research progress. While many scholars claimed that mixed method is a comprehensive study to help researchers understand more about particular problems, Teddlie and Tashakkori (2003) confirmed that the approach also helps the researcher to confirm results from exploratory research and, therefore, enhance the validity of the study. The fact that Laos SEZs have not conducted any previous study of micro or firm level, especially the literature related to HRM policies and practices, extended the belief that modern HRM activities cannot be readily followed in Laos SEZs. To respond to the way Laos SEZs, influence on HR development entails a qualitative method, and the best approach is case study research.

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Bryman (2006) lists five grounds for combining quantitative and qualitative research: triangulation, mutuality, creation, induction, and extension. In addition, the logic behind the combination and integration of quantitative and qualitative research includes triangulation, comprehensiveness, legitimacy, significance, elaboration, validation, and creation. This study also uses these rationales as its methodology to choose a mixed-method approach. Triangulation is observed in this study to ensure data validity and trustworthiness in terms of data sources and data collection methods — triangulation observation in this study, including researcher, management, and non-management employees.

3.4 Research Design: Justification of the case study approach

Sage (2008) implied that research design is a road map transformed from a research concept into a research scheme that a researcher can implement. In the point of view of Creswell and Clark (2011), the research design is a process in research studies to collect, analyze, interpret, and report data. Zikmund et al. (2013) claim that “a research design has to display the overall research configuration involving decisions on what kind of evidence needs to be collected, where the data is to be collected and how the data will be analyzed.” In sum, a research design is a practical implementation plan for a research project. It is conducted with logic by which the outcomes of the research were interpreted.

Stake (2010) asserts that a case study by pursuing academic research questions optimizes understanding. According to its contextual position, case study research usually examines one or several cases, so a case study can include the context as an essential part of a study (Veal, 2005). The use of multiple data collection methods is another feature associated with case studies (Creswell, 2007). Some positivists contend that a case study has no natural scientific design rigor (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). In order to avoid this lack of rigor, Yin (2006) implies that before any data is collected, all case studies should have a bright design and that these designs should cover the main questions or proposals.

While several observers such as Veal (2005) contented that case study results can be generalized critically, “case-based research” findings allow the observers to provide meaning and generate concepts to be theoretical positions that can be examined by future studies aimed at a significant population, or some theoretical insinuations could arise. A case study is valuable in refining theory, indicating intricacies for future examinations, and assisting in setting the generalizability limitations. For the following reasons, the use of the case study approach for this study is justifiable:

First, the case study is the preferred strategy of “when, how, who, why, or what” questions are being asked, or when the investigator has little control over events, or when the focus is on a contemporary phenomenon in a context of real life” (Burns and Burns, 2008). The five questions could be answered by the case study method in this study.

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It allows perception of how employment opportunities were created in a zone and what are policies, challenges, and opportunities of human resource development in Laos SEZs. Also, it examines which HRM policies and activities are used by the selected foreign-invested businesses in Laos SEZs influence human resource development. It is also necessary to know which HRM policies and practices should be emphasized and supported by the local government and the enterprises to enhance human resource development in the firms as well as in the country.

Second, a case study method is justified by considering 1) the type of research questions presented, 2) the scale to which an investigator controls actual behavior, and 3) the degree to which contemporary events rather than historical events are focused on (Yin, 2006). This study uses a theory-building mixed-method design. A case-study method has been adopted as the primary investigation strategy.

Third, an approach to case study enables different methods of data collection to be used to support triangulation (Gillham, 2000). Triangulation can consist of multiple researchers, multiple data sources, or various approaches to confirm emerging outcomes (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). They further claim that the purpose of triangulation in case studies is to enhance validity. Based on these justifications, the adoption of the case study approach was suitable for this study's data collection and analysis, which used a mixed method of “QUALQUAN” at both Macro and Micro level.

Following Figure 18, illustrated research questions shall be answered through a case study at Macro or zone and Micro or firms' level.

Figure 12: Macro and Micro level study

3.4.1 Case Study Design for Macro-Level Analysis

3.4.1.1 Unit of Macro-level analysis

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The analysis unit is “the type of unit used when measured by a researcher” (Neuman, 2006). In a case study, determining the unit of analysis is critical because it is related to a research project’s level of investigation (Zikmund, 2003). There are different levels of research in a research project. In other words, individuals, groups, organizations, social categories, social institutions, societies, speeches, or a geographic area, event or entity may be the unit of analysis (Neuman, 2011).

Before ascertaining the unit of analysis of study, investigating at zone level was the most developed Laos SEZ in terms of investment, export, and employment. The justification of selection the most advanced zone was that the rest of Laos SEZs are young and have no or only a few demonstrations regarding social benefits. Savan-Seno SEZ was selected since the zone is the first Laos SEZ establishment in 2003 and gradually demonstrated some achievements up to date. The selection of the zone is also based on the accessibility of secondary data such as zone’s report, strategy and another related document to support the analysis of employment generation within the zone.

Furthermore, the selection of the zone depends on the availability of the interviewees, who are the developers, zone economic board, and other related authorities. The interview was conducted smoothly after received permission from the Head of Laos SEZs management and development office and then, facilitation and coordination from the zone economic board demonstrated in Annex.

3.4.1.2 Quantitative approach for Macro-level analysis (secondary data collection)

Secondary data were collected to analyze the way employment has been generated in selected Laos SEZ. The data on profiles of the zone, zone strategy and development report, regional and international employment reports were sourced from national and local statistical bureau, the zone management department, SEZ management and development office, investment promotion department, and World Bank Group. With the focus on employment, econometric data were analyzed and evaluated to understand the trend and employment structure of the selected zone within the three themes, including direct employment generation, gender employment and indirect employment of the selected zone.

3.4.1.3 Qualitative approach for Macro level analysis (semi-structured interview)

An interview is a research approach that an investigator can obtain information directly from interviewees (Neuman, 2011). Patton (2002) supported that the type of data collection allows participants to speak about their ideas and visions towards problems and experiences, and the participants are likely to give more information when they feel comfortable with the interviewer and the interview environment. Furthermore, it is claimed that the benefits of conducting interviews are that interviews provide the observer with more personal insight and flexibility than

questionnaires do and that they are easier for the interviewee's response to a question in detail (Thomas, 2003).

Face-to-face interviews or an interview with a focus group are types of meetings. Thomas (2003) implied that a face-to-face interview is more effective in promoting the sincere participation of a respondent in a research project. Oppositely, to provide information on specific topics, the researcher may conduct a focus group interview (McMurray et al., 2004). Wilkinson (2004) explained that a focus group interview involving a small group of participants to discuss the same topic.

Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) found several methods to administer an interview based on the research questions and how much structure is put into the conversation. The meeting can be highly expressed and can be structured, or semi-structured, and even unstructured. Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005) assert that the structured (highly formalized) interview is generally and strongly influenced by positivism and can yield valuable outcomes in extensive quantitative surveys. They further implied that in qualitative research, "the semi-structured interview is used to explore the complexity and the in-process nature of meanings and interpretations that cannot be examined using positivist methodologies."

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to collect data. In this study, judgment was established to implement interviews since insignificant numbers of participants are involved, they are accessible vital people, and the questions are mainly open and require an extended response from the interviewer with prompts and samples to clarify the answers (Gillham, 2000).

According to the design, face-to-face interviews were conducted with each participant or interviewee. Interviewees were the zone economic board, the zone developer, and senior managers from SEZ management and development office who are engaged in the management of Laos SEZs as well as the selected zone. All interviewees were asked different questions that are suited to their positions to explore current policies of human resource development and challenges and opportunities that the zone faces regarding the policy implementation and human resource development in the zone.

3.4.2 Case Study Design for Micro-Level Analysis

3.4.2.1 Unit of Micro-level analyses

It is like sampling in the quantitative method to determine the unit of analysis in a case study. Patton (2002) fights that example choices, both example size and examining systems, are reliant on earlier decisions on the suitable investigative unit. There are numerous techniques for inspecting that can be utilized to decide the group of examinations. The motivation behind this investigation was to "catch real varieties instead of recognizing a typical center" (Patton, 2002), utilizing stratified intentional inspecting. The unit of the inquiry in this examination is resolved

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based on three strata utilizing the stratified purposive testing technique. The leading stratum depends on the organization's measure. There are four sizes of large organizations, for example, miniaturized scale, little, medium, and worldwide. This examination focuses on the massive global organizations with more than 300 workers.

There are several reasons why major companies are selected. First, large international firms may have better formal HRM practices than small or medium-sized firms. Local micro, small and medium firms are yet to establish their HRM activities due to the management's inadequate knowledge and skills, deficiency of organizational structure, and simple procedures. On the other hand, most large businesses developed their HRM methods in ways best suited to their corporate culture and developed HRM strategies to support their business strategies. It is expected that those companies will bring their new HRM policies and practices to their plants in Laos.

Secondly, there is little research around HRM practices for international enterprises in Laos as well as Laos SEZs. Thirdly, most local workers have yet to adopt their working habits to international HRM practices, and it is interesting to explore how the new management policies and practices influence their development. In addition, owners and managers of foreign investment firms may lack knowledge of local work practices as they manage the firms from their headquarters in traditional ways.

The second and third stratum is based on types of industries and case companies. Although an SEZ comprises various kinds of sectors such as oil and gas manufacturing industries, textile industries, electronic industries, and so on, all the foreign-invested companies are light industries focusing on export and sound processing. The justification for selecting the companies is that they are factories that have similar organizational structure, especially having systematic human resource management policies and practices hesitated from their headquarter. The three chosen cases are well-known companies that became representatives of successful business cases in Laos SEZs.

3.4.2.2 Qualitative approach for Micro-level analyses (Semi-Structured Interview)

The Micro-level analysis also uses a qualitative approach. Data were collected using semi-structured interviews. After getting permission to conduct the interview from the SEZ management and development office, zone developer, and senior officers from the office helped the researcher coordinate with each company. After receiving an interview agreement from the proposed companies through e-mail and phone calls, the researcher coordinated with the companies' managers to plan the interviews. Each case company A, B, and C were proposed to have at least **three managers and five non-managers** for the meetings.

The face-to-face interview was conducted with each management participant. The management participants were interviewed regarding the impact of national culture on their management and how they handled the challenges. A group interview was conducted for operational employees. The motive for undertaking a group interview was that due to the absence of its employees for interview activities, and the company would not lose much time from its

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production hours. A similar set of questions was provided to all interviewees to ensure that no critical data was lost and allows cross-data checks. Documents like letters of request to conduct interviews and data collection periods are demonstrated in Annex 6 and 7.

a. Selection of sample for the interview (Non-probability sampling method: Snowball sampling)

The non-random sampling strategy helps the surveyor select participants randomly. This type of sampling might lead to “skewed” outcomes. Yet, it is suitable for the initial phase of this research where the cost is insufficient for establishing the interview. Snowball sampling is a sampling strategy that is applied on investigations which are required to be conducted to acknowledge awkward matters. This sampling strategy is implemented in this research since the number of interview participants is small, and some questions are sensitive, especially for operational employees. An interviewer will ask the participants to provide an example of others’ experiences regarding human resource management in the company.

b. Observations

Observation is defined as the primary basis of all social and behavioral science research methods (Angrosino, 2007). Two major types of inspections are identified: observations of non-participants and participants (Lee & Broderick, 2007). Participant observation creates an environment where, over time, investigators and attendants communicate with each other naturally and comfortably (Benz et al., 2008). On the other hand, the investigator watches attendants doing activities or view the environment.

He or she is not involved in the activities or interactions with the attendants. This type of observation is called non-participant representation (Slack & Rowley, 2000). This research implemented a non-participant observation as the investigation was aimed at examining HRM practices in foreign investment firms, and the researcher was not involved in those processes. At the management and non-management level, the participants in this research were the employees. For each company, the total participants were five to seven, but the employees being observed were randomly selected by the researcher or appointed by the manager.

Observations were made for each company during field visits of one to two hours. The observations were made in the offices of the manager and in the plants of the production site. The observation's purpose was to record participants' activities related to HRM execution. The observed social behavior included what attendants do, the way they do it, and the behavioral impacts on people around them. In addition, taking a photo is a practical way to collect data based on the given topic, and it is the way to enhance trustworthy pieces of evidence (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). Photographs can also contribute to a more accurate process sequencing. A camera was

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also used when technical needs arise. Yet, some companies did not allow the researcher to take a photo in the production site.

c. Documentation and archival records

Documentation is a multi-faceted sort of data and ought to be the subject of unequivocal designs for information gathering (Yin, 2006). In this examination, authoritative records identified within the organization's HRM strategies and practices were the assortment of reports utilized as wellsprings of proof. Chronicled records were additionally gathered as hierarchical records.

d. Triangulation

It was purported that triangulation is a mixture and a comparison of various data sources, procedures for collecting, analyzing data, study approaches, examinations, and inferences at the final phase of research (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). In the study, triangulation is the use of a social phenomenon of several approaches or an origin of information to cross-check findings (Bryman, 2006). Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005) describe triangulation of the origin of an information as utilizing various sources of information even though triangulation involves the implementation of multiple methods of research.

Nevertheless, Berg (2009) claims that the same phenomenon is being investigated by many researchers using three data collection techniques. Since the case study practices some methods of information gathering, including “semi-structured interviews, observation, and documentation,” triangulation was possible to be employed in this study. The unique techniques of data collection added to the results' comprehensiveness.

3.4.2.3 Quantitative approach for Micro level analyses

a. Justification of the survey method

Fowler (2009) contented that the survey is designed to produce statistics about the target population. Neuman (2011) further explained that “a researcher samples many respondents in surveys to answer the same questions, measures multiple variables, tests multiple hypotheses, and infers temporal order from past behavior, experiences, or characteristics questions.” The method of survey is the best way to obtain data with a large sample. Questionnaires can be sent by email, phone, or even directly delivered to participants. Another advantage is the short time it takes to complete a survey. Statistical procedures used to analyze data support the research's validity.

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Surveys are used to quickly gain specific information by getting answers from the target group to the questionnaire (Kumar, 2019). Questionnaires offer a convenient, cheap, efficient, and accurate information gathering (Bryman, 2012; Zikmund et al., 2013). In addition, surveys can be distributed quickly through different ways such as face-to-face, mail, telephone, online, or drop-off and pick-up. The survey was conceived and conducted in this study based on the findings of the case study and the literature implications of relevant studies. The hypotheses were generated based on variables developed from the findings of the case study. The confirmation of the hypotheses enables the researcher to answer the third question of the research.

Based on the qualitative results, quantitative methods were used according to the exploratory sequential method used in this study. The study questions were hence planned to utilize the basic factors distinguished in the discoveries of the contextual analysis. A mail poll was disseminated to a huge example of three chose overseas firms to improve the representativeness of the discoveries from contextual analysis, a. Consequently, the limitations of the case study research's generalizability were avoided.

b. Research hypotheses

Six independent variables: “recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and rewards, performance appraisals, retention and union and labor relations” were obtained. The correlation between the six independent variables on the dependent variable of human resource development was determined. This study was founded on six hypotheses mentioned in the research framework, which needed to be verified.

c. Measures of variables

“Recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, performance assessments, retention and union, and labor relations” were the variables used in this research. This portion reports variables used for the development of variables for this research in previous studies as references. Also shown in Table 3 is the original scale used in previous studies and the range used for this study.

Variable measure	Items of variables measure	Original scale
Recruitment and selection	Level of the formal recruitment process, the external source for hiring, advertisements, selection criteria, interviews, and practical tests	The scale of 5 points
Training and development	Presence of formal training, number of training participants, apparent efficiency of training	The scale of 5 points

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Remuneration and rewards	Percentage of staff receiving awards, the relevance of staff performance in obtaining the employee's salary	The scale of 5 points
Performance appraisal	Percentage of staff getting formal work appraisals used in determining their rewards	The scale of 5 points
Retention	The loyalty of employees	The scale of 5 points
Labor union and relations	The importance of the association to staff	The scale of 5 points
Human resource development	Perception of toward quality of life, income, skill development, career, gender equality, and working condition	The scale of 5 points

Table 3: Variables and measurement scale of the survey questionnaire

d. Questionnaire design

Sekaran (2003) characterizes a questionnaire as a rewritten set of questions read by the respondents and then write down their answers (Kumar, 2005; Zikmund, 2003), usually by selecting defined alternatives. The research questions and hypotheses must be associated with each issue (Kumar, 2019; Ticehurst & Veal, 2000). In large-scale investigations, questionnaires are widely used to seek reliable answers from a selected sample (Sekaran, 2003).

A questionnaire was conducted in this study to test the generalizability of case-based findings. Because the survey strategy was used after the case study method, the questionnaire formulation was based on the case findings and the previous research conducted in Laos SEZs in relation to HRM policies and practices of foreign investing companies.

According to Zikmund et al. (2013), one of the most critical stages of the survey research process is the design of the questionnaire. In addition, two criteria must be met by a good questionnaire: relevance and accuracy. The questionnaire design usually begins with the problem and question of research (Sekaran, 2003). Good questionnaire design must provide plenty of items to cover in the necessary detail all aspects of the research problem.

Some questions were intended to include multiple-choice responses to enable respondents to select the option closest to their point of view (Yuji, 2003). Closed-ended questions are expedient to gather factual data and the respondents are more comfortable to answer (Zikmund et al., 2013). Likert-scales provide a series of dimensions of attitude for respondents ranging from strongly disagreeing to strongly agreeing (Brace, 2008). In this research, questionnaires for HRM policy and practice were designed to ask correspondent range from “strongly disagree” to “agree strongly,” and for perceptions of human resource development was the range from very low to very high.

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Closed-ended questions and multiple-choice answers, which used a 5-point Likert scale, were designed in the survey form for this study. The first two types of the questionnaire were established to obtain information and data from the participants and the firm, and the Likert-scales was designed to collect information regarding HRM activities implemented by the firms and the perceptions of the companies' employees towards HR development. Furthermore, the personal and factual close-ended questions that require the correspondent to divulge information, such as age, gender, education, and employment status, were included in the survey form (Bryan and Bell, 2013).

Based on the relevant literature and research hypotheses, all questionnaire items for this research have been developed. A total of 49 questions were formulated as follows: 39 for HRM policies and practices, seven questions for perceptions of human resource development, and five questions for demographic information. The 39 Questions were intended to reveal the enactment of HRM practices through six independent variables, namely "recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and rewards, performance assessments, retention and union, and labor relations;" and a dependent variable, namely the development of human resources. Details of the sources for the development of the questionnaire are provided in Annex.

The questionnaire needed translation from English to Laos in this study. Most Laotians regularly use Laos in a formal situation, at school or at work. Also, English is known to very few staff. Before being distributed, the questionnaire was translated into Laos. The Laos translation was then brought back into English by the researcher to check the similarities of content.

e. Measurement of scale

Research projects of this type generally use Likert scale measurements because they are easy to build (Kumar, 2019; Zikmund et al., 2013). Likert-scales are used by measuring their level of agreement or disagreement to indicate the attitudes or opinions of respondents (Kumar, 2005; Veal, 2005). Typically, a categorical scale is used in the Likert scale that has a numerical range of three, five, seven, or nine points depending on how finely researchers need to rate the intensity of respondent attitudes (Kumar, 2005). For questions related to HRM practices and perception of human resource development, this research used a 5-point scale of agreement measurement. One of the upsides of applying closed questions is that they can be pre-coded, making computer analysis data processing a simple task (Bryman and Bell, 2013).

f. Selection of sample for the survey (Probability sampling: Simple random sampling)

Probability sampling is a sample strategy that considers every member of the population and forms samples on based on a fixed process. For instance, in a population of 1000 members, each of these members shall have 1/1000 chances of being selected to be a part of a sample. It gets rid of bias in the population and gives a fair opportunity for all members to be included in the sample. This study utilized a random sample approach since the survey focus on population

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included the employees in all positions, who experienced human resource management procedures. The simple random sample is used in this study as the most basic form of a probability sample. Bryan and Bell (2013) implied that with random sampling, each population unit has the same likelihood of sample inclusion. For example, potential managers and non-managers experienced formal interviews in a company, or a supervisor and operational employees feel that they have a decent working environment in a company. This method is called the sampling fraction and is expressed as:

$$\frac{n}{N} \text{ i.e. (1 in 20)}$$

Where n is the sample size, and N is the population size. The selection of the sample assumes that all employees in the three cases are Laotian full-time employees. N is 1,463, and therefore, n will be 73 to 75 employees from management and non-management positions. The survey forms were disseminated to nine managers after their interviews. The other 64 survey participants are operational employees. Table 4 demonstrated the sample size.

Survey Sample Size		
Case	Population (N)	Sample (n)
A	313	15.65
B	750	37.5
C	400	20
Total	1463	73.15

Table 4: Sample size

g. Pilot study and response rate

A pilot study is a small research that needs to be developed before taking the actual data collection, and it was conducted before the questionnaires were disseminated in this study. Zikmund et al. (2013) implied that this type of study provided a guideline for the more prominent research and focused on deducting some variables to a more adaptable number since the more significant number of variables are discovered. In addition, while a pilot study is just a small-scale trial run of a more substantial survey, it can examine any kind of research procedure (Veal, 2005).

Before the central survey, the pilot study was established. The drop-off and pick-up techniques were used to get a quick response. The pilot study questionnaire was anonymous. Those who took part in the pilot study put the completed surveys in the sealed envelope for the researcher to collect. The finishing time was about 15 minutes. The rate of response was 100%.

The questionnaire was reviewed by the supervisors of the study to obtain comments regarding sentence construction and possible ambiguity of questions, based on these experts' feedback and approval, some changes have been made, particularly several confusing statements.

Then, a pilot research further supports the effectiveness of the research plan. The researcher used the mail and the methods of drop-off and pick-up for data collection. To ensure a high response rate suitable for sample size, which is 73 to 75 correspondents and to facilitate data analysis, researchers distributed a few more questionnaires. The researcher obtained 75 answers from 80 surveys. Consequently, the data collection response rate was 100%. The high response rate also accounted for the assistance and support from zone authorities and developers coordinate with selected companies within their zone.

3.5 Reliability and Validity of Method Selected

With each research strategy, instruments picked for the assortment of information must finish the assessments of validity and reliability before they can be viewed as significant measures. The safety of a standard is accomplished when it reliably, and without inclination, measures the ideas it should gauge (Sekaran, 2003). It is built up either through a test and – a re-test where a similar test is regulated to the same respondents at various occasions gets similar outcomes or parallel structure dependability and when a similar experiment with different wordings or arrangement of inquiries likewise brings about the same information (Sekaran, 2003).

The validity, then again, is planned for guaranteeing that the instrument of estimation has tapped the idea it embarks to quantify by including a sufficient portrayal of things that operationalize the idea or "content validity," separates elements on a satisfactory paradigm or "criterion-related validity," and guarantees that the measure utilized fits around the hypotheses for which the test is made. "Construct validity" (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005; Sekaran, 2003), however, and Mouton and Marais (1996) contend that approval is definitely not a need in subjective research as ideas now mirror the universe of the object of study. One approach to guarantee that legitimacy is accomplished in any examination is to direct a pilot investigation of research instruments.

A pilot study is characterized as a smaller than usual rendition of an exploration or a preliminary run led in readiness of a full-scale research and might be directed explicitly to pre-test an examination instrument. (Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001) and Tashakkori and Teddlie (2003) have set up that pilot tests are considered helpful in both quantitative and subjective research. Different creators have featured the significance of the direction of a pilot study as essential to any exploration as it serves the capacity of distinguishing potential blemishes in the estimation instrument (Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001; Watson et al., 2007) and whether ideas have been operated enough.

This is accomplished by pre-testing the instrument on a little number of interviewees having indistinguishable qualities from those in principle study. Sekaran (2003) likewise contends that interviewees can predispose the information gathered in the event that they don't comprehend the inquiries put to them and, as per Calitz (2009), a pilot trial of investigations distinguishes hazy or equivocal articulations in the examination convention while Van Wijk and Harrison (2013)

accept that pilot studies can add worth and believability to the whole research venture. Generally, a pilot study discovers how well an examination instrument will function in the real investigation by distinguishing potential issues and territories that may require modifications.

The pilot study was conducted in this research. In the lead of the pilot testing, endeavors made by the interviewer to guarantee the setting, selection of interviewees, and meeting techniques were as close as those proposed in the fundamental investigation as it would be prudent. The interviewer used similar criteria for the choice of interviewees that shall be used in the actual research. Seven interviewees were selected for the small testing, and questionnaires were disseminated after the interview. The interviewees were from Case C company located in Vientiane capital. This can be beneficial for the interviewer to save time and money for conducting the small study. The initial interview provides the chance to refine, rethink, and explain a few inquiries in the guide.

For instance, question 1 of the meeting convention which was pointed towards deciding the degree of the information on respondents in human resource management of three managers and five operational employees was altered as it was seen. As it was encircled, question 1 would, in general, evoke data about what they thought about human resource management and development. The outcomes of the pilot study confirmed if participants selected have the knowledge and the ability to answer interview questions. Also, questionnaires were disseminated to test if participants understand the way to fill it.

3.6 Data Analysis

3.6.1 Qualitative data analysis of cases studies at the Macro and Micro-level

The research should apply four principles in order to provide high-quality analysis. First, the analysis should demonstrate that it is based on all relevant evidence; second, it should include all conflicting interpretations; third, it should tackle the most crucial aspect of the case study; and fourth, it should bring to the study the previous expert knowledge of the researcher (Yin, 2006). As multiple case studies were used in the first research methodology, the case-oriented analysis was used. The information collected from variable sources was analyzed in the case study stage in order to pre-test and refine the questionnaire. Once all the data are available, a strategy of “relying on theoretical proposals has been adopted to guide the process of data analysis because theoretical proposals can help to decide whether to accept or reject raw data and therefore this is the “first and the most preferred strategy for case-oriented analysis” (Yin, 2006).

The specific procedure suitable for qualitative data analysis for this research was based on the model provided by Creswell (2003), having decided on a data analysis strategy. In analyzing the data collected through qualitative methods, a six-step process was followed:

1) prepare and organize the data

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- 2) review the data
- 3) work out a coding process
- 4) apply the coding process to generate settings or people descriptions as well as categories or themes for analysis
- 5) specify how the description and themes in the qualitative narrative are represented
- 6) interpret or demonstrate the meaning of the data.

Coding is a way of representing data by using numbers. During coding, data is transmitted to a format that facilitates practical analysis from the original notes. It is conducted to organize data to reduce the possibility of errors when reading. Before they are ready for tabulation, editing is necessary to group the data into categories. Interpretation is used to generate an understanding of the concepts and theories of the subject being studied.

There are two qualitative data sets in this study, which were coded manually. The first data set is from an interview with the zone authority, the government, SEZ seniors from SEZ management and development office, and an SEZ consultant regarding policies, opportunities, and the challenges of human resource management and development of Laos SEZs. The data were analyzed through simple coding. Semi-structured questions help the researcher or interviewer to organize the contents recorded the researcher's notes during the interview.

The second arrangement of subjective information is from meeting the director and operational representatives from chosen cases to consider. There are two methods of examination accommodated in the contextual analysis; they were dissected and utilized during the event and cross-case. Investigation inside a solitary case deals with information and examples. This investigation uncovered the instance inside a case organization in HRM arrangements and practices.

Strategies for "coding, ordering and detailing the information" were directed to encourage these procedures. Initially, an exploration-based coding structure was utilized to sort out information for the investigation into points and sub-subjects. This procedure was done physically. Second, an information ordering procedure was embraced to allow an in-order announcing mark to each case so as to look after classification. The letters A to C were assigned as three outside organizations associated with this exploration.

Last, few stages have been taken to make information announcing simpler and more manageable. The scientist finished on the off-chance that examines and point-by-point gives an account of every one of the three cases to start the procedure, covering all interviewees for each situation. This progression bolstered the specialist to check with members in each organization the precision of the discoveries. The reports likewise introduced the cross-case investigation stage.

The succeeding examination was a cross-case investigation with contrasting information and examples over the three case firms. In these three organizations, these uncovered similarities and differences in HRM strategies and practices. To sum up, the three cases were first broken down exclusively by utilizing information strategy triangulation, and afterward, two types of case

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investigations were utilized to feature examples and subjects that rose up out of the information. Likewise, the two cases break down created factors that filled in as the wellspring of the study technique factors.

3.6.2 Quantitative data analysis of the survey

Quantitative information investigation regularly addresses methods of measurable examination, especially in the review of the execution of social components (Amaratunga et al., 2002). Essential factual investigation utilized instruments, for example, factor examination and examination of the relationship. Four fundamental examinations were received for the technique for the study.

First, demographic analysis and descriptive statistics of HRM arrangements and practices and human asset advancement were connected to the overview results. Second, the examination of connection was connected in testing the positive relationship between the free factors of HRM arrangements and practices with enlistment and choice, preparation and improvement, compensation and prizes, execution of evaluations, maintenance and association, and work connection, and the reliant variable of human asset advancement.

Further investigation was fitting if all relationships were sure. Third, testing of the theory was performed based on connection esteems to decide the idea of the association between a needy variable and more than one free factor. Fourth, this research utilized a different straight relapse investigations (Black, 1999). SPSS program was being used in the primary, second, and forward investigations.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethics in social research is indispensable when including individuals as the subjects of study. At any phase of the examination procedure, moral issues may emerge; these issues identify with the rights and commitments of specialists and members (Creswell, 2003; Zikmund et al., 2013). The scientist is required to ensure the privilege of the respondents to classification and security concerning moral contemplations (Zikmund et al., 2013). Prior to leading the examination, endorsement for the exploration ought to be gotten to address the commitments of the scientist completely. When performing information gathering, classification affirmation ought to be given with respect to all gathered data, and members ought to be educated that all archives, composed notes, and sound tapes containing such data will be wrecked at the supplier's solicitation.

As to ethical contemplations in this examination, the compelling interviewees were educated about the motivation behind the procedure of research and information accumulation, including the utilization of semi-organized meetings, preceded by a consent to take an interest in

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the exploration. They additionally told interviewees that they would be ensured privacy and that they reserved the privilege to pull back from being met as analysts.

Assent structures and polls were endorsed from the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland and the boss' earlier accumulated information. Preparatory meetings and assent structures were given to interviewees. The nature and reason for this examination, the obscurity of support, the opportunity to pull back from the meeting whenever, and the techniques to be pursued were altogether educated to all interviewees. As recently expressed, all interviewees got an educated assent structure. Prior to the start of the meeting, this structure was quickly talked about and finished and marked by the members and the analyst, and the structure was kept in a college file organizer.

The meeting utilized sound account and penmanship to record the appropriate responses. Prior to the meeting session, in any case, the interviewee was informed that the meetings recorded would be kept private and utilized for this exploration alone. Moreover, all the interviewers stayed anonymous. All the information was coded to keep singular members from being distinguished. On solicitation and as a significant aspect of the commitments of the researcher, an exploration outline was sent to the interviewee.

Ethical contemplations regarding classification, protection, and obscurity were additionally connected to the review. The respondents were welcome to finish the poll; however, without weight (Salant and Dillman, 1994). Besides, since the respondents were anonymous, there was no reference to explicit respondents to the informal investigation. This added structure to some portion of the privacy in the interview.

3.5 Conclusion of Chapter 3

Chapter 3 explained the adjustment of research methodology. Mixed method was selected in this study and was separated into two-level research. At the macro/zone-level study, secondary data and semi-structured interviews will be conducted to answer research questions 1, 2 & 3. Question 1 will be answered through secondary data, which will be gathered from reports of Laos SEZs, the World Bank, LIO, and so on. Also, Laos SEZs authorities and the developer of the selected zone will be interviewed to answer questions 2 & 3.

At micro/firm-level study, semi-structured and survey questionnaire methods shall be used in the study. Question 4 will be answered through semi-structured interviews to help the researcher explore the rules and activities of HRM of three case study firms located within SEZs. Then, to answer research question 5, the survey questionnaire will be adopted to examine the relationship between HRM of FIEs and perceptions of HR development. Outcomes of the zone and firm-level study will be critically analyzed to answer research questions 6.

Chapter 4: Macro-Level Data Analysis: A case of Laos Zone (Savanh-Seno SEZ)

4.1 Introduction to Chapter 4

Chapter 3 discusses two significant sections, such as research strategy and methodology. Research gaps derived from existing literature demonstrated the absence of systematic examination regarding the advantage of SEZs on the local economy. Therefore, this study is conducted to measure the benefits of SEZs at the Macro/zone-level and Micro/firm level.

Chapter 4 is conducted to measure the effects of SEZ on HR development at the Macro level. Quantitative and qualitative approaches are employed and analyzed in the following sections to measure SEZ benefit at Macro/zone-level. To answer research question 1, the way a Lao zone contributes to employment in three ways such as direct employment, indirect employment, and gender employment will be measured through a quantitative approach. Then, the qualitative approach will be used to answer research questions 2 and 3.

Chapter 4 begins with 4.1 introductions of the chapter. Section 4.2 is a quantitative analysis and proceeds with a qualitative analysis within the section. Within the quantitative analysis, macroeconomic analysis is utilized in selected Laos SEZ and the ways Laos SEZs contribute to employment in three ways such as direct employment, non-direct employment, and gender employment. Thus, qualitative analysis is provided in Section 4.3, which explored the current policies and practices related to human resource development in Laos SEZs. In addition, the opportunities and challenges of implementing the policy were investigated. Chapter 4.4 finalized the findings in Chapter 4.

4.2 A Case of Savanh-Seno SEZ

4.2.1 Background and Development Strategy of Savanh-Seno SEZ

Savanh-Seno Special Economic Zone (SSEZ) was established in 2003 as the first Pilot zone in Laos. The zone is located in Savannakhet province, the second largest province in population and area in Laos. Next to the river Mekong, which forms the border with Thailand at that point, Savannakhet is linked with neighboring Myanmar province by the Second Friendship Bridge. The Bridge was opened to the public in 2007. For several years, the zone struggled for success. At some extent, this is the result of the need to achieve a critical mass of activities to stimulate growth.

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The situation changed as a result of the 2011 floods in Thailand, which had a disastrous cost on lives. The floods also led to the closing of some foreign-invested enterprises and disruptions in global supply chains, particularly in the automotive sector. Accordingly, some companies facing this problem decided to withdraw from the company and relocate to Savan-Seno SEZ (as few others in Laos were then ready), on the basis that their management and production methods were stable and could be transferred elsewhere.

The additional transportation cost would not make much difference to overall profitability. One example of this is Nikon, which opened a factory in Savan-Seno SEZ to conduct some aspect of its manufacturing of primary and middle-level digital SLR cameras and interchangeable lenses, which will continue to be finished in its Ayutthaya home (Thailand). Approximately 800 jobs will be created by this factory, and the management has created its own cross-border value chain. Nowadays, more than 60 companies have announced plans to invest in the zones, and the total investment is listed as US\$223.1 million (as of June 2015).

When plans to create Savan-Seno SEZ were announced, it was widely assumed that Lao would be able to operate in partnership with the Thai border SEZs that were to be spread around the country and designed to be how Thailand would be able to escape from the Middle-Income Trap (Savan-Seno Project Development and Strategy, 2005). However, after the military coup of 2014, the SEZs at the border appeared to be the solution to the supposed security problem posed by the presence of large numbers of cross-border migrant workers.

It was announced that the SEZs at the border would act as internment camps for Lao, Myanmar and Cambodian workers, and then it quickly became clear that the prevailing economic logic was to be abandoned in this case. As a result, the belief that Savan-Seno SEZ and its Lao companions would be able to provide the low-cost logistics, transportation, warehousing, and low skill assembly tasks required by corporations in the paired SEZs has had to be abandoned. In the place of the previous policy, Thailand's junta has proclaimed that the attempt to escape the Middle-Income Trap will be led by the Eastern Economic Corridor (EEC).

The EEC might appear to be quite distant from Savan-Seno SEZ and its activities not directly relevant as anything other than a rival and potential substitute for international investment as if any more such were needed in a region with a growing surfeit of capacity. However, it might be possible that they could be integrated into a single system. How this might be brought about is through interests in China, which sees the two facilities complementary to its growing investments in SEZs of various sorts in Yunnan province. Yunnan is the southwestern province in China that is nearest mainland Southeast Asia, and which has such a long history of cultural, political, social and economic interactions that it has officially been incorporated into the Greater Mekong Sub-region by the Asian Development Bank (as has also, subsequently, the Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region).

Yunnan has some strengths in agriculture, tobacco, non-ferrous metals, and tourism, which, as anticipated, may be enhanced through cooperation with a low-cost, low-skilled logistics center

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(i.e., Savan-Seno SEZ) and a high-skilled production hub (i.e., the EEC). This would act as a variation of emerging Thailand's strategy, by which most Japanese firms switch products between Thailand and neighboring countries, often Cambodia, depending on whether the stage of production for any individual product requires high or low skill and plant.

The initiative would also be a logical addition to China's One Belt One Road policy, which seems to be intended to incorporate all of Europe and Asia into a single economic production and consumption area with China at its center. If this were to occur, then Laos would indeed be one step closer to the goal of converting the country from a buffer state to a crossroads (Pholsena & Banomyong, 2007) but it would remain unclear how much control the Lao government would be able to enforce over events taking place in its territory.

4.3 Quantitative Data Analysis

Chapter 4 represented quantitative and qualitative results derived from information and data at the Macro-level. Quantitative data was analyzed based on secondary data included zones' reports, national static bureau, world bank economic report, and so on. To understand the way Laos SEZ generates employment, a Laos SEZ was chosen as a case study. Results of the case study aimed to answer question 1:

Research Question 1: How does a Laos SEZ generate employment opportunities to the locals?

4.3.1 Analysis of Secondary Data

4.3.1.2 Direct Employment Generation

In 2003, the only operating zone in Laos SEZ was Savan-Seno SEZ (SSEZ). Since the zone was situated in a very remote area, the need for substantial investment in infrastructure was critical for the Laos government. At that time, there were only ten registered companies. Since the budget to develop infrastructure and other facilities to serve investment needs was limited, the government decided to lease the zones to foreign developers divided into four zones (A, B, C, and D) and holds 30 percent of the total share.

After the introduction of the National Committee to SEZs in 2011, SEZ activities exhibited significant progress. In 2011, when the first SEZ Decree No 443/PM was created, a major thrust was given by the government to SEZs. Since then, SSEZ has been expanding rapidly in different sectors. In 2014, the total number of workers in the area was 2,123, including 1,994 local workers. Until 2017, the total number of workers has jumped to 4,793, including 4,610 domestic workers

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(Figure 20). This due to the soaring increased in the number of foreign companies from 52 in 2014 to 105 in 2017.

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017.

Figure 13: Laos and Foreign workers in Savan-Seno SEZ (Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017)

Despite a remarkable increase in SSEZ's employment, their share of manufacturing jobs remains relatively low. The national labor force accounted for 40.8 percent of the total population in Laos (Laos Labor report, 2018). Although Savannakhet is the most populous province that accounted for 15 percent of the total population in Laos, the contribution of the labor force in Savannakhet province is the lowest level accounted for 2.19 percent of the national labor force. The number of laborers employed accounted for 12.4 percent of the total workforce in the province. Workers employed within SSEZ contributed to only 0.5% of the overall population in the province in 2017 (Figure 21).

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017 and Lao Labor Report, 2017.

Figure 14: Share of Labor Force in Savan-Seno SEZ (Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017; Lao Labor Report, 2017)

Figure 21 above demonstrated employment creation of SSEZ, the oldest and one of the most developed SEZs in Laos in terms of employment, exports, and investments. Since its establishment in 2003 and until 2016, Laos SEZs provided less than 1% of total production jobs (World Bank, 2016). Their share of manufacturing has been slightly above 1 percent since 2017. Therefore, one might argue that job creation in SEZs is marginal in Laos relative to an area outside the zone.

The reasons that the zones in Laos remained very small, and it is not surprising that the share of SEZs in total employment is insignificant until recently, virtually stagnant. However, SEZ has had a significant impact on the regional/local employment situation, which is not captured in the overall picture. For example, within three years of development, total employment, including foreign and domestic workers in SSEZ, has doubled from 2,123 workers in 2014, and 4,793 workers in 2017 4,610 of whom are Laotian workers. This has had a tremendous impact on job creation in and around the SEZ regions.

In any case, in the regular part in neighboring territories, there are no elective businesses opening doors for them, and from that viewpoint, a zone is seen (even by specialists) as instrumental in creating work and easing their district's destitution. An HR manager uncovered during the meetings that most Laotian laborers had no formal wellspring of salary before they joined the zone. A few units in labor-serious areas, for example, electronic parts, utilize essential or even non-instructed specialists and give preparing on-the-work. This has improved the district's work situation.

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Critics argue, however, that openings for work made inside SEZ won't supplement business; they will supplant existing occupations outside the zones because of the movement/redirection of speculation exercises from the terrain to SEZ. Maybe the marvel is unique to Laos. It must be seen, be that as it may, that Laos SEZs are set up to pull in just a fair amount of arranged exercises that would somehow, or another not have happened because of poor venturing atmosphere and high monetary expense of generation. The search for household market is mostly of FDIs outside the zones. In any case, the new zones pulled in various remote financial specialists who were hesitant to come to Laos as of not long ago.

Another angle to argue the statement is that most of the labor outside the zone is low-skill labor with a lack of industrial working experience. Those workers never have a career and had worked in farming or agriculture before they came to work within the zone. Those agricultural or farming activity is often not to market but to serve the basic needs of their families. Therefore, SSEZ provides them formal jobs. In sum, Savan-Seno SEZ has made considerable progress on employment generation during the last few years. Yet, the SEZ does not contribute significantly to the employment of the province where the zone is located.

4.3.1.3 Female Employment

In similar observation on many other SEZs when viewed from a comparative perspective, the proportion of female workers in total employment is substantial in Savan-Seno SEZ. While in the initial stages the number was above 70% in many developing countries, it was more than 80%. From 2003-2017, it continuously increased to hit 112% (Table 6). Yet, based on Table 6, the soaring trend in female employment is not consistent during phases of Savanh-Seno SEZ development. The number of female workers from the initial stage of development from 2003-2011 was not very significant.

At this point, the zone developer explained during the interview that during this phase infrastructure was developed and, therefore, needs more male workers to support construction work. He also added that there were more foreign workers, especially engineering workers, than the locals. The significant increase was from 2011 when Japanese companies had moved from Thailand during the flood disasters. Also, a human resource manager in a Japanese company reported during the focus group interview that their companies prefer to employ female workers who are more familiar with stitching, and most of them apply for manufacturing work due to their low-level of education. Accordingly, the share of female workers has consistently increased in the case of Savan-Seno and, therefore, contributed significantly to female employment in the region (Figure 22).

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017.

Table 5: The Share of domestic workers in Savan-Seno SEZ from 2003-2017 (Savan-Seno SEZ annual report, 2017)

Redactions due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 15: Percentage change of female workers in Savan-Seno 2003 to 2017

Critics emphasize that the female workforce in SEZs are typically between the ages of 20 and 25 with weak bargaining power and, therefore, are often exploited. Hence, job creation in the area does not empower them (Aggarwal, 2011). The samples in this sample study also reveal (Table 7) that most women are in the 20-29 age group. The figures are not very different for male workers as well. Survey results show that the age distribution of male workers is also highly skewed in the 20-29 age group, with 59 percent of males.

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Enterprises Report.

Table 6: Distribution of age of male and female workers as of the year 2017 (Enterprises report)

While taking a gander at ladies' conjugal status (Table 8), a more ladies in the zone are unmarried in contrast to male specialists. The reason may be established in the nation's long-haul social molding. Due to particular financial foundations, single ladies (unmarried/widows/divorced people) are among the most vulnerable segments in creating nations. Consequently, their monetary strengthening is significant, and the SEZ can assume a vital job here. Nevertheless, comparing the data of other countries in Asia such as Thailand, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, Laos ranks 5th in the world for equality of labor force participation and is 13th globally for equality of opportunity and participation in the economy. This demonstrated moderate bargaining power of women labor and foreign firms within SEZ might be a significant part in enhancing ability since more women workforce within the zone.

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Enterprise Report.

Table 7: Men's and women's marital status in Savan-Seno SEZ (Enterprise report)

In the future perspective, younger women will sooner or later move out of the zone. Based on the National Labor Force, Laotian women get married between 20-29 years old (National Labor Force Report, 2016), and those between 18-25 years old are low-skilled labor working within the zone. Although pieces of evidence support the hypothesis that knowledge spillover occurs when labor moves from zone to non-zone, critics claimed that those laborers are young who still have less skills and were trained only just a few weeks.

Nonetheless, this points out that Laos SEZs, especially Savan-Seno SEZ, are changing their gender working structure in the manufacturing sector. Although many Laotian women have less opportunity in education than men, the SEZ provides an opportunity for them to have a formal career. The legal profession helps those women to become more independent, earn more income, and offer them working experiences to improve their career pathway. However, those young

women have low bargaining power, which is inevitable in the least developed country. Therefore, a comprehensive human resource management policy should be more focused on protecting and enhancing the equality of women.

4.3.1.4 Indirect Employment Generation (Sub-Contract Evidences)

However, the effect of employment outside of SEZs is dependent on the zone industry's backward and forward connections with local suppliers of raw materials and other required inputs, as well as the SEZs' success in attracting investment (Farole, 2011). Creating backward linkages with expanding investment in zones could certainly help create more out-of-zone employment. Indirect job creation is inevitable in any country where SEZs or EPZs located. Yet, this depends on what kind of job has been created. To some extent, an indirect post created from the establishment of local firms has contracts with firms within SEZs, mostly Small-Medium enterprises or infrastructure and construction enterprises inside the zone (Aggarwal, 2011).

Although very few pieces of evidence support the statement, the research attempts to test the hypothesis if the SEZs enhance business activities of local firms and, therefore, create more job opportunities outside the SEZ. Although there is no static measure to indicate if the number of jobs has been created outside SEZ, the indirect measure can look at subcontract evidence between firms inside and outside the SEZ. Following zone and enterprises' report (Table 9), 32 percent of foreign and local firms in SSEZ reported that they have at three to five contracts, and 28 percent of them have more than five contracts with local companies providing complementary goods and services company or suppliers.

Table 8: Subcontract evidence between local companies and firms within Savan-Seno SEZ (Zone development report, 2016)

Most of the local firms surrounding SSEZ are Small-Medium enterprises (SMEs) according to the researcher's field survey. Those SMEs such as minimarts, restaurants, hotels, laundry shops, cleaning companies, and so on serve employees and companies within SEZs daily.

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The development of those local enterprises might have occurred since those SMEs must adjust their products and service to fulfill the requirement of foreign firms or employees within SEZs. For instance, a hotel near the zone-hired managers from Thailand to train local staff. In sum, it can be said that Savan-Seno SEZ spurred business activities of local counterparts, especially SMEs and therefore jobs have been created indirectly. Also, it looks like those SMEs have been adjusting their business standards to fulfill the needs of firms within the zone.

4.4 Qualitative Data Analysis

Chapter 4 also included information on overall Laos SEZs analyzed in a qualitative approach. After quantitative analysis, this chapter focuses on an in-depth analysis of the 2nd and 3rd questions.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges and opportunities of Laos SEZs in the context of human resource development?

Research Questions 3: What are the current policies and incentives offered by the government to enhance human capital in SEZs?

In-depth interviews related to government authorities and zone developers were conducted to understand current policies and incentives related to human capital accumulation in SEZs. Interview participants included a senior manager from an SEZ management and development office, Savan-Seno economic board, the zone developer, and SEZ consultant. A senior manager and Savan-Seno commercial board from the SEZ management and development office were selected and appointed by the head of the office. The zone developer and SEZ consultant were selected and appointed by the researcher.

Material related to Laos SEZs were provided by participants before interviews such as SEZs decree, SEZs strategy and development (2017-2022), project calling list, labor, and economic report of Laos SEZs and project calling lists. The interview was conducted in various places depends on the preference of interviewees. The interview findings were analyzed in the below paragraphs.

4.4.1 Analysis of Semi-Structured Interview

4.4.1.1 Potential Benefits of Laos SEZs

Although the SEZ's program was not viewed as the first choice for economic transformation in the Laos, specific ways in which the program can address economic challenges were mentioned from an SEZ consultant. An interview consultant was conducted in the SEZ management and development office after a consultation meeting, which the researcher joined

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during the data collection period in Laos. Firstly, SEZs can offer diverse business activities in Laos and therefore improve current macroeconomic conditions. This shall help improve GDP, boosting local productivity and thus, reduce poverty of Laotian. He said:

“Laos SEZs is no panacea to resolve all economic problems... Yet, we believe that SEZs can help sectoral diversification if specific industry activities to target, such as manufacturing, and tourism are focused based on market demand for those activities in the area. Each SEZ can cater to these activities by offering specialized infrastructure, facilities, and services designed to meet their specific needs.”

If it is well-managed, the diversion of business activities might help the government to improve macroeconomic conditions by addressing current account deficits. An early version of the modern SEZ, export processing zones, was used as a tool for strengthening the developing countries' trade balances by boosting exports (Farole, 2011). While direct export subsidies, such as conditioning tax incentives on export activity, should be avoided as WTO-illegal, SEZs can still help promote exports, and thereby improve trade balances. SEZ consultant implied several strategies to achieve the objectives. The government can be eliminating non-tariff barriers in the SEZs, such that SEZ enterprises can export goods subject to simplified documentary requirements, shorter timeframes, and modern customs procedures, and in some cases, even leverage better transportation infrastructure (such as through in-zone airports).

Also, giving SEZs extraterritorial status for the purposes of customs, such that foreign goods can be brought into the SEZs duty-free and used in products that are then exported without every applying tariff. Other ways such as treating domestic goods and services sold to SEZ enterprises as exports, entitling them to duty-drawback and other benefits granted to exports, and encouraging SEZ enterprises to source products from domestic suppliers through financial incentives and 'soft' incentives such as supplier matching programs and associated technology transfer arrangements. Under these programs, more domestically made goods will become suitable for export through scaling up of production and improvements to quality.

Secondly, SEZs might help Laos on improving trade facilitation and integration with global value chains – The consultant said:

“SEZs can integrate countries with global and regional trade networks by eliminating tariff and non-tariff barriers.”

Along with that, SEZs improve investment climates by reducing regulatory barriers to investment through policy reforms, reducing bureaucratic/procedural hurdles, and delivering high-quality infrastructure to support industry clusters. The same mechanisms mentioned above on addressing current account deficit might help address this issue as well. This involves creating a unique legal and institutional framework for the SEZs, with liberalized policies and a dedicated regulatory authority with the power to consolidate and independently perform most regulatory functions on behalf of all levels of government for SEZ businesses.

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Lastly, it can attract workers with industrial occupations and improve labor productivity. As the consultant mentioned that:

“Since manufacturers have had difficulty finding enough skilled workers, the SEZ can develop ways of attracting workers from agricultural occupations.”

Attractive worker training programs should be provided in the zones to provide Lao workers with the skills needed for the activities targeted in the zones. Connections should also be made with existing educational and training institutions in Laos to help match graduates with SEZ employers in targeted sectors. In addition, life in manufacturing should be made more desirable within the SEZs. Among the possibilities for doing this include negotiating arrangements with the private-sector SEZ developers and operators to provide attractive and safe worker accommodations, common spaces, child care, health clinics, cultural amenities, and other types of services and “social infrastructure.” Furthermore, creating clear guidelines for employers on standards for working conditions and assisting them with compliance (Laos SEZs strategy, 2016).

He implied that the government side could provide incentives, such as rent reduction, developers, operators, and enterprises, training to workers, establishment of more flexible leave and working hour policies, professional development/career advancement opportunities, and other practices desired by workers. In addition, arranging for SEZ operators and employers to reach out to prospective workers by visiting cities and villages and hosting on-site visitation days can be necessary.

4.4.1.2 Current Challenges of Laos SEZs

Apart from opportunity, challenges on SEZ development were explored by interviewing a zone developer and a vice president economic board of Savan-Seno SEZ. While collecting data at the micro level, an interview with the zone developer and the vice president was conducted at the developer’s office located within the zone. The main discussion related to research questions pointed out that logistical challenge and lack of human capital accounted for the slow development of several Laos SEZs.

Firstly, since Laos has no seaport, logistics become difficult and expensive to investors. Most of Laos SEZs located within the remoted area usually developed to become a new town instead of focusing on export-oriented zones. Most of the zones located near the border depend on Thai and Vietnam seaport, which makes logistics become more expensive than neighboring countries such as Thailand, Vietnam, and Cambodia. Nevertheless, the government is cooperating with its neighbors to resolve the challenge. The zone developer provided an example:

“We knew that logistics could be a challenge before developing this zone. Yet, we expected that a new railway link between China and Singapore running through Laos should eliminate the logistical challenge faced by investors. The project is expected to be finished by 2020.”

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The second major problem of Laos SEZs is the lack of human capital. Most of the workers come from the rural area with basic agricultural skills that had entered the zone for the first time. The unfamiliar industrial routine accounted for very high retention within the enterprises located in the zone. Human capital in SEZ is extremely significant for SEZ development. The labor force is very significant to companies that operate efficiently (Wang, 2015). Obviously, in Laos, the skills required for these clusters were not available.

Thus, attracting employees with relevant technical know-how and stimulating spill-over of knowledge to the host economy is a critical success factor. Education would be transferred to citizens at a later stage who would, in turn, set up new business economic industries and services. It is also essential to link the cluster-specific industries with vocational institutes in order to provide them with the calibre needed.

It is crucial that these institutes a concept that firms in the zones would have a significant impact on the development of human capital (Wang, 2015). In addition to the challenge of low skill workers, Laos SEZs unable to attract local workers to the zone. The zone developer stated that:

“Although we have enough workforce, most of them are low-skilled workers who lack of industry working experience. Also, most young workers are immigrants from a neighbour, especially Thailand.”

The statement explained the reason behind the above results of the employment generation of the case study of Savan-Seno SEZ, which is ineffective in attracting local workers. Those younger workers in the province relocated to Thailand. This immigration might not have caused by the higher wage in Thailand compared with Laos but might be working conditions and the environment. For younger workers, this factor seems to play a significant part in their decision to work in Thailand.

Furthermore, based on the SEZs development report (2017), firms within the zones, especially those developed by the Chinese, seem to prefer to hire laborers from the Southern part of China. This might happen due to Chinese workers have experienced longer working hours and complex industry working routines from China. Also, most investors within the zones are Chinese companies so that it would be easier for them to manage workers compose the same culture and language. Nevertheless, the situation is gradually improving at a particular time since the zone developer and investor are coordinating with local authorities to focus on resolving the challenge. The zone developer said that:

“The situation is getting better these couple of years. We are coordinating with local vocational education institutes, provincial labor unions, and so on to tackle the challenge.”

4.4.1.3 Existing Human Resource Development Policies of Laos SEZs

Along with the provided working papers on SEZ decree, which just passed the National Congress at the end of 2018, SEZ management officer explained further on current policies and incentives offered by the government. In sum, those incentives are not very outstanding compared with other investment incentives outside SEZs. Labor-related regulations are based on the national labor law. The policies are focused on fiscal incentives provided for zone developers and investors.

For the developer who develops land and infrastructure in SEZ, they are entitled to receive facilities, customs and tax promotion incentives such as land lease, one-stop service, special incentives on import-export tax, profit tax, and value-added tax. Other incentives, such as receiving investment support privilege, are mentioned in the Law on Investment Promotion. Developers shall receive additional incentives based on their negotiation and the decision set in the Development Agreement, which will be according to conditions, location, and characteristics of remote areas, a business activity that the government gives priority to.

Investors or domestic and foreign business units in SEZ are entitled to receive customs and tax incentives. Most incentives were based on the Investment Promotion Law and tax regulation such as value-added tax, incentives for the use of electricity and water supply, and discount import raw material tax. Other non-fiscal incentives also provided such as the right to hold real estate ownership, long-stay visa, and one-stop service facilitations granted in each SEZ.

4.5 Conclusion of Chapter 4

To answer questions 1, 2, and 3, Chapter 4 attempted to analyzed Macro-level data through a quantitative and qualitative approach. Findings were summarized in below table 10.

Quantitative analysis

RQ1: How do Laos SEZs generate employment opportunities to local?

No. Finding	Topic	Finding
Finding 1:	Direct employment	Under a decent investment climate, Laos SEZ generates employment opportunities to local people, which can be seen through the soaring number of employments within the zone from 2003-2018. Yet, the zone employment

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		contributes only a small fraction of national hiring and provincial employment where the zone located.
Finding 2	Gender employment	SEZ generates employment for female workers. The number of female workers within the zone covers more than 80 percent of total workers. Those female workers also enroll in management sections.
Finding 3	Indirect employment	SEZ enhances business activities of local surrounded by the zone and therefore, indirectly generate employment outside the zone. This can be seen from the sub-contract pieces of evidence from the firms and linkage between the zone and domestic economy.

Qualitative Analysis

RQ2: What are the challenge and opportunities of Laos SEZs in the context of human resource development?

RQ 3: What are the current policies and incentives offered by the government to enhance human capital in SEZs?

No Finding	Description	Finding
Finding 1	Potential benefits of SEZs in the context of Laos	If managed well, SEZs in Laos context should: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have diverse business activities • Capture regional value chain • Enhance human capital
Finding 2	Challenge of Laos SEZs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistic challenge • Lack of human capital

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Finding 3	Incentives and regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No specific policy focuses on enhancing human capital (based on national labor law)• Focus on fiscal incentives based on national investment promotion law such as import and export tariff and income tax• Other incentives such as land lease, one-stop service• New SEZs management decree 2018 included real estate policy
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Table 9: Summaries findings Chapter 4

Chapter 5: Micro-Level Data Analysis: Cases Study of Foreign-Invested Enterprises in Laos Zones

5.1 Introduction to Chapter 5

Research framework demonstrated systematic investigations regarding outcomes of SEZs in two levels, including the macro and micro level. Chapter 4 discusses the measurement at the macro or zone level. The previous chapter employed quantitative analysis to examine the way a Laos zone generated employment in three ways, such as direct employment, gender employment, and sub-contract evidence (non-direct job). Also, HR regulations of Laos SEZs, especially HR development policies, were explored through semi-structured interviews. Nevertheless, although the selected zone (Savanh-Seno SEZ) generates employment inside and outside the zone and has been shaping female workforce structure, employment plays an insignificant role in employment in the province and national employment.

Yet, we cannot assume that Laos SEZs does not or has very few impacts on HR development since numbers of employment are not the only indicator of HR development. Therefore, Chapter 5 focuses on measuring Micro benefits at the firm level. At the firm level, a case study of FIEs located within two most developed zones, such as Savan-Seno SEZ and VITA Park, is conducted. In this chapter, a qualitative and quantitative approach is employed. The chapter begins with a qualitative approach to answer research question 4. Later, the survey questionnaire will be conducted to answer the research question 5. Outcomes from the survey also support the answer to question 4.

Chapter 5 begins with this introduction 5.1. Later, qualitative analysis and followed by quantitative analysis to measure the impact of Laos SEZs on HR development at the Micro level. The qualitative data analysis in section 5.2 begins with a within-case analysis in section 5.2.1. In line with this, Cross-Case Analysis has already been mentioned in Section 5.2.2, which examines the HRM policies and activities used on HRM in the three firms included in the case study located in Savan-Seno SEZ and VITA Park by comparing their practices. Section 5.2.3 offers a conclusion to this qualitative data analysis.

Subsequently, the quantitative data analysis is organized into section 5.3, commencing with analyzing data of 75 participants in Section 5.3.1. This segment included demographics of the sample, descriptive analysis of HRM policy and practice, and Descriptive Analysis of Perception of HR development. Section 5.3.2 portrays an analysis of the correlation between HRM policy and Practice and HR development. Section 5.3.3 provides Hypotheses reports. Section 5.3.4 offers multiple linear sample analysis. Lastly, Section 5.3.5 provides a conclusion to the chapter.

5.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

The aftereffects of the top to bottom investigation of the data gathered from the qualitative analysis were spoken to by the subjective examination in Chapter 5. The formal HRM regulations and exercises are inspected utilizing five zones. These are enlistment and determination, preparing and advancement, compensation and rewards, maintenance, workforce's privilege, and security. Besides, it likewise investigates the components of Laotian culture and authoritative culture on HRM rehearses. These variables incorporate the way of thinking and estimations of the organization, order, position and status, style of administration, the inclusion of representatives in primary leadership forms, and the principles and guidelines of the organization.

The challenges in qualitative data analysis are the identification of data patterns and proof of confidence. Triangulated information was obtained using data from interviews, observations, and reviews of the companies' publicly available documents. In this case, the data patterns explained the HRM practices of selected foreign companies investing in two Laos SEZs and how Laotian culture and organizational culture influence the implementation of HRM and those companies' practices.

5.2.1 Within-Case Analysis

The within-case analysis explores the human resource management policies and activities of the individual foreign-invested enterprises located within two major Laos SEZs, including Savan-Seno SEZ and VITA Park, with respect to research question 4. The responses of employers and employees supported comparison-and-contrast analysis and permitted triangulation. The three companies from the case study were foreign investment firms characterized by a prescribed framework of an organization, equal distribution of tasks, structured organizational process, and departments of personnel accountable for policies and activities of HRM. These firms were well-known international firms.

In-depth interview intended answering the 4th research question:

Research Question 4: What human resource policies and activities regarding “recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration rewards and appraisals, retention, union labor, and regulation” were enforced within foreign-invested firms in Laos SEZs?

The dialogue of HRM policies and activities included managers, supervisors, and operational employers of the firms. The assessment will be supported by data gathered through semi-structured interviews, observation, and analysis of documents.

5.2.1.1 Case A

a. Company Profile

Case A was an ophthalmic lens manufacturing company located within zone C of Savan-Seno SEZ. It now manufactures 120 million lenses per year in Thailand, which are exported across ASEAN as well as India and China. Now that a stable and reliable zone is available in Laos, the company has taken advantage and used its Bangkok base to manage this cross-border value chain. Currently, there are 67,000 employees in 70 countries worldwide, including 313 people in Laos manufacturer, established in 2013 with 75 years of investment registered.

Under the project manager, five departments handled the company operations, including human resource, financial, logistic, production, and maintenance department. Apart from the maintenance department, the rest of the departments are managed by the Laotian manager. The human resource department conducted HRM activities, including employee record-keeping, recruiting, training, and other activities concern with human resource management within the organization. It was also responsible for the entire responsibilities involving organizations from outside, like the government, zone authorities, and local vocational schools.

b. Summary of daily recording

The visitor was not allowed to enter the production area where machinery and other technical equipment located. While observing the production process through the glass window, all employees wearing gloves, masks, and uniform to ensure health and safety. Inside the company, it is clean and tidy but required more fresh air to reduce heat. There are facilities such as the canteen and toilet available in each department.

c. Interview participants

The interview was conducted in two-level positions, including management and operational level. The face to face interview at the management level includes the manager of the HR and the manager of finance. Interview responses of the manager of the HR and the manager of finance were taken during break time in the morning and afternoon at the management office located within the zone. Three females and one male from the different departments were selected by the researcher and interviewed at the canteen during the lunch break.

After the consent form was signed, the interviewer set up audio recording and informed the interviewees to know that the interview was recorded but will be shared for academic propose only. The audio recorder was set aside to increase confidence between interviewees and the interviewer. With a focus on the semi-structured questionnaire, the interview human resource manager lasted 25 minutes, and the rest of the interviews lasted between 10 to 15 minutes.

d. Human resource management polies and practices

The company's document analysis indicated that this company-maintained records of personnel. Forms were used to record details of employees such as biographical data of employees, interview forms, and contracts for employment. The HR department was responsible for the company's human resource policy, rule and regulation, manpower planning, recruitment, selection and employment, training, development and orientation, performance appraisal, compensation and motivation, welfare, payroll, disciplinary and grievance, employee relation, career management, promotion, general affair, security, employee transportation, social connection, housekeeping, and canteen.

- ***Recruitment and selection***

The company recruitment policy was based on national labor regulation. The company shall give priority to Laotian workers, especially the person who targets under poverty alleviation programs. In case necessary, it is permitted to accept foreign workers not more than 10 percent, and workers with specialized skills may undertake not more than 20% of the total number of workers in that unit. Furthermore, the foreign worker working in Laos has an obligation to transfer expertise to Laos worker. Given priority to Laos workers in management and non-management level is a critical global strategy of the company since this help overcomes challenge on local adaptation.

However, due to technical sophistication in the production process and maintenance, the company management also hires experts from their headquarters in Europe and a branch in Thailand. Those managers and experts usually relocated from Thailand, where one of their subsidiaries was located. Some of them do not live in Laos, but rather travel when it is needed. Yet, the company is relying on local managers to cover more than 80 percent of total employees at the management level. For the operational level, hiring domestic workers is one of the human resource management policies and strategies of the company. A Laotian worker has lower wage comparing to their peers in neighboring countries.

In practice, the decisions for recruiting employees at the operational level were made by staff managers based on the advice from the production department. Staffing was once to two or three weeks during the initial period of the company establishment. For the managerial level, the recruitment decision was made by a general manager from Thailand. External and internal recruitment sources have been used to obtain suitable candidates. The staff manager described the recruitment system for managerial and operational staff as follows:

“For the management level, as part of promotion and retention, the company uses advertisements in the newspaper, magazine, or selects from among our employees. At an operational level, we usually rely on the local magazine, advertise on vacancies board in vocational schools and several

training centers, and some of the employees applied from words of friends who are working in the company.”

The manager participants said they applied through local newspapers. They do not have any friends or relatives who used to work in the company since they are the first management group in the factory. The selection process included the individuals’ interviews on education, working experiences, salary expectations, work ethics, and commitment. They have 5 to 10 years of working experience in a related field before applying for positions. The company HR manager used to work in the government sector. There is no written test in the process. At the operational level, the selection process used simple genuine tests like sampling and numerical experiments. Working experience is not necessary but might include in interview question for promotion and reward propose. The criteria described by the manager of human resource:

“The main requirements for management roles are education and work experience, but we do not have much expectation for operational positions as long as they pass the small practice test, they will be hired. The company lacks the workforce at an operational level and do not want to set much standard on our recruitment and selection. Instead, we rely on on-the-job-training.”

- **Training and development**

At the operational level, on-the-job-training is the only training for new employees that will last for two months. This included working under the supervision of a trainer. The trainers can be the leader, supervisors, or managers, depending on each department. Most of the training was aimed at familiarizing new employees with the work environment and teaching them how to do the job. It is a company policy to provide health and safety training for workers, and it is mentioned in labor protection regulated by the government. The authority concerned from the government sector used to come to check if the company use compulsory requirements to instill a safe and hygienic workplace. Nevertheless, the government or training agencies should provide mandatory health and safety training and certificate at companies’ expenses to obligate them in health and safety activity.

The company’s human resource management policy tends to focus on building the capacity of an employee at the management level. In some cases, the managers were sent to headquarter in Europe for five to six weeks training while the supervisors and other employees at the management level were trained in Thailand and local for six months. There is a training going on during the initial phase of business operation from 2013 to 2015. In recent years, new supervisors or future managers who are qualified engineers, logistic officers, or production technicians were trained from three to six months regarding technical requirements and company management on local training centers. An interview with the manager of human resource demonstrated the criteria in selecting the candidates for training at the supervisory level:

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“After the selection process, new managers in each department were sent to the headquarters in Europe and Thailand for six months of training. After that, we choose applicants who are disciplined, industrious, creative, and promotable supervisors and operators.”

- **Remuneration, reward and performance appraisals**

Earnings of employees at the operational level should follow the regional minimum wage established by the government. The national minimum salary range of laborer for USD 78.25 per month has made for quite a noticeable difference with Thai expectation where the government raised the minimum wage to 300 baht or USD 10 per day means how shocking the economy relies out of low labor price. This is one of the main reasons that the company relocated its plant from Thailand to Laos. Case A’s national minimum salary used the basic pay for employees in operations, including allowances for tenure. The human resource manager mentioned that:

‘Compared with other similar manufacturing firm outside the zone, our wage is quite higher at the management level. Also, our wage for the operational level is above the national standard’.

Apart from national labor law, other benefits include childbirth benefits for women workers who were able to take maternity leave three months before and after birth. After birth, this full paid leave was provided. The human resource explained the remuneration system as follows:

“Besides providing above national minimum wage, we also give an allowance based on their absence in a year which should not be more than 60 days. Yet, this does not include national holiday on various occasions throughout the years.”

Apart from wages, the national labor law requires each unit shall take part in the social security scheme by contributing to the Social Security Fund to implement, in accordance with the regulations, the social security system for employees, and employers. Most of the paperwork regarding social security is a response by the training center and zone authority. The employees that the researcher interviewed found that some of them had not registered with the scheme yet. The long process of registration seemed to cause dissatisfaction. The interview confirmed their dissatisfaction with the system of remuneration:

“We are not satisfied, because our basic wage is the same as new employees although we have worked for five years. It also does not consider the skills and working experience. The difference is only on the tenure allowance, which is very small.”

The performance appraisals in case A, intended to determine allowance increase, bonuses, and promotion of each worker. Supervisors in each department conduct performance appraisals and report the results to their managers. The standards for the evaluations consist of behavior, cooperation, accountability, productivity, and creativity. Nevertheless, the rules were not the same from the employees' perspective. As one of the operational employees mentioned that:

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“The performance appraisals are based on our output or whether we can achieve our target or not. Our team leader will only give feedback on our poor performance. Often the team leaders work together and help us achieve our target because this is also part of their responsibility.”

Learning and career advancement in the manufacturing and maintenance departments were very minimal. The only career paths that were possible led to team leaders or supervisors. The employees were not informed of the promotion policy and the selection process. The participants of the study (workers) from those departments warranted, *“We have never been promoted,” and that “The company appointed the new team leader directly.”* Hence, the promotion was deemed unfair.

- **Retention**

Retention of employees at the operational level remain a significant challenge to human resource management of the company. In each year, the number of workers has changed continuously up and down from 200 to 300 people. Human resource manager mentioned that:

“Retention is a major challenge for our human resource management. It was worse during the initial establishment of the company. This due to local people's lack of industrial working background such as having discipline and not getting used to long working hours. The situation is getting better since many local training schools are developed to supply the basic industrial working knowledge to the workers before getting into the job.”

The company's policy is to provide facilities to workers such as accommodation, transportation, and a better working environment. Also, the company focuses on the career development of workers from the operational level, who is performing well to get promoted in time. At the management level, employees receive a bonus each year and an increase in allowances based on years of working. Also, there is an opportunity to grow in their career pathway. A manager stated that:

“I have been working in the company since its establishment. Although the allowance and bonuses are minimal, working in an international company in some period shall enhance my career pathway in the future.”

Employee participants at the operational level said that *“I prefer to have a career and have more permanent income than working in the rice field, which heavily depends on seasons and weather in each year. Working in this manufacturing firm helps me to support my family back home every month...”*

- **Union and labor relation**

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That national labor policy indicates that all companies must have a labor union or projects with the legally authorized business license. Case A permitted its staff to sign up for one official association, which is the National Labor Union. According to the manager of human resources, the Union's pursuits include the negotiation of wage and company policy issues experienced by the employees. However, most of the staff did not participate actively in Union activities. Some participants of the team mentioned, *“We do not like to make noise as long as the company pays us on time. Since we started working, the company has never been late on paying our salary.”*

e. The dominant person responsible for HR practice

It occurred that nearly all HRM activities were conducted by the Personnel Manager. His accountabilities, however, covered other tasks, including executing the functions of public relations and enforcing rules and policies of the company. It surfaced that there were only a few departments in the organizational structure of case A, and this led to the same person covering more tasks and responsibilities. Therefore, workers at the management level often must perform a greater variety of functions.

d. Analysis of findings

It seems like the company Case A implemented human resource policies that follow the national labor policy. It appeared that employees at the management level performed formal human resource practices rather than the operational level. It is argued that informal recruitment might be *viva voce*. The casual selection might depend on a relationship such as family members or friends between the selector and new employees (Myers and Dreachslin, 2007). It looks like employees at the operational level could not access or rely on job advertisements, but rather trust their friends or relative who used to work in the company. Managers were selected by the general manager from Thailand, and the human resource manager is authorized to select staff.

On-the-job training gives the idea that all new joiners should undergo it. Essential health and safety knowledge were included in the training based on the requirement of national labor regulation. Aggarwal (2011) argued that training for non-management employees lasts for a short time and shall not contribute much to human resource development in the country. However, the contribution of human capital appeared to be more noticeable at the management level. New managers of the company were sent abroad for training in their European headquarter and a major branch in Thailand. Supervisors and heads of technicians were sent to Thailand or the local training center for three to six months.

It was alleged that the system of remuneration and rewards provided all employees with a fair salary at all levels comparing to similar firms outside the zone. Yet, there is no evidence on the comparison. There was, however, unhappiness about the same fixed wage for old and new

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employees, the low allowance rate and bonuses, the delinquency to claim social security benefits for all employees. Performance appraisals were enforced to calculate impending allowances, bonuses, and promotions. It is not intended for employees' career advancement.

Suharnomo (2009) argues that supervisors need loyalty and obedience in cultures with significant influence and that performance assessments, therefore, prefer to use behavioral parameters. The staff just followed the criteria implemented to reduce risks. The workers asserted, however, that performance assessments were based solely on their productivity. There is bias in the promotion process, especially among production, logistic, and maintenance departments. Table 11 finalize employers; employees' interviews on human resource management practices of case A.

Human resource management policy and practice	The employers	The employees
1. Recruitment and selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Following national labor regulation by giving priority to Laotian worker at management and operational level - Using formal recruitment - Using the internal and external source - Using a local advertisement - For the management level, the selection was based on education and working experiences - For non-manager, the selection was based on the simple, practical test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manager and supervisor received vacancies information from public advertisement such as newspaper and local magazine and undergoing the interview - Non-manager employees received vacancies information through friends/family and local training center and undergoing a simple, practical test
2. Training and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-the-job training in the workplace for two months - Apart from national labor law and the company HR policy, the training included health and safety training - New managers were sent to headquarter for short training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operational employees received on-the-job training for two months - Management employees received three to six months of training within and outside the country

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	- New supervisor and potential promote employees were sent to Thailand and local training center for three to six months	
3. Remuneration, reward, and appraisals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Performing above minimum wage - Employees' absence should not be more than 60 days excluding national holiday - Employees shall receive bonus and allowance based on their discipline and years of working - Providing pregnancy benefits for female workers based on federal labor regulation. - Performance appraisals were conducted by supervisors and then were reported to managers of each department - Managers were appraised by the general director 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaints on the same salary for all active staff - Claims on a small allowance - Some of them have not registered the social security regime since it's too complicated - The appraisals were based on workers' production only - The advancement procedure was unclear
4. Retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing better necessary facilities such as transportation, accommodation, and food - Providing bonus, allowances, and opportunity for all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Employees prefer to be employees in the company and have more permanent income rather than being a farmer
5. Union and labor relation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company enrolled in national labor union when getting a business license 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They were rarely involved in union activities unless a significant problem occurs

Table 10: Interview of the employers and employees on human resource management policy and practice of Case A

5.2.1.2 Case B

a. Company Profile

Case B is a Danish business producing high quality and safe work ware. The company was established in 1982 and the headquarters was built in Denmark. The company opened its

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manufacturing firm in a Laos SEZ, VITA Park in 2013. It constructed the 9,000 sqm building, and the new production unit became the fourth series of factories in South East Asia. The company employed more than 2,400 people in Asia included approximately 750 employees in Laos factories, producing the work ware that is developed, marketed, and sold by their colleagues in Europe.

The company intends to integrate all aspects of the CSR policy in the new facilities in Laos as a part of their global company strategy like they had in Vietnam factories. The company built and opened its first factory in South East Asia in 2008, approximately 50 km from Hanoi in the Northern part of Vietnam, and its production was SA8000 certified as a CSR certificate.

Case B had a linear organization structure with five departments, such as human resource management, sales and exports, IT and logistics, financial, products, and specialized project departments. Several documents related to human resource management provided by the company included labor agreement, SA8000 certificate (CSR certification), occupational safety info, nonattendance list form, employment contract and separation form, and fingerprint record lists.

b. Summary of daily recording

The researcher entered the production building that demonstrated a clean and tidy environment. Yet, there should be more windows for natural light and air to come inside the building. All safety signs and fire hoses were placed in some areas. More than 80 percent in the production area are noticeably women workers who work with the sewing machine. Each of them is wearing a hat to cover hair and wearing a uniform. The production department included sewing, quality control, and logistics divisions, which have their own working area. The canteen area is immaculate, and the lights are located in another building on the back of the primary office.

c. Participant interview

The interview participants from the management side are composed of the human resource and IT and logistic managers. Both managers finished a degree overseas and had been employed for five to seven years. Five female employees selected by a human resource manager and researcher were from different departments. They were interviewed after an hour's lunch break. It took approximately 40 minutes to interview a group of female employees and 15 to 20 minutes to interview two managers.

d. Human resource management policies and activities

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The findings regarding policies and activities of the human resource management have been categorized into recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration, reward and performance appraisals, retention and union and labor relations.

- **Recruitment and selection**

Case A employs more than 700 Laotian workers on all levels. The central company policy is to implement CSR activity with the focus on hiring local workers, equipping them with a new skill, and ensuring they receive decent wages and better livelihood. This achievement started in the recruitment process. The hiring manager was promoted by an overseas general manager. Job vacancies were advertised to job magazines, vocational schools, universities, and newspapers. VITA Park itself also has its own magazines to help companies advertise all vacancies going on within the zones for free of charge. Managers and supervisors were selected through interviews only.

On the other hand, the recruitment and selection process is more complicated for non-management levels. The recruitment activity, including job advertising through radio and newspapers, was conducted by the human resource management department. After that, the production manager conducted an interview and practical test in the selection process. The interview production manager described the recruitment process:

“After the report, the vacancies number to a human resource manager, the jobs were advertised. Supervisors and I interviewed potential employees in each division and conducted simple, practical testing. After the candidate was selected by us, their detail will be sent back to the human resource department to ensure the employees' clean history.”

Work experience and the willingness to learn were the primary selection criteria for operational level workers. Most employees had graduated from a vocational school. Only a few of them did not have degrees but only graduated from senior high schools or lower than that. Other criteria include health and disease, drug, and criminal records. These criteria will be checked by the human resource department after a potential employee was selected. Having a health certificate is required to work in factories according to the national labor law and the company's recruitment policy. Also, maintaining transparent in the recruitment and selection process is the company's policy to ensure the right candidate and keep their management at an international standard. As human resource manager said”

‘Even though our recruitment and selection process is quite complex, it helps us ensure that we have selected the right person to the job, and this helps us enhance productivity and retention.’

Employees reported that they get the job quite easy since they used to work in other manufacturing firms outside the zone before. When the company needs people, they sometimes ask to give vacancies form to friends or relatives. Four out of five employees said that what they learned from vocational school help them to learn faster. One of the employees' participants stated that:

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“My major in vocational school is cutting and designing clothes. I am familiar with cutting and using sawing machine and this helped me learn faster during on the job training.”

However, some of them complain that the jobs they applied are over repeated. Supervisor wants to keep them longer if they are right.

- **Training and development**

Human resource development is one of the companies' human resource management policies. The company's strategy is to promote the labor productivity of local workers by train and educate them not only skill but the company culture, enhance employee's loyalty, discipline, and value of their tasks. Based on national labor law, training was conducted to all level employees, and knowledge and skills were transferred from foreign directors to local managers.

For the first three months since joining the workplace, on-the-job training for new hires was carried out in groups. The trainers were manufacturing supervisors. New joiners received 80% of the regular wage under on-the-job training. Only for the purposes of the contract extension was the evaluation made after training. Non-management staff received group training leads by team leaders. The staff claimed that on-the-job training remained too long, and supervisors are over control.

Managers said that they received in house training from their supervisors who travel from abroad. Potential supervisors were sent to local vocational schools for their certificate and some of them collected in house training from foreign technical teams who travel from Vietnam or Europe.

- **Remuneration, reward, and appraisals**

Compensation was the obligation of the human resource department. The salary paid is above the provincial minimum, the lowest pay permitted by law standard, which is dependent on living expenses in the capital. It is recomputed every year. A residency recompense is given to staff who have worked for more than three years and is raised at regular intervals. Also, the team who had low nonappearance scores gets month to month premiums and remittance once every year. The nonattendance is recorded in a unique mark machine that each representative must take the unique finger impression each morning. Workers griped that there was no contrast between the pay rates of talented and underqualified representatives.

Aside from remittances, the organization gives maternity leave depending on the national labor law. Customary execution examinations were done by checking the profitability score of workers appraised by the head of divisions. Criticism was given distinctly for missed targets, mistakes, or slacking errands. Professional success was restricted to the chance of turning into a

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group head. Career advancement was limited to the opportunity of becoming a team leader. The staff interview characterized the advancement scheme:

“I just got promoted after working here for three years and my friends also. Although it’s not easy to get promoted since I have dedicated a lot to the work and got my new degree from a vocational school, it looks like the company provides the opportunity for all.”

Group pioneers, directors, and supervisors used a particular scoring framework to complete execution examinations. Character (discipline, duty, helpfulness, and activity) and individual aptitudes (quality and amount) were incorporated into the score. The HR administrator keeps evaluation reports to lead expectation to absorb information of representatives in every office. The IT and strategic administrator portrayed the reason for executing examinations as pursued:

“We conduct performance appraisals to determine the achievement allowance or as a promotion criterion.”

The results did not appear to be shared with the staff and this became the cause of gripes. The team even believed that the probability of promotion was very low because the system and the criteria were vague.

- **Retention**

The company focuses on building better facilities to support everyday working routines of employees at each level and provide decent wages and essentials such as free lunch at the canteen, free transportation, free medical health check in clinic, and so on. Furthermore, there are financial incentives to support the retention of employees, such as bonuses and allowances. In addition, all supervisors were required to keep in touch with employees, including listening to their problems and feedback.

- **Union and labor relation**

The labour union is allowed at all levels of employees in Case B, which included national labor unions and women and youth unions. There are small fees to join the union in each year. The unions support employees to claim for their labor rights and guard them against irregular treatment. Also, those unions are working with the vocational school to conduct workshops, provide capacity-building activities where employees are free to join. Labor unions in the capital are more active than in provinces.

e. The dominant person response to HR practice

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The human resource was in control of HR activities. Some activities were undertaken communally with other departments; for example, recruitment and selection, training and development, and performance appraisals were administered collectively with the Production Manager and the supervisors. Other obligations not included in the job description of the Personnel and General Affairs Manager were executing public relations duties and addressing any issues to the local government related to workforce management. Case B has a hierarchy. This helped staff acknowledge structured control in the organization, executive power, and accountability. Also, there are more opportunities for promotion of employees who perform well (Colette and Meehan, 2018).

f. Analysis of findings

Case B appeared to be carrying out comprehensive administrative work and keeping records of all employees. Staffing was formal since the company is trying to keep its management standard and unique cultural. The recruitment and selection strategy involves the HR and production manager. Morissey and Nankervis' (2002) principle states that whatever selection method is decided, it should endeavor to ensure that investment in recruitment activities will attract skilled and motivate new employees to contribute to the organization's objectives. Additionally, Case B accepts staff founded on their education and working experience rather than connections. Education might not be necessary much for employees at the operations, but it helps them to learn faster on the job training.

On the job training was carried out to all new joiners in two months. Furthermore, in-house training was given to supervisors and team leaders. New managers or potential technician supervisors were trained by foreign supervisors who travel from overseas to provide a short training. Case B never sent their staff for training abroad. Training evaluation was not yet provided, but the human resource manager keeps records on the learning curve from the performance appraisal score of each employee. The company is following government labor policy and CSR. Although many foreign companies within and outside the zone offer a decent free lunch for employees, some CSR activities such as free clinics for employees have not to be seen in the country.

The remuneration system appeared to comply with the national labor policy. Yet, although a decent wage was offered above minimum wage, living expenses are very high in the capital. Also, some employees complained that salary is not different from their team leaders and their subordinates. This might base on experiences, productivity, and discipline that make outstanding employees. Case B handled the remuneration system to regulate employees' bonuses and allowances. Having a hierarchy system comprises various persons at the management level to help the company keep records and get in touch with employees. While performance allowances were based on the efficiency of an employee, the amounts paid were low compared to the living expenses in the capital.

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Case B performance appraisals were administered using a form with items to be scored. The intention and the evaluation results, however, have not been conveyed to the employees. Yet, employees did not benefit from the purpose of performance appraisals as the system was based on education and work experience. Employees claimed that they would have to get promoted if they did not go to vocational schools. Yet, they felt that an opportunity is available to people who are willing to try.

Apart from allowances, there are no other fiscal incentives to support the retention of employees. Some employees claimed that their task is overly repeated. Some employees have been working in the same divisions for more than three years. A company should have relocated employees to reduce boredom, enhance human resource, and retention. Case B permitted all staff to sign up for labor and women union, which they must pay small fees for the village unit every six months. It looks like the employees play an active role in joining the unions' activities. Table 12 finalizes employers and employees' interviews on human resource management practices of case B.

Human resource management policy and practice

1. Recruitment and selection

The employers

- Following national labor regulation by giving priority to Laotian worker at management and operational level
- Focusing on CSR policy
- Using formal recruitment
- Using local advertisement (Zone's magazine, a local newspaper, radio, and word of mouth)
- For the management level, the selection was based on education and working experiences
- For non-manager, the choice was based on a simple, practical test
- Production manager got involved with the selection process

The employees

- Manager and supervisor received vacancies information from public advertisement such as newspaper and local magazine and undergoing the interview
- Non-managers received vacancies information through friends/family and local training center and undergoing a simple, practical test

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2. Training and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-the-job training in the workplace lasted two months - 80 percent of the standard wage provided during the training period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Undergoing on the job training in groups led by team leaders - In house training conducted for management employees - No overseas training - No training evaluation provided
3. Remuneration, reward, and appraisals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Performing above minimum wage - Tenure allowance provided after 3 years and increased every two years - Employees shall receive bonus and compensation based on their years of working - Providing pregnancy benefits for female workers based on national labor regulation. - Performance appraisals were conducted through rating employees 'productivity held by a team leader - Using electronic fingerprint to record in and out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaints on the same salary for skilled and unskilled staff - Claims on small allowance comparing with living cost - The appraisals results were not provided - The promotion policy based on education and working experience
4. Retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing better necessary facilities such as free lunch, transportation, and free clinic service - Providing bonus, allowances, and opportunity for all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaining about overly repeated tasks
5. Union and labor relation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company allow all employees to enroll in national labor and women union 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They were actively involved in union activities

Table 11: Interviews with employers and employees on HRM policy and practices of case B.

5.2.1.3 Case C

a. Company Profile

Case C is a Japanese electronic material component and materials found in 1871 and has about 120 factories in Asia. Case C inaugurated a new manufacturing subsidiary in Laos SEZ at the beginning of 2015 and exports across the Asian and Europe regions. Currently, the company employed more than 400 employees at the management and non-management level. Under the medium-term management strategy for the 2016 premium materials and through the improved production system with the new production based in Laos, the electronic equipment and a component firm is expanding other factories in the same SEZ at the end of 2017 and will be sold it to the domestic market.

The organizational framework of Case C is patterned after the headquarter's regulatory framework. The Director is at the top while the Production Manager oversees production practices and handles some activities of human resource management such as recruitment and selection, training, and supervision. Laotian staff covered more than 95 percent of total employees, and many are employed in the manufacturing sector. The firm followed a single shift pattern operating between 0800 to 1700.

b. Summary of everyday activities

The production area was observed to be clean. Locker rooms were provided to store the staff's properties, and a cafeteria was installed. A machine that captures the staff's fingerprints for attendance was situated in the security room. Attached to walls, symbols like "No Smoking" abound inside and outside the building. The production building located in the back of the office building had enough light and ventilation. Apart from the company's employees, outsiders were not permitted to the production room.

Before getting inside the building, all participants, including the researcher, were asked to wear a cap. The assorted colors of the cap demonstrated different management levels and tasks of employees in the company (for instance, the red cap for the director, green cap for supervisors and blue cap for operational employees). The documents applicable for analysis were very minimal due to the confidentiality of most employee records. This company only performed simple management, including the general director, the finance department, and the production departments that included logistics, quality control, maintenance, and product processing division.

c. Participants of the interview

The Production Manager and three supervisors were the respondents from the management while five respondents came from different areas of the department of production.

d. Human resource management polies and activities

Interview answers on human resource management activities by employers and employees are mentioned below:

- **Recruitment and selection**

The recruitment and selection methods were carried out both officially and unofficially. The Manager of Production was in charge of recruiting operation-level staff only. Recruitment of management-level positions including the finance manager, production manager and head of each division was conducted by the Director. Interview with the Manager of Production recounted his experience with recruitment:

“I recruit new employees if there is a vacancy or an expansion plan (a new machine addition). I advertise the vacancy through newspapers and ask the employees to bring applications from family or friends.”

The main criteria for recruitment were skills and experience. Many staff finished senior high and only a few managed to finish a vocation on electrical engineering. Some staff asserted that the occupations they were applying for were comfortable and did not correspond to their education. The practice of placement implicated the selection, interview, and sample testing of documents. Before commencing their work, successful applicants signed contracts.

Apart from national labor and zone policy, HRM policy of the company is to hire Laotian workers and trains the Laotian manager to enhance the human capital of the company. The company maintained their culture by hiring supervisors and managers who graduated from Japan or used to work for the Japanese company. The company Japanese director stated that:

“Our human resource management policy is to hire the Laotian manager to supervise Laotian workers. Nevertheless, this does not mean we do not protect our organizational cultural and Japanese management standards. We normally select managers and supervisors based on the education of which most of them graduated from Japan. Or someone who used to work for a Japanese company before. It’s important that those supervisors understand and get used to our working culture.”

- **Training and development**

Based on the training schedule, it seems like the company’s human resource development policy focuses on building the capacity of a few local managers than non-management employees. This might be due to the company having a small management team and operational employees who do not require much skill to work besides being familiar with the machinery and being

disciplined. Within the first three months at work, new joiners undergo on-the-job training in groups. The trainers were a head of the division and two senior supervisors (The selection of trainers was based on types of machinery used). While on training, new joiners received 90% of the usual salary. The certificate of training was produced in accordance with the contract. There is in-house training for supervisors from different sections. Potential supervisors who do not have a degree were sent to a vocational school. Yet this case is rarely based on employees.

- **Remuneration, reward, and appraisals**

Remuneration was the responsibility of the production department manager. The salary paid above the minimum salary rule was calculated annually. Two categories of salary include hourly and contractual wage. Depending on the number of days the workers coming to work, the hourly wages were computed. Casual employees or contractual employees got paid based on their contracts. Most employees who received hourly wages were working in the quality control divisions. A talk with the manager detailed how salaries for contractual workers varied:

“Because we value the quality of works more than quantity, we cannot rely on our quality control on one person every day. There were at least two quality controllers within a week. Various shifts were provided by the production manager.”

“Tenure allowance” was given to workers who rendered service of at least one year and rose every two years. Additionally, the workers at management level were compensated with monthly bonuses and allowance once a year. Overtime practice is offered to management employees and paid in full. Case C also listed all workers for social security regime to take pension plans and other essential materials and moral needs of employees and their families.

Complaints from workers regarding a massive discrepancy between the skill of employees at management and non-management level who received different benefits were observed. Also, the prescribed performance appraisals were carried out unofficially by verifying the workers’ efficiency. Feedback was given only for missed targets, errors, or lagging tasks. Career advancement was restricted to the probability of becoming a team leader. An interview with the staff depicted the method of promotion:

“I never get a promotion; it looks like the company has chosen its own candidate.”

An absence form is available to all employees for sick leaves, maternity leave, and annual leave, not exceeding 45 days (accept maternity leave based on national labor law).

- **Retention**

Apart from allowance increase every two years of working, there are no other fiscal incentives to remain retention. Employees said that the compensation is small, but they feel

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committed to the company and work. The interview with operational employees described their feelings towards the company that:

'My supervisor is being supportive and can be relied on when I have trouble with work.'

'Although salary and allowance are not much different from where I used to work, I feel that my supervisors and managers do care about their employees with their basic needs.'

- **Union and labor relation**

Based on the national labor policy, the fund of the labor unit shall not be deducted from employees' salaries or wages but shall be paid by the labor unit. One of the female supervisors is a worker representative who belongs to the labor unit. The worker representative has the responsibility of encouraging workers to have labor discipline, promote solidarity, and train them to successfully perform work based on a given task and protect them from unfair treatments of employees. She explained her actual responsibility that:

'I have been working in this company since 2015 and have not heard any serious issues up to date. I am trying to encourage women to be more independent and being positive. Our manager is quite strict and is results-oriented during working hours. Besides this, she is alright. We also have activities outside working hours such as aerobic and cooking together for dinner in the dormitory.'

e. The dominant person response to HR practice

The Manager of Production was in charge of the activities of the human resource management and resolved the issues of the workers in the factory, except for remuneration and rewards, which were the duty of the Director. Together with the supervisors, training, supervision, and unofficial performance appraisals were carried out.

f. Analysis of findings

In Case C, the manager of the production monitored the operations of manufacturing and some HRM processes. Official and unofficial recruitment and selection were performed. Job openings were announced by the press and by word-of-mouth. Regarding staffing, managers relied on the new requirements of the organization (Schaper & Volery, 2004). On-the-job training was only delivered to new workers. This training was vital for new workers with no experience in working with machinery. In a house, coaching is for managers and supervisors to use new equipment or machinery.

New workers have seldom been appropriately trained with the required learning and the ability to work their job roles (Schaper & Volery, 2004) correctly. The evaluation after the training was not recorded formally. Only a training certificate will be provided for a contract agreement.

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This means that selection was informal and based on the manager’s option, and there might be bias for their friends and family. The remuneration policy denoted to above the minimum salary set by the country. Complaints regarding the failure of the system to differentiate the skill of management and non-management level receive a very different bonus, and allowances existed.

Performance appraisals were carried out unofficially. Case C appeared to have implemented on-the-job evaluation processes, which meant that observing the worker directly in their day-to-day tasks (Schaper & Volery, 2004). Feedback was only by reaching targets. Career advancement was limited to the supervisory role, with very little likelihood to happen. The workers signed up for two unions, which are national labor and women union. Many never got involved with violence or strike. Employees appeared to be satisfied with their job and feeling commitment due to the working culture. HRM policy and practice of Case C summarized in Table 13:

Human resource management policy and practice	The employers	The employees
1. Recruitment and selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Following national labor regulation by giving priority to Laotian worker at management and operational level - Did not have much training going on for management-level employees - Using official and unofficial recruitment - Use of local job ads and word-of-mouth - For the management level, the choice was based on education and working experiences related to Japanese - For non-manager, the selection was based on the practical test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Submitting an application in person or through staff - Some positions they applied to were light and did not correspond to their education
2. Training and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-the-job training in the workplace for three months - 90 percent of the regular wage provided during the training period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very few employees were sent to vocational school

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3. Remuneration, reward, and appraisals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The training certificate is to contract agreement propose - Performing above minimum wage - Implemented dual wage system such as hourly wage and casual wage - Bonuses were providing to management employees only - Conducting informal assessments for productivity development only 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaining about the same skill of management and non-management employees, who received different bonuses and allowances - Career advancement was restricted to supervisory posts.
4. Retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing necessary facilities and bonuses for managers and supervisors - Enhance cultural adaptation by hiring local manager and supervisor who understands Japanese working cultural - Create a relaxing working environment . 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complaining about overly repeated tasks - Feeling committed to work and the company
5. Union and labor relation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company allows all employees to enroll in national labor and women union - Having a female labor representative act as a focal point between employees and employers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There were activities to enhance the relationship among workers outside working hour.

Table 12: Employers' and employees' interview HRM policy and practice of Case C

5.2.2 Cross-Case Analysis

In an earlier sub-chapter, the within-case analysis described the way each situation enforced the activities of HRM that matched the business well. The subsequent sub-chapter compares the activities of the three case study firms. The investigation will recognize the forms of activities of human resource management. The answers to the interviews utilized for comparing are generally sourced from the viewpoint of the managers and employers. Based on the research framework, knowing the rules and activities of human resource management of multinational

enterprises shall enhance understanding the way Laos SEZs, mainly the enterprises, contribute to human resource development in the country.

Furthermore, the results of each case are linked to associate the similarities and the differences in human resource management policies and activities of foreign-invested enterprises located in Laos SEZs. The analysis of human resource management is excluded cultural analysis since the selected companies are from dissimilar industries composed of different management cultural. This section focused on discussing how HRM rules and activities enhance human resource development, including recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, retention, and labor union and relation. The discussion address research questions:

Question 4: What are human resource policies and activities regarding recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration rewards and appraisals, retention, union labor, and regulation are implemented in foreign-invested enterprises in Laos SEZs?

5.2.2.1 Discussion of the findings

- **Recruitment and selection process**

Generally, cases A, B, and C have HRM policies and practices that encourage local employment. The policy is one of their international strategies focusing on reduced production cost by lowering labor costs in which Laos has the lowest labor cost compared to neighboring countries such as Thailand and Cambodia. When internal employees are insufficient in terms of quantity and skill, cases A, B, and C recruit outsiders. All cases conducted similar recruitment and selection processes in formal and informal ways. Job vacancies were publicly advertised through the newspaper, local vocational school, and magazine. Case B state stated that the zone in which they located helps with the advertisement for free. Also, Case B and C seems to have enough labor source since it was in the capital.

Although the job was advertised publicity, operational employees in all cases received the vacancy information through word of mouth and submitted their application by themselves or employees. Informal recruitment within an international organization is not new and has been widely practiced in many low-income countries. For instance, (Kundu and Gahlawat, 2015) found high rate correspondents of employee referrals within multinational enterprises in India. Tardoa and Pedersen (2011) found informal recruitment and selection practices for low-skilled employees in European companies located within developing countries. In addition, they implied that low-skilled job seekers facing difficulties in the labor market, and direct application seems to be a channel by which low-skilled job seekers at a disadvantage in the labor market.

All managers in each case were selected based on degrees and working experiences in the related field. Local managers, in all cases, have 10 to 15 years of working experience

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in the relevant field. Their selection process was conducted through face-to-face interviews mostly by the foreign general manager or project manager. Operational employees have gone through a practical test during the process. Case B, which is a textile company, recruited operational employees based on their degree in clothes sewing and designing from the local vocational school. The recruitment practices of Case A and C focused on the ability of willing to learn and discipline.

- **Training**

Only Case A sent new managers for overseas training. For supervisors or subordinates within the company's management team were sent to local vocational training. Other Cases, all management employees received in-house training from foreign supervisors who were traveling from neighboring countries where another factory of their companies was located in SEZ management theory, training local managers to enhance human capital. Also, it helps the SEZ to facilitate knowledge and skill spillover to the rest of the economy when those managers are bringing their international management policies and practice to local firms (Zeng, 2015; Moran, 2012, Farole and Akinci, 2011).

Case C indicated that hiring local managers and equipping them with international management knowledge and experiences helped the company manage human resources more effectively by facilitating cultural adaptation. Several studies derived from Chinese experiences support the finding. Collins et al. (2018) found that during the open-door policy in China, international HRM policies and practices embedded Chinese characteristics have been implemented successfully within foreign-invested enterprises in Chinese SEZs. This had played a significant part of economic reform in the country.

For operational employees, training lasted for two to three months for all Cases. Based on the national labor law, training should not be more than three months since these associated with lower wages during the training. Case B and C provided lower wages during the training period for operational employees. Aggarwal (2011) claimed that training for non-management employees does not contribute much to human resource development in the country since the training is conducted within an abbreviated period. However, most employees never have career experience such as the Laotians, and training seems to help them to be more disciplined, punctual, and familiar with industry working environment.

- **Remuneration, rewards, and appraisals**

All cases are providing wage or salary above the minimum wage. Firm A stated that their minimum wage for employees at the management level is higher than those working in a similar company outside the zone. There is no evidence to support the statement. The answers of the workers regarding remuneration methods were alike. All acknowledged that the domestic salary requirement was met. Discontent was observed, though. Sources of discontent constituted low tenure allowance received, the applicability

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of previous year's in the current year, and fixing of the same basic salary to old and new management and non-management workers.

All cases provided allowance, bonus, overtime, and maternity leave based on national labor regulation. Compensation by Case A and B were provided based on their discipline in working hours and years of working. Case C provided a bonus for management employees each year. Case C followed two methods, one method for contractual workers and the other method for workers reporting in various shifts given by the production manager. A variable salary method was observed for workers working on shifts as quality controllers. Ding et al. (2011) also found that businesses invested by foreigners have shifted lifetime employment to contractual where permanent salaries are grounded on each worker and business fulfillment. The research also implied limited differences between management and operational employees.

Performance appraisal methods can be utilized administratively, which relate to workers' circumstances like career advancement, resignation, and rewards (Gomez-Mejia et al., 2004). All cases conducted formal performance appraisals. Case C did formal evaluations in an informal way. The objective of performance appraisals in Cases A and B was to calculate allowances for the succeeding year or to evaluate workers for career advancement. Case B, a European company, used specific performance appraisal methods through a form with scoring.

Even though the performance appraisals were conducted formally for operational employees, results were not provided or provided only negative effects, especially of which was evident in Case C. This formed rumors that the organization might conduct promotions unfairly. Moreover, only operational employees in Case A felt that there was some career pathway for them. Operational employees in Case B and C felt that the probability of being promoted as a team leader was very low. In addition, No performance appraisals for the manager in all cases. Only Case A occasionally conducted performance appraisals to the manager informal way by the international project manager.

- **Retention**

Allowance appeared to be the only fiscal incentives that most cases used to enhance employees' retention. Managers frequently provided only basic needs such as free lunch, transportation, and accommodation for employees. Operational employees in Case B and C complained about overly repeated tasks while employees in Case A felt appreciative of their current career providing them more permanent income. This might be due to the employees not working in the capital zone, where more opportunities for low or semi-skilled workers were provided. Case C provided an interesting point regarding company culture. Although the employees complained about the same job every day, group activities after working hours such as exercise, cooking and so on made them feel more attached to the team and the company.

- **Union labor and relation**

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All cases permitted employees to join unions. Based on the national labor law, all labor units shall join the labor union automatically after the business license was provided. There are small fees for each group every year and will be paid by the company. Comparing with the income exemption provided by each SEZ, those fees are nothing. Apart from the labor union, there are youth and women union that employees can join. There are no fees to join the group. Based on the researcher's survey, those women and youth union received money from the charity of significant business units in each year during the celebration of the event.

Also, the Ministry of labor and social welfare paid some amount of money for those unions to run their activities. Those unions are quite crucial in a socialist country such as Laos. It appeared that labor unions such as Case B and C are more active than on Case A located outside the capital. A supervisor from Case C was a committee member of a women union and acted as a middle person between employees and employers. This might be the reason that Case C seems to have a stronger organization, a more diverse culture and working environment.

5.2.2.2 The major person response to HRM practice

The managers of the human resources of Cases A and B contributed so much in leading HRM regulations and activities. In Case B, the manager of the production was included in certain activities like selection. The production manager of Case C seemed to succeed in most activities of HRM. The organizational structure of Case C, a Japanese company, appears to be simpler than in most cases. Yet, it seems like Case C is more successful than other cases in terms of cultural adaptation.

5.2.3 Cultural analysis

National culture is a critical concern among HR managers when performing abroad. This section analyzes the way national cultural impact on HRM of FIEs. The in-depth interview helps researcher answer research questions 6th:

6. How does national cultural influence HRM of FIEs in Laos SEZs?

- **Challenges that HR managers of three companies have been faced when performing their task in Laos branch are:**
 - **Labour shortage:** due to Laotian's value in working within the government section rather than private sector, labour shortage occurred in the zone. Also, some Laotian people have farmlands and do not have debt or mortgages to pay. Case A manager stated that "apparently, when there is labour shortage, every company has a recruitment problem since we need lots of people for production department, so recruitment is our challenge" (Case B). "Some districts have very less Laotians in

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working age since most of them usually immigrant to work in Thailand. Meanwhile, others do not fit to our criteria”

- **High retention rate:** since the needs of working in manufacture is very less, it's very easy for Laotian workers to decide quitting job. Plus, they cannot adapt themselves to industrial working routine. “some of them left their home and enter the jobs for the first time, it seems like they don't like the environment and leave after they have started working only a couple of days” (Case 2). “Although our welfare and salary are very good compared to other companies inside and outside the zone, they just leave and stay home.” “Our retention rate is equal to hiring rate, especially during harvest season retention rate can reach up to 50% of workers who just recruited couple months ago” (Case 3).
 - **Ignore overtime payment:** Laotian workers prefer to work for only 8 hours a day and do not wish to do any overtime work, although their managers ask for it. “Sometimes we have to speed up production but very less or none of them agree to do overtime” (Case B). “They do not wish to do overtime even we agree to pay them extra.” (Case A).
 - **Poor coordination between HR manager and government officer:** due to foreign HR managers do not have experience on coordinating with government staff and cloud labour policies of the zones, challenges of labour policies implementation occurred. “Sometimes when we approach government staff to ask about labour policies, they do not give us clear answers. Then we were asked to check up with other department to ensure the answer.” (Case B).
- **HR managers participated in the interviews recommended that:**
 - Foreign HR manager need to adapt to new working cultural by concerning about the actual current labour status.

“We need to change everything including our thoughts, we need to step back not only one step but miles, if we want management to be like what we used to do, we would not survive.” (Case A). “We need to adapt everything to their culture, for instance, employees always ask if they can leave work early or for couple of days, we have to allow them to do so otherwise no one will work for us” (Case B).
 - Networking and social connections are very critical to coordinate with private and government officers.

“We have good friendship with our partners” (Case B). “Laotian people like socializing, we created network from colleagues or friends in ceremonies, weddings, and others special occasions. If we encounter problems, we can call for their help and recommendations” (Case C).

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- Language communication is critical. HR managers in Laos need to learn Lao language to communicate with employees and counterparts. They can use informal communication as well during work such as text and call instead of email.

“We need to speak Lao language and understand their culture as much as we can. If we can speak their language, it means that we can connect with them and then they start to talk” (Case B). “We have to know Laotian culture, what we should not say or do” (Case A). “Lao language is easy to learn compared to Cambodian or Burmese. Although it’s very easy to communicate we need to be detail-oriented in what we going to say” (Case C).

- Foreign HR manager needs to understand Laotian culture by knowing individual characteristics. In Laos, culture impacts highly to the way of working. Laotian employees need to feel comfortable at work, do not like to speak loudly or ask when they don’t understand problem. HR manager should communicate with them softly.

“Sometimes when we loudly criticize Laotian employees when they make a mistake, they will conceive us as being aggressive, and that will make them more shy if we do it in front of others. Therefore, it’s better to criticize individually” (Case C). “Just say that this area is not clean enough can make her cry. We need to change our words to make them feel better” (Case A).

“We adapted to the local culture, we need to know their values and characteristics, focus on communication, and help them to adapt with industrial working routine” (Case B).

- HR officers should be Laotian people since they understand Laotian values, cultural and characteristic of locals rather than the foreigner. Foreign HR manager should help their local staff design a system, govern, and monitor.

“Our Laotian officers understand the characteristics of locals and implement all HRM tasks, the foreign HR manager providing system, HR training and monitoring” (Case B). “Operational employees prefer to work with Laotians since they can understand each other, it’s better to hire locals and train them about the system so they can do the job for us” (Case C).

5.2.4 Summary of Qualitative Data Analysis of HRM activities and cultural

- To answer question 3, Chapter 6 attempted to analyzed Micro-level data through a qualitative approach. Findings were summarized in below table 14.

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	Case A	Case B	Case C
Recruitment and selection			
1. Focus on hiring Laotian	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. Formal and informal recruitment	Formal	Formal	Formal and informal
3. Vacancy advertisement	Public	Public	Public and word of mouth for operational employees
4. Selection criteria: education and working experience)	All but not necessary for operational level	All	Skill and experience
5. Selection technique	Interview for a manager, sample test for operational employees	Interview for the manager, sample test for operational employees	Interview for the manager, sample test for operational employees
6. Person in charge	HR manager	HR manager	Production manager
Training and development			
1. On the job training	Two months	Two months	Three months
2. Other training	Overseas training, vocational training	In house training	In house training
3. Trainer	Foreign supervisor	Foreign supervisor for management level and internal supervisor for operational level	The supervisor or team leader
4. Training evaluation	No	No	No
Remuneration, reward and performance appraisal			
1. Following national minimum wage	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. Providing allowance, bonus and other benefits base on	Yes	Yes	Yes

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national labor
regulation

3. The person in charge of the remuneration system	HR manager	HR manager	Production manager
4. Formal performance appraisals	Yes	Yes	For operational employees: Yes For manager: No
5. Performance appraisals as a standard for an increase in wage and allowance	Yes	Yes	No
6. Performance appraisals as a base of career advancement	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
7. A person in charge of performance appraisal	Manager and supervisor	Manager and supervisor	Team leader and supervisor

Retention

1. Allowance as a fiscal incentive	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. Other fiscal incentives	No	No	No
3. Providing enough basic needs	Yes	Yes	Yes
4. Other non-fiscal incentives (activity outside working hours)	No	No	Yes

Union and labor relations

1. Union existence	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. Automatic membership	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Person pay for joining fees	Company	Company	Company

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4. The benefit of the union to workers	Some	Yes	Yes
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The semi-structured interview gave a primer assessment of the human asset management approaches and practices of overseas investors. Unmistakably, the number of cases was insufficient even to consider verifying the actual state of foreign ventures, yet further assessment with more significant data is necessary. The information from the above case study was utilized to do a survey for the following step of this study. The consequences of the survey are given in the quantitative examination in the following paragraphs.

- To answer the 6th research question, impacts of national cultural on HRM were explored through semi-structured interview. Result of the interview can be concluded that:
 - To implement HRM activities overseas, HR manager should concern about national culture and norms.
 - Foreign HR manager should be able to understand and speak Laos as well as being able to communicate well with a local subordinate. Speaking the same language and acting the same way help the foreign HR manager build trust among workers.
 - The manager needs to understand characteristic of local workers and accepts it
 - Good network is very critical to do business in Laos. Coordinating with government officers and local counterparts require good friendship so that it helps exchange information while doing business.
 - Implementing HRM activities are performed by the local HR officers. Yet, the HR manager is a foreigner who should help design strategies and policies and train them the new system.

The cross-cultural analyses are applied in Hofstede dimension in **Chapter 6**.

5.3 Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis in Chapter 6 presented a case analysis of HRM policies and the practice of three foreign-invested enterprises within Laos SEZs. It also partially answered the 4th question and supported the validity of the above qualitative data analysis at Micro-level:

Research question 4: What are the human resource policies and activities with regard to recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration rewards and appraisals, retention, union labor, and regulation enforced in foreign-invested enterprises in Laos SEZs?

This section also answers research question 4 through quantitative analysis. It also answers research question 5:

Research question 5: What is the correlation between HRM policies and practices in foreign-invested enterprises within Laos SEZs and human resource development?

This chapter analyzes and interprets all quantitative data from the responses of 75 Laotian employees and managers who are working within three selected Cases A, B, and C within Laos SEZs. The survey determines if the finding based on the recommendations in the case study are

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validated on a broader case of foreign-invested enterprises in Laos SEZs. Triangulation attained through combining qualitative and quantitative systems strengthen the legitimacy of the paper (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Furthermore, the paper uncovers the enforcement of rules and activities of HRM in overseas firms in two major Laos SEZs such as Savan-Seno SEZ and VITA Park. The scope of these activities was picked up through surveys. The questionnaire was formulated from the results of the case studies in Chapter Three. Six fields of HRM were reported in the case study as follows: recruitment and selection, training and development; remuneration and reward; performance appraisals; retention and union, and labor relations. A review of these six areas and the theory helped formulate the questionnaire. The six areas have been identified as factors of the businesses' rules and activities of human resource management.

The quantitative analysis also explored the correlation of the HRM rules and activities in oversea firms and the insights of human resource development. Six hypotheses were articulated with regard to the insights of the employers on human resource development.

H_1 = A positive correlation between the policy and enforcement of recruitment and selection methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

H_2 =A positive correlation between the policy and enforcement of training and development methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

H_3 =A positive correlation between the policy implementation of remuneration and rewards methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

H_4 =A positive correlation between the policy and implementation of performance appraisals methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

H_5 =A positive correlation between the policy and implementation of retention methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

H_6 =A positive correlation between the policy and implementation of union and labor relation methods and the insights of human resource development exists.

5.3.1 Descriptive Analysis

5.3.1.1 Demographics of Sample

Demographic features of the 75 samples categorize the participants in terms of gender, age, education, and work experience within selected Cases A, B, and C. These data are demonstrated in Appendix 3. Data were summarized in the following paragraphs.

The distribution of the participants in terms of gender signified that many employees in these companies were female (60 out of 75 respondents or 80%). Interestingly, 10 out of 14

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employees at management level are females (Table 15). The distribution of employees in terms of age signified that the age of the employees at management and non-management level ranged from 25 to 35 years (33 out of 75 respondents or 44%) trailed by the 18 to 25 age group (26 respondents or 34.7%).

There were only four employees in the over 45 age category of 5.3% of the sample. The most significant cluster of (31 out of 75 participants or 41.3%) of the employees finished high school, followed by the Diploma group (18 respondents or 24%). Only six employees (8%) completed a university degree or its equivalent. Yet, there are four employees who have a post-graduate degree, and one of them has a Ph.D. degree. The number of employees who gained one to five years of experience of working was 42 out of 75 participants (56%). This signifies that many respondents have little related knowledge and experience in their working field. Table 15 showed the gender and positions of employees in three case companies.

Gender * Position in the company Crosstabulation

		Position in the company			
		Management	Non-management	Total	
Gender	Male	Count	4	11	15
		Expected Count	2.8	12.2	15.0
		% within Gender	26.7%	73.3%	100.0%
	Female	Count	10	50	60
		Expected Count	11.2	48.8	60.0
		% within Gender	16.7%	83.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	14	61	75
		Expected Count	14.0	61.0	75.0
		% within Gender	18.7%	81.3%	100.0%

Table 13: Gender and position of three case companies

5.3.1.2 Descriptive Analysis of a sample

Descriptive analysis requires transforming actual data into an easily understandable and interpretable form (Zikmund, 2003). Descriptive statistics include clear descriptions of the samples and form part of quantitative analysis. Descriptive statistics are utilized to decide if enough variation in the 75 answers for each variable is present to prove specific relations and to help show if the inherent distributions of variables are typically distributed and whether the discrepancy of the comparable distributions justifies the use of parametric statistics in later evaluations (Matthews, 1990).

The descriptive analysis tests the variable's average score using a standard in measuring average. The approximately typical formula for measurement distribution is: $\mu \pm 1SD$, where μ is

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the population means, and SD is Standard Deviation (Mendenhall et al., 1990). The measurement of the distribution can be predicted from 0 to 1 SD (Welkowitz et al., 1982). This study will use $\mu \pm 1$ SD to describe the variable, t

Answers to all items measuring the variables treated Likert-type measurements with solutions spanning 1 to 5. The standard measurement for the Likert range of 1–5 in a normal distribution will be: 3 ± 1 SD, in accordance with the distribution measurement rule. 68% of the measure belongs to the range between 2 and 4 under a normal distribution. Average results within this range are deemed appropriate. The following paragraphs show the average results and standard deviation of the combined sample variables to verify that the mean scores of the combined sample variables were within the range.

a. Descriptive analysis of the rules and activities of HRM in multinational firms in Laos SEZs

The descriptive analyses of the rules and activities of HRM in multinational firms in selected two major SEZs were from responses set of 5 Linkert scale range between “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree.” The high score for items 5 or 4 indicated the effectiveness of HRM rules and activities of foreign firms and low scores 1 or 2 stated ineffectiveness. Table 16 showed the average mean score of the variables.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Recruitment and Selection	75	3.67	4.83	4.2867	.25492
Training and Development	75	3.33	4.83	4.1289	.32831
Remuneration and Rewards	75	3.71	4.86	4.4762	.28987
Appraisals	75	3.00	5.00	4.1844	.63528
Retention	75	2.83	5.00	4.1022	.81276
Union and Labor Relation	75	3.25	5.00	4.2267	.51853
Valid N (listwise)	75				

Table 14: Mean score and standard deviation of variables (HRM policy and practice)

Table 16 shows that all variables contained average results within the range ($\mu \pm 1$ SD) and were deemed appropriate. This indicated that the HRM practices of foreign-invested enterprises were uniform high. The highest mean score is remuneration and reward consider decent wage and other fiscal benefits such as allowances and bonuses. Recruitment and selection are subsequently

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high since all foreign-invested enterprises follow the national labor policy to hire local workers. Yet, formal recruitment did not attract low-skilled workers to the zone as much as it should be. Therefore, relying on vocational school or the third person with the advertisement is critical for those companies. In the meantime, retention appeared to be the lowest concern of those enterprises.

b. Descriptive analysis of HR development

The descriptive analyses of perception on the development of human resources were from responses set of 5 Linkert scale series between “Very Low” to “Very High.” The high score for items 5 or 4 indicated a high level of human resource development, and low scores 1 or 2 indicated a low level. Table 17 showed the average mean score of the variables.

		Income earning	Skill and Knowledge formulation	Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities	Working/Living condition	Gender equality	Quality of Life	Career Prosperity
N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.3733	4.2667	4.3333	3.7867	4.3600	4.4933	4.3600
Minimum		3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Maximum		5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

Table 15: Mean score and standard deviation of variables (Human Resource Development)

Human Resource Development	
Valid	75
Missing	0
Mean	4.2819
Minimum	4.00
Maximum	4.71

Table 16: Total Mean score and standard deviation of variables (Human Resource Development)

Table 18 shows that all variables contained average scores within the series ($\mu \pm 1$ SD) and were deemed appropriate. Employees had a high perception of their quality of life and income earning. In the meantime, the employees rated the lowest score on working/living conditions. The overall mean scores 4.28 indicated that human resource development based on employees’ perceptions is relatively high.

5.3.2 Correlation analysis

Bivariate correlation analysis is treated with examining the correlation between two variables (Manning & Munro, 2007). Bivariate correlation analysis was carried out through the insights of human resource development as the dependent variable and the six parts (recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, performance appraisals, retention, and union and labor relation) as the independent variable. A Pearson product-moment (r) correlation value was used in determining the strength of the correlation.

The correlation between recruitment and selection and the insights on human resource development was positive ($r=.262$, $p<.05$), as seen in Table 19 below. The correlation was substantial because of $p<.05$.

		Correlations	
		Human Resource Development	Recruitment and Selection
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.262*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.023
	N	75	75
Recruitment and Selection	Pearson Correlation	.262*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.023	
	N	75	75

* The relationship is substantial at 0.05 (two tails).

Table 17: Relationship between recruitment and selection and human resource development

Table 20 sees a positive relationship between training and development and human resource development ($r=.473$, $p<0.05$). The association was substantial because of $p<0.05$.

		Correlations	
		Human Resource Development	Training and Development
Pearson Correlation		1	.473**

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Human Resource	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Development	N	75	75
Training and	Pearson Correlation	.473**	1
Development	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	75	75

** The relationship is substantial at 0.01 (two tails).

Table 18: Relationship between training and development and human resource development

The bivariate relationship of remuneration and reward with the insights on human resource development in Table 21 expresses a positive integer ($r = .310$, $p < 0.05$). Because $p < 0.05$ the relationship was substantial.

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Remuneration and Rewards
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.310**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007
	N	75	75
Remuneration and Rewards	Pearson Correlation	.310**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 19: Relationship between remuneration and rewards and human resource development

As shown in Table 22, there was a positive correlation between performance appraisals and perception of human resource development ($r = 0.344$, $p < 0.05$). This correlation was significant since $p < 0.05$.

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Appraisals
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.344**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	75	75
Appraisals	Pearson Correlation	.344**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	

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N	75	75
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 20: Relationship between performance appraisals and human resource development

The bivariate correlation of retention with the perception of human resource development in Table 23 shows a positive value ($r=.471$, $p<0.05$). Since $p<0.05$ the correlation was significant.

		Correlations	
		Human Resource Development	Retention
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.471**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	75	75
Retention	Pearson Correlation	.471**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 21: Relationship between retention and human resource development

The bivariate correlation of union and labor relations with the perception of company performance in Table 24 shows a positive value ($r=.228$, $p<0.05$). Since $p<0.05$ the correlation was significant.

		Correlations	
		Human Resource Development	Union and Labor Relation
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.228*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.049
	N	75	75
Union and Labor Relation	Pearson Correlation	.228*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049	
	N	75	75

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 22: Relationship between union and labor relation and human resource development

5.3.3 Report Hypotheses

The gaps of literature review chapter 2 developed six main hypotheses tested in Micro-level analysis. Outcomes of the hypothesis examined are represented in this section. This area displays the consequences of the examination of the speculations and reaches determinations about the connections between human asset arrangements and practices and views of workers towards human asset improvement. Every one of the speculations plots in Chapter 3 can be tried utilizing the above bivariate relationships. In particular, the six theories were tried against the Pearson's item minute connection coefficient for the connection between every factor and view of organization execution, as portrayed in Tables 19 to 24 in the relationship segment above.

H₁= There is a positive relationship between the policy and implementation of recruitment and selection processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 19, the bivariate relationship amongst enlistment and determination procedures and view of human asset improvement had a measurably noteworthy positive estimation of 0.262 importance enrollment and choice was emphatically corresponded to human asset advancement. This implies changes in enlistment and determination could be required to change the organization's exhibition. In this way, Hypothesis 1 was acknowledged.

H₂=There is a positive relationship between the policy and implementation of training and development processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 20 the bivariate connection amongst preparation and improvement and view of human asset advancement had a noteworthy positive estimation of 0.473. This demonstrates the usage of preparing and improving procedures upheld human asset advancement. It creates the impression that expanded preparation and promotion could be required to build the human asset improvement. In this way, Hypothesis 2 was acknowledged.

H₃=There is a positive relationship between the policy implementation of remuneration and reward processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 21, the bivariate connection amongst compensation and prizes; and view of human asset advancement had a noteworthy positive estimation of 0.310. It gives the idea that improvement to the compensation and rewards framework will improve the view of human asset advancement. Subsequently, Hypothesis 3 was acknowledged.

H₄=There is a positive relationship between the policy and implementation of performance appraisals processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 22 the bivariate connection is tween's presentation examinations and impression of human asset advancement had a positive estimation of 0.344. It very well may be inferred that there is sufficient proof to show a positive connection between execution examinations and human asset advancement. In this manner, Hypothesis 4 was acknowledged.

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H₅=There is a positive relationship between the policy and implementation of retention processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 23 the bivariate relationship between staff maintenance and view of human asset advancement had a positive estimation of 0.471. It tends to be reasoned that there is sufficient proof to exhibit a positive connection between maintenances of staff and human asset improvement. Along these lines, Hypothesis 5 was acknowledged.

H₆=There is a positive relationship between the policy and implementation of union and labor relation processes and perceptions of human resource development.

As shown on Table 24 the bivariate connection amongst association and work connection and impression of organization execution had a positive estimation of 0.228. It very well may be inferred that there is sufficient proof to exhibit a positive relationship between association and work and human asset advancement. Subsequently, Hypothesis 6 was acknowledged.

5.3.4 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The method of reasoning for leading numerous straight relapse investigations is to make a model to depict the commitment to... the six factors (Selection, preparing and improvement, compensation, and prizes, execution examinations, maintenance, associations, and work relations) to the needy variable of an impression of human asset advancement. A method of reasoning for the examination is to scan for indicator factors that help to clarify noteworthy varieties in the reliant variable.

Along these lines, it is conceivable to determine that the differences in the needy variable of an impression of human asset advancement that can be represented by the autonomous factors in a blend (Manning and Munro, 2007). If several significant predictors can be identified, then not only the employers/HR managers can manage risks and maximize the favorable outcomes, but also policymakers can develop policies and incentives to facilitate human resource development.

In Table 25, the multiple correlation coefficient (R=0.672) was significantly different from zero, F (6, 68) =9.348, p<.05.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. An error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.672 ^a	.452	.404	.13200	.452	9.348	6	68	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Union and Labor Relation, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Remuneration and Rewards, Retention, Appraisals

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b. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

Table 23: Model summary

The coefficient of various assurance R squared (R^2) speaks to the extent of difference that can be represented by the indicator (autonomous factors) in a blend (Hair et.al. in Manning and Munro, 2007). Here, 45.2% of the change in human asset advancement could be clarified by enrollment and choice, preparing and improvement, pay and reward, execution evaluations, maintenance, and association and work connection ($R^2=.452$, balanced $R^2=.404$).

The ANOVA examination appeared in Table 26 underneath uncovers noteworthy relapse esteem ($\text{sig} < 0.05$). This shows indicator factors in blend could represent a lot of the difference in view of human asset advancement.

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.977	6	.163	9.348	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.185	68	.017		
	Total	2.162	74			

a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Union and Labor Relation, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Remuneration and Rewards, Retention, Appraisals

Table 24: ANOVA Analysis

The consequent examination tested the multicollinearity and clarified the relapse yield. Multicollinearity was estimated through the collinearity measurement area of the coefficients table (Allen and Bennett, 2010). Table 27 demonstrates that none of the factors had a resistance < 0.2 and $VIF > 5$. Accordingly, all factors were free from multicollinearity issues.

		Coefficients							Collinearity Statistics		
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Correlations			Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part		
1	(Constant)	2.606	.341		7.637	.000					
	Recruitment and Selection	.062	.067	.092	.929	.356	.262	.112	.083	.814	1.228

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Training and Development	.161	.052	.309	3.111	.003	.473	.353	.279	.817	1.224
Remuneration and Rewards	-.020	.074	-.034	-.272	.786	.310	-.033	-.024	.512	1.952
Appraisals	.008	.042	.029	.188	.852	.344	.023	.017	.327	3.055
Retention	.096	.028	.458	3.465	.001	.471	.387	.311	.462	2.164
Union and Labor Relation	.096	.036	.293	2.681	.009	.228	.309	.241	.676	1.479

a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

Table 25: Coefficients analysis

Data in the Sig. section of Table 27 demonstrates that four free factors training, maintenance, and labor union had huge (sig.) values under 0.05. This shows those related free factors fundamentally and interestingly added to the relapse condition for human asset improvement. An assessment of the t-value likewise demonstrates that every one of the three autonomous factors was related radically to human asset improvement. The other three independent factors of enlistment and choice, compensation and rewards and staff execution examinations didn't make a one of a kind individual commitment to the relapse condition since their criticalness esteems more noteworthy than 0.05.

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Figure 16: The normal probability

The ordinary P-P (probability) plot of relapses institutionalized lingering in Figure 24 was utilized to evaluate the suspicion of ordinarily circulated residuals. Figure 24 above demonstrates that the point bunched sensibly firmly along the inclining line, in this manner the residuals were regularly disseminated.

Figure 17: The scatter plot of standardized

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The dissipate plot of standardized residuals against anticipated institutionalized qualities in Figure 25 was utilized to evaluate the supposition of typicality, linearity, and homoscedasticity of residuals. The nonattendance of any reasonable example in the spread of focuses shows that these presumptions have been met. Despite the fact that there were just three autonomous factors extraordinarily adding to the relapse condition for human asset advancement, to investigate the connection between each of the six free elements and human asset advancement, the six autonomous factors were utilized in the below equation.

$$Y = 2.206 + 0.062x_1 + 0.161x_2 - 0.020x_3 + 0.008x_4 + 0.096x_5 + 0.096x_6$$

Equation 1: Equation model between dependent and independent variables

Where:

Y = Human resource development

X₁ = Recruitment and selection

X₂ = Training and Development

X₃ = Remuneration and rewards

X₄ = Performance appraisals

X₅ = Retentions

X₆ = Union and labor relation

5.3.5 Summary of Quantitative Analysis

By analyzing quantitative data, it can be concluded that the variables training and development (t=3.11, p=.003), retention (t=3.45., p=.001), and union and labor relation (t=2.68, p=.009) contributed uniquely and significantly to the regression equation (i.e., the prediction of perception of company performance). Recruitment and selection (t=-0.929, p=.356), remuneration and rewards (t=-0.272, p=.786) and performance appraisals (t=0.188, p=.852) did not appear to provide any significant contribution to the prediction of the perception of human resource development. Remuneration and rewards appeared to contribute negatively and non-significantly to the opinion of human resource development.

5.4 Conclusion of Chapter 5

Chapter 5 represented data analysis at the micro-level using a qualitative and quantitative approach. Results from the studies are summarized in the below paragraphs.

For qualitative results,

- The findings from three cases qualitative analyses indicate that FIEs have conducted international HRM practices in their own formal ways. The type of business appeared to influence the level of formality of HRM practices. Yet, some legal rules might not work for operational employees' recruitment and selection process.
- Although a few cases had straightforward line authoritative structures, the sets of expectations of every division were clear, and the undertakings depended on the primary exercises, for example, funding, promoting, creation and HRM. Besides, those organizations have increasingly extensive worker's records, which show the higher level of the custom of their HRM rehearses.
- Within-case examination gave an itemized investigation of the HRM approaches and practices of each case depends on the businesses' and the workers' answers. Looking at the examination results demonstrates that the genuine practices executed neither pursue government guidelines nor live up to workers' desires.
- Regarding Research Question 3 about the HRM guidelines and exercises in FIEs, there were practices directed by the administrators that got no bad things to say from the representatives. These included enlistment and determination, preparing and improvement and modern connection. A few contentions and protests were about compensation and rewards, execution examinations and maintenance.
- The cross-case analysis showed that Case A, Case B, and Case C had similar HRM policies and practices and the critical person who managed and implemented the HRM practices held the same position in each case. Yet, it seems like Case C, which is a Japanese company that has the simplest organizational structure since the production manager is working as HR manager in the company as well.
- The Recruitment procedures that were led officially and casually to get the correct applicants were comparable. These three cases likewise led hands-on training for every single new worker while the current representatives, particularly at the director level, were some of the time given other training dependent on necessities. Case A gives overseas training to new Laotian chiefs.
- Interestingly, the remuneration rewards systems adopted above the national minimum wage for all case companies. Recompenses changed among cases, yet they all gave comparable advantages, for example, maternity leave paid for a quarter of a year. Execution of examinations were led with various frameworks and destinations yet not critical and formal. The employees could join unions, but the membership policies were

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different based on the national and provincial levels of the zones each company was located.

For quantitative results:

- Demographic analysis of the data samples, as well as extensive descriptions, was presented to get a better understanding of the data set and the relationships of the variables under investigation.
- The descriptive analyses of HR rules and practices of FIEs in selected two major SEZs were from responses set of 5 Linkert scale range from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The descriptive analyses of perception on HR development were from responses set of 5 Linkert scale range from Very Low to Very High. Descriptive results demonstrate the significance of HRM policies and activities and HR development (Mean < 4.0). Generally, HRM rules and activities that are conducted formally, and which follow HRM standards, will positively affect HR development (Aggarwal, 2011; Farole, 2011; World Bank, 2015).
- The correlation analysis of the 75 respondents showed largely empirical evidence of the adoption of formal HRM rules and practices because the relationships showed positive values. The positive values of the correlations enabled a multiple linear regression analysis to be conducted.
- The regression analysis of foreign-invested enterprises generated a model of human resource development that could be predicted by predictor (independent variables) of HRM policies and practices. The model suggested that the four predictor variables of training and development, retention, and industrial relations, significantly contributed to human resource development while the other predictors' variables of recruitment and selection, remuneration and rewards and performance appraisals did not.

As a result, the proposed six hypotheses were accepted. In Chapter 6, the concluding chapter, the outcomes, and results for the six research questions are discussed further as well as policy recommendations.

Chapter 6: Discussion of Research Outcomes and Policies Implications

6.1 Introduction to Chapter 6

Chapters 4 and 5 provided results on SEZs benefits on HR development at the zone and firm-level. At the zone level, employment in a Laos zone has been generated in three ways, such as gender employment, direct employment, and non-direct employment or sub-contract evidence. Also, current HR development policies, opportunities, and challenges of HR development within Laos SEZs were discussed through face-to-face interview with the authorities concerned and the developer. Meanwhile, through the semi-structured interview, HRM rules and implementation of FIEs located within SEZs were explored at Micro-level analysis. Additionally, the survey questionnaire was conducted to investigate the relationship between HRM practice and regulations and HR development. The survey outcomes also support finding the semi-structured interview.

Accordingly, Chapter 6 is a discussion on outcomes from above chapters 5 & 6, which help the researcher answer five research questions. Findings from the two core chapters will be critically analyzed to define what has been discovered and what is the newly discovered. After that, to reach the aim of this research is to come up with comprehensive HR development regulations for Laos SEZs, and to answer research question 6, policies implementation is demonstrating in this chapter 6. In sum, Chapter 6 includes two major sections such as discussion of research outcomes answer research questions 1-5, and policy implication answer research question 6.

6.2 Discussion of research question 1

RQ1: How does a Laos SEZ generate employment to the Laotian workforce?

The quantitative data analysis in chapter 4 attempted to examine the way Laos SEZs generate employment opportunities to local. A zone was chosen as a case study and secondary data were gathered to examine the way a Laos SEZ impacts employment in three different ways, including direct and non-direct work and gender employment. The data sources were from Laos SEZs management and development office of Ministry of Planning and Investment, Zone management board office, Laos Statistic Bureau, World Bank report, and Laos Labor organization of Ministry of Labor and Welfare. The designated zone, namely Savan-Seno SEZ, was the first pilot zone developed by Laos government and foreign developers from China. The zone was the most developed in terms of employment and investments, and that is the reason why it was chosen as a case study. The following paragraphs discuss the main findings from the case study.

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Regarding *direct employment*, the zone generated the most Laotian workers comparing with the rest of Laos SEZs. Under a sound investment climate, Savan-Seno SEZ produces significant direct work each year and yet contributes only a small fraction of provincial employment, as well as national employment. In 2014, total employment in the zone amounted to 2,123 workers, including 1994 local workers. The number of foreign companies jumped from 52 in 2014 to 105 in 2017. As a result, the level of employment also increased significantly to around 4,793 by 2017.

Despite an impressive increase in employment in SSEZ, their share in manufacturing employment remains relatively low. The national labor force accounted for 40.8 percent of the total population in Laos (Lsb.gov.la, 2019). Although Savannakhet is the most populous province accounting for 15 percent of the total population in Laos, the contribution of the labor force in Savannakhet province is the lowest level accounting for 2.19 percent of the national labor force. The number of labors employed accounted for 12.4 percent of the total workforce in the province. Workers employed within Savanh-Seno SEZ accounted for only 0.5 percent of the total population in the province in 2017.

Like Laos, few nations where zone improvement and coming about business creation didn't satisfy hopes. A report covering Southern Africa focuses on particular and reasonable SEZ disappointments (Jauch 2002). Work creation has been small. Kenya, for example, burned through a massive number of dollars on SEZ advancement; however, in the initial five years, just 2,800 new openings were made (Rolfe et al. 2004). In Central America, Guatemala zones couldn't satisfy hopes. Agreeing with the official figures, customary SEZs in Guatemala had just 9 firms utilize around 1,400 laborers in the late 1990s (Jenkins et al. 1998).

There are a few such models crosswise over landmasses. These disappointments thusly could be ascribed to the disappointment of SEZ's approach to offer an exhaustive bundle of world-class foundation, quality administration, great area, and appealing to financial motivators, which is pivotal to draw in interest in SEZs (Aggarwal 2006). A few researchers contend that even among those nations where SEZs have encountered accomplishment regarding producing business, there are countries, (for example, Philippines and Indonesia) where the socially touchy joblessness issue has not really been settled on the grounds that the yearly increment in the size of the work power in these countries diminutive people such work as the SEZ may create (Madani 1999).

However, others recommend that the portion of EPZs in national business is an unacceptable marker of the zones' impacts on work and destitution easing. It is conceivable that the foundation of EPZs benefits lopsidedly the ventures that are escalated in the utilization of incompetent work since, in creating nations, these are the businesses that are probably going to create under the facilitated commerce system (Schwellnus 2003). All things considered, the effect of zones on provincial work and destitution might be significant, which may not be caught in the full-scale picture.

Apart from general employment to local workers, reports demonstrated that the zone has a critical impact on gender employment, which might transform the demography of the manufacturing industry in the country. Like the experience of numerous different SEZs in the

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Philippines, Bangladesh, Mexico, Dominican Republic, Korea, and China, the extent of female laborers' incomplete work has considerable in Savan-Seno SEZ when seen from a similar point of view. While it had been over 70 percent in many creating nations in the underlying stages, it was more than 80 percent. It expanded persistently to hit 112 percent from 2003-2017.

It has been set up in the writing that the financial investment of ladies, their essence in the workforce in quantitative terms, is significant not just for bringing down the unbalanced degrees of destitution among ladies, yet in addition as a considerable advance toward raising family salary and empowering monetary improvement in nations (WEF, 2005). It appears that SEZs have given openings for work to numerous young ladies from the country and connecting zones that have been instrumental in diminishing destitution in their locales.

A total evaluation of the business effect of EPZs ought to consider both immediate and backhanded work creation by zones. Tragically, tantamount information on the circuitous work impacts of EPZs is not broadly accessible. Constrained proof that is accessible demonstrates that circuitous business impacts of zones could be more articulated than direct impacts. For example, while breaking down the work effect of Masan SEZ in Korea, Cling and Letilly (2001) have contended that the accomplishment of Masan SEZ (Korea) indirect business commitment is moderate; however, its effect on roundabout business is required to have expanded considerably.

This is on the grounds that subcontracting to neighborhood ventures in this zone has developed significantly. There were 76 sub-temporary workers in 1976 speaking to 15 percent of the occupations in the SEZ working straightforwardly for the zone. Before the finish of the 1980s, the number of household subcontractors expanded to 525. The number of representatives in these organizations was generally half of the SEZ work. In the case of Savan-Seno SEZ, the sub-contract evidence is moderated. It has been reported that 32 percent of foreign and local firms in SSEZ reported that they have at 3 to 5 contracts, and 28 percent of them have more than 5 contracts with local companies serve as complementary goods and service companies or suppliers.

Indirect job creation seems to be an inevitable effect of SEZs in any country. Most of the local firms surrounding SSEZ are Small-Medium enterprises (SMEs) according to the researcher's field survey. Those SMEs such as minimarts, restaurants, hotels, laundry shops, cleaning companies, and so on serve diary basis of employees and companies within SEZs. The improvement of the local business surrounded zone generates job opportunities for locals in the province as well as in the country. In sum, under a sound investment climate, Laos SEZs have a high potential to increase jobs opportunity to Laotian people.

6.3 Discussion of research question 2

RQ2: What is the opportunity and challenge of human resource development within Laos SEZs?

Following the quantitative data analysis, the attempt to answer research question 2, enhances research results and validity by analyzing qualitative data from the semi-structured interview. Qualitative data were analyzed through in-depth interview persons experienced and

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contributed to the management and development of Laos SEZs. The qualitative analysis attempted to explore the challenges and opportunities of SEZs in the Laos context. Also, policies and incentives related to human resource development were discussed during face-to-face interviews. To find out the benefits of Laos SEZ, which has not demonstrated much based on the result of quantitative analysis, one of the most effective approaches is to ask policymakers or consultants who experienced SEZ management planning and strategy.

The interview discussion with an SEZ consultant found that if implemented in the right context, Laos SEZs have three potential benefits such as diverse business activities, improving trade facilitation and attract workers to industrial occupations, and improving labor conditions, which were most discussed during the conversation. Laos SEZs might help sectoral diversification if the strategy is in place based on market demand. Currently, labor incentive sectors such as manufacturing are improving, and tourism has recovered (World Bank, 2018). SEZs can enhance the potential of the sector by providing a friendly investment climate for an investor such as cheap land lease, fiscal incentives, and reduce investment papers and process.

Additionally, improving the manufacturing sector shall enhance the country's integration with the regional value chain. A good example was determined in the previous survey analysis of Savan-Seno SEZ where some foreign firms capture value chain through established factories across the region. Finally, the most expected benefit from the SEZs is to develop human capital in the country by attracting factory workers, provide a better working environment, and therefore improve their livelihood.

Apart from benefits, there is a challenge on SEZ development mentioned by a developer who experienced real-life SEZ development. Two major problems were discussed during the interview such as logistical challenge and insufficient human capital in the country. Although the logistics has become the main challenge of the zone, it is expected to be sorted out after the railway project linked from China to Singapore. However, the lack of human resources became a problem for investors within the zone as well as the developer.

Although the working-age population is 4,758,031 people, the Laos workforce accounted for 1,940,230, which is quite enough compared to the size of the country and its overall population; most of the Laotian labor are low-skilled and they lack industrial working experience (lsb.gov.la). The high retention rate within the zones is dramatically increased owing to the lack of manufacture working experiences. What should be more worrying, apart from low-skilled labor, is the unemployment rate. Approximately 40 percent of the working-age population (2,817,801 people) are counted as being outside the labor force since they are not interested in or cannot be hired partly due to age, studies, and other socio-economic reasons or undertake their own production work.

In addition, interview data also explained that most young workers tend to relocate to Thailand since the working environment is not attractive enough in the country. Nevertheless, the zone developer felt that the situation is getting better, and they are coordinate with authority concerned and local vocational school. Zeng (2015) implied that the government should focus more on human resource development policy and incentives to attract overseas talents and

stimulate the establishment of vocational and training schools to the zone. In addition, foreign-invested enterprises should be a source of knowledge and skill transfer to national workers.

6.4 Discussion of research question 3

RQ3: What are the incentives and policies offered by the Laos government to encourage human resource development within Laos SEZs?

On top of opportunities and challenges, the interview explored incentives and policies in SEZs. In sum, most of the investment policies are focused on fiscal incentives, which are not superior compared to policies outside SEZs. Most of Laos SEZs regulations, including developers and investors, are based on national investment incentives. Also, human resource management policies and labor relation policies in Laos SEZs are based on general policies of the Ministry of Labor and Welfare. However, additional to the previous SEZs management and administration policies is the real estate regulations and incentives that have not found outside SEZs. More about policy recommendation will be discussed on section 6.7.

6.5 Discussion of research question 4

RQ4: How human resource management policies and practices of foreign-invested enterprises are implemented within Laos SEZs?

Chapter 5 represented data analysis at the micro-level using a qualitative and quantitative approach. Case study analysis investigated three cases of the foreign-invested companies in which all case study companies were manufacturing companies from Europe and Japan located within two Laos SEZs called Savan-Seno SEZ and VITA Park. The findings of within-case analysis showed that the three case companies had formal organizational structures with personnel or HRM department, clear job descriptions, and legal HRM practices. Case A company, which was a European company, seems to have the most formal organization structure comparing to others.

The key person for HR management usually was a personnel manager. For case B and C, a production manager, who was responsible for overseeing manufacturing activities, also involve HR activities. The involvement of line managers in HRM has always been noted in the literature and has become important element of an HR approach (Legge, 2005), but in recent years the line has been seen to play a more prominent role in HRM due to more HR work being “devolved” to them (Currie and Procter, 1999; Guest and King, 2004; Storey, 2007).

Managers of three case study companies had post-graduate' degrees, and all of them are Laotian managers, who graduated from foreign countries, have similar culture of the companies they are working in. This point out that the managers play a significant role in the cultural adaptability of the company while maintaining HR policies and practices of their home country. Therefore, all cases seem to follow a home-oriented approach to their HRM, where MNEs behave

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in distinctive ways when managing HR issues. Kang and Shen (2014) implied that the transfer HRM practices are due to the dominance effect resulting from the fact that the host economy is relatively advanced than the home economy.

On the other hand, the tendency to localize HRM policies resulting from contextual differences between host and home nations, such as economic development, living cost, and compensation tradition. Since HR policies of SEZs in a low-income country such as Laos are not strong enough to control or compensate those foreign companies for developing human resources, so labor outcomes are very much dependent on the quality of HRM policy of the foreign enterprises. However, several shreds of evidence from the literature indicated that the transformation of new HRM policies and practice of the foreign-invested enterprises in SEZs shall enhance human capital and finally transform their HRM system in the country (Ding et al., 1997; Aggarwal, 2011). In the case of Laos, SEZs might need more time to demonstrated spillover of the new HR management knowledge to the rest economy.

As was talked about in Chapter 4, the contextual investigation discoveries about enrollment and determination demonstrated that all cases organization utilized both formal and casual techniques for enlistment. The proper procedure appeared in enlistment exercises, for example, publishing the vacancy through paper, talking to applicants, and evaluating up-and-comers' information and abilities. The casualness appeared in the utilization of informal exchange as the reciprocal method for publicizing the opening. The informal recruitment process occurs among operational employees. Research of Sun et al (2013) implied that in Asia, word of mouth seems to improve the organization's commitment more than formal recruitment. Since IHRM is still new in Laos, the word-of-mouth approach is inevitable for low-skilled employees to attend a manufacturing job for the first time.

The contextual analysis discoveries demonstrated that representatives announced having on the job training (OJT) as their conventional preparation lasting between two to three months. This affirms Kotey's and Sheridan's (2004) attestation that at the operational level, most managers gave hands-on preparation to their representatives. Additionally, the research of Aggarwal (2011) contended that the laborer in SEZs caught in low-talented employment since the preparation is short and, for the most part, task-explicit, outfitted to improving profitability and proficiency in the company's activity. It is anyway contended that SEZs still help in making aptitude bases by acquainting laborers with the rigors of the modern order, promptness, quality control, and timeliness.

OJT strategies prevalently include proprietor administrators watching and rectifying representatives at work. The organization, once in a while, assessed OJT in light of the fact that the reason for existing was to acquaint the new representatives with their occupations and workplace. Another preparation was dependent on requirements, for instance, word related wellbeing and security are prepared by bosses or the group pioneers that are offered consistently by the administration. This preparation gave advantages to the two managers and the organization

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in light of the fact that word related to wellbeing and security was the principle issue for assembling organizations.

For rewards, cases A, B, and C organizations gave wages above the lowest pay permitted by law of the host nation. The custom of compensation and rewards appeared on the execution of pay frameworks to decide workers' installment, including rewards and advantages framework that pursued government guidelines. The discoveries demonstrate that the proprietor/HRM directors revealed they gave their workforce explicit advantages, for example, recompenses and premium advantages, and those female representatives qualified for maternity leave benefits. Retirement advantages are not provided by all cases companies.

It creates the impression that appraisals were directed officially yet uncommon. A contextual analysis on organizations utilized structures to be filled in by chiefs or directors. Different organizations utilized generation accomplishment to assess workers' exhibitions. These were the criteria for evaluations using structures, and the outcomes were typically utilized for apportioning advancements. Be that as it may, the consequences of assessments were not handed-off back to the representatives, and this regularly caused disappointment among workers. This is another case of the paternalistic practices of the three case organizations, particularly in regard to advancement.

As was examined in Chapter 4, the contextual analysis discoveries about enrollment and choice demonstrated that all cases organization utilized both formal and casual techniques for enlistment. The proper procedure was appeared in enlistment exercises, for example, publicizing the opportunities through paper, talking with applicants, and evaluating up-and-comers' information and abilities. The familiarity appeared in the utilization of informal exchange as the reciprocal method for publicizing the opening.

Regarding remuneration and rewards, cases A, B, and C companies provided wages above the minimum wage of the host country. The formality of remuneration and rewards practices was shown on the implementation of wage systems to determine employees' payment, including rewards and benefits systems that followed government regulations. The findings indicate that the owner/HRM managers reported they gave their workforce specific benefits such as allowances, premium benefits, and those female employees were eligible for maternity leave benefits. Retirement benefits do not provide in all cases.

It appears that performance appraisals were conducted formally but were rare. A case study company used forms to be filled in by supervisors or managers. Other companies used production achievement to evaluate employees' performances. There were criteria for appraisals using forms, and the results were usually used for allocating promotions. However, the results of appraisals were not relayed back to the employees, and this often-caused dissatisfaction among employees. This is another example of the paternalistic practices of the three case companies, especially regarding promotion.

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In the interview, managers indicated that retention became the challenge of the companies. The situation was worse during the initial stage of the company establishment since Laotian workers do not have any industrial background. Firms, in all cases, focused on providing basic needs for an employee to enhance retention. The basic requirements are critical and gradually shape employees working routines to a new working environment. This shall strengthen the employee's adaptation to the firms' culture. Operational employees of Case A and B reported that they are feeling boredom since tasks given repeated overtime.

Tangthong et al. (2014) suggested that there are two aspects of employee engagement, such as cognitive and emotional engagement. The employees lack cognitive commitment since the workers are not aware of their mission at work and their role in the organization like case A and B employees. Emotional engagement is the extent to which the worker empathizes with others at work and connects in meaningful ways with co-workers. A case C company is an example of emotional engagement that employees are feeling connect to workers. For instance, workers join exercise activities after working hours. Emotional engagement is critical for socialist countries such as Laos. Laotian workers tend to feel more engaged in a meaningful way when they join a group of co-workers doing the same activities other than work.

The findings on industrial relations showed that employees of all case companies could join labor unions. Apart from the labor unions, there are youth and women labor union that anyone can join free of charge. All companies automatically join labor unions when they registered their business in Laos and must pay for the cost of participating in labor unions every year. It appears that all proprietary limited companies allowed unions regulated by the government. Employees are feeling satisfied with a labor union and never join any strike. Case C company has an employee who became a member of a woman union in the village.

6.6 Discussion of research question 5

RQ5: How does national cultural influence HRM of FIEs in Laos SEZs?

Semi-structured interview demonstrated that Laos cultural strongly impact ways of working of HR managers. This section demonstrated application of Laos cultural through Hofstede cultural aspects.

- **Power distance**

Hofstede (1973) explained that power distance refers to business hierarchy and different generation of power. Normally, an organizational structure portrays operational employees at the end of the ladder, and each ascending rung such as “supervisors, managers, directors and executive leadership.” Once workers recognize or acknowledge the power distance culture at work, they realize that supervisors have more power than employees, managers more power than supervisors, and executives more power than everyone else.

Within a culture of high-level power distance, workers seek approval from others at higher levels, and therefore have little choice but to submit to high-level management regarding strategic decisions. Laborers who want an fair power distribution would most likely want a flat structure of organization. They may be in a system of lower-level dominance, in which there are little to no structured divisions of dominance, or they may oppose the structure and levels of power within that structure.

On the point of power distance, Laos is not a typical case. Although the country is a communist country and power distance should be high similar to China, North Korea and other communist countries, Laotian dislike being authorized. Acceptance of subordinates seems to rely on relationship with higher authority that are built outside the organization. Foreign managers usually improve relationship with their subordinates through hanging out or doing activities together.

In case an organization comprise with many operational employees, managers should arrange activities that employees in each rank can do it together. In case of Case C, the company using this scenario to reducing retention rate. By conducting activities that employees in each range can participate, employees in each range get to know each other so that friendship and feeling attach to the organization are built.

- **Individualism vs. Collectivism**

Hofstede 's theory of individualism vs. collectivism characterizes self-centered workers vs. team-centered workers. Individualism states that individuals operate independently of their co-workers, while collectivism indicates a coexistence between employees, whether they operate in designated teams or behave jointly in certain ways, such as forming a union to discuss wages or benefits. Both individualism and collectivism can exist within the workplace, especially when you have departments where the productivity of employees relies entirely on the knowledge and skills of each employee, and other organizational areas where workers work in teams.

Laos is a mixed case on the individualism vs. collectivism. Throughout the Laos society, social practice is reflected throughout work or group activities. Banding communities and families to work together; holding meetings; and having festive occasions. The regulators, however, direct much of the collective task within the societies to ensure that everyone contributes back to society in equal measure.

Interestingly enough, the Laotians are not as conformist or collectivist as most of their neighbors in East Asia since Laos has 65 ethnic minorities and each has its own culture and language (Central Intelligence Agency, 2013). Even the Lao, the largest ethnic group that comprises nearly half of the population, is considered a minority in their own country. Therefore collectivism and conformity are cultural absurdities. The strong Buddhist conviction that each person is responsible for his or her own conduct is an added force working against the Asian

collectivist inclination. This encourages individuals to go their own way, and not mess with others' way. Although Laotian workers may usually be regarded as collectivists, they are far more individualistic than people know.

- **Masculinity vs. Femininity**

Worker actions under the theory of masculinity vs. femininity culture can demonstrate itself through specific roles or positions, or in the way workers perform themselves at work. For instance, in many situations, women employed in support positions, such as in administrative staff, have traditionally female positions in organisations. Roles where men have historically been put are in senior leadership roles or in positions requiring greater physicality, such as truck operators, shelf stackers or construction workers.

This MAS theory, on the other hand, could also describe the way workers behave themselves at work. For example, women are efficient negotiators (a study by Professor Michael Morris of the Columbia Business School and Emily Amanatullah of the University of Texas-Austin shows that women are "skilled negotiators"), while men participate in negotiations from an aggressive standpoint that can put them more from a hostile viewpoint.

Laos will be classified for this aspect into the category of femininity. Though it's individualistic, people prefer to cooperate, act modestly, and show care for the weak and wellbeing, much in line with the Buddhist view of accepting the current condition. The people of Laos are patient, non-confrontational and non-materialistic, making them particularly un-masculine (Centre Hofstede, 2013). The case study of foreign firms located in Laos SEZs, although supervisors are female, higher authority are male that has been sent from head quarter. Male managers design system and give tasks to HR supervisors who are female to implement all HR activities.

- **Uncertainty avoidance**

Workers who act as if they are not affected by uncertainty or inconsistency may have a very low level of avoidance of uncertainty. The cultural aspect relates to how relaxed the workforce is with transition. Likewise, workers with strong tendencies towards avoidance of ambiguity may feel more secure in positions where they have a high level of certainty that the company and job will stay stable.

The primary religion in Laos is Buddhism, and the Laotians believe strongly in the principles set out by Buddhism (Rook, 2011). A commitment to Buddhism may identify the nation as having a solid avoidance of uncertainty, which can be accompanied by disdain for dissidents and political or ideological protestors from the government (The Heritage Foundation, 2013). Buddhist teachings imply that people should be more easygoing in their lives, and that they should accept their situation more. People's practice, the way they treat others, is very crucial, which indicates the avoidance of uncertainty in Laos is reduced.

Like other countries, it takes some time for Laotian workers to become familiar with industrial working routines. Laotian managers of the companies confirmed that the situation is getting better since the retention rate is getting more stable. Also, it is believing that Laotian HR

officers or production directors are being promoted. Local supervisors have more understanding about local cultural as well as better communication, should make their subordinate feel more comfortable regarding to change.

- **Long-Term vs. Short term orientation**

Bureaucrats – those working in government agencies – can have lower scores on the Long-Term Orientation vs. Short-Term Normative Orientation (LTO) because they are employed in positions that can change in the long-term, often permanent, with election outcomes or transition in the government. Political appointees, for example, are likely to score little on the LTO. They are in traditional fields, but when a new president is elected their positions could come to an abrupt end.

Meanwhile, technology workers may score high on this index because they are constantly looking for opportunities that will allow them to remain in the sector as a way to prepare for inevitable changes. A high LTO rating means workers are considering their choices because they want to be capable of change while a low LTO rating means workers are relaxed at the moment, but they know that change will happen. Laos could be considered to be more oriented in short-term. This might be that Buddhism have taught them to live in the present and be happy with what they have. Laotians found it difficult to adjust in their career since they have been comfortable with being farmers. Nevertheless, society of young generation is changing rapidly. Young adults seek opportunities in the capital and are willing to develop their knowledge and career.

- **Indulgence vs. Restraint**

Work-life balance is perhaps the most effective way of defining employee behavior, using this index score for culture. A high rating on the Indulgence vs. Discipline (IND) index side indicates workers adopt a lifestyle that respects both personal and professional achievements. Workers who find it hard to loosen up on family holidays and remain attached to the workplace and their work, no matter where they are or what else happens in their personal lives, might have high Restraint ratings on this culture index.

After exploring the impact of social and political changes on employee behavior, in 2010 Hofstede again added to the previous five dimensions with this sixth. For this dimension, Laos may be considered to lean more towards restraint. The Buddhism teachings state that gratification should be delayed, as this comes with re-incarnation into a higher being. The Laos government also encourages restraint amongst the people, enforcing rules to create strict social norms. For this reason, Laos would have a low indulgence score.

6.7 Discussion of research question 6

RQ6: What are the relationships between human resource management policies and practices of foreign-invested enterprises located in Laos SEZs and perceptions of human resource development?

The socioeconomics of the 75 respondents from case A, B, and C organizations demonstrated that the businesses or people who had HRM obligations were generally male (26.7%). This affirmed in external contributing endeavors where business visionaries'/administrators' jobs were overwhelmed by men. The biggest gathering of respondents was somewhere in the range of 25 and 35 years old (44%) and had gotten a tertiary training (8%). This affirmed the Laotian work inside SEZs ruled by the low-talented workforce.

A large number of the businesses/directors had in any event 1 to 5 years of involvement in the related working field (56%). Reynolds et al. (2000) found that matured people in the 25-44 age group were the most innovatively dynamic. There are not many respondents who had post-graduate instruction, and the majority of them are Laotian administrators showing that the chiefs had information and abilities that were helpful for the organizations, and this may have added to the execution of formal administration rehearses. The remainder of low-gifted workers are operational representatives.

As was talked in Chapter 5, the graphic examination of exclusively restricted organizations demonstrated that the mean scores of factors fell inside the scope of $\mu \pm 1SD$ or above. This demonstrates the usage of HRM approaches and practices was consistently high. From six ward factors of HRM arrangements and practices broke down in the outside contributed organizations had mean scores over the range ($>\mu + 1SD$). These variables included recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and rewards, performance appraisals, retention, and labor relations. Human resource development was also analyzed in the mean score and standard deviation.

Child and David (2001) have previously proposed that MNEs can influence the actual structures of national business systems and the policies enacted by institutions within the countries. When applying to SEZs context, Ding et al. (1997) confirmed that the formality practice of FIEs in Shenzhen SEZ has changed the employment system in China and, therefore, contributes to economic transformation in the country. In the case of Laos, this research result confirmed that FIEs in SEZs have the potential to enhance the standard of HRM policies and practices in the Laos economy.

The remuneration and rewards variable appeared to have a high mean score, while the lowest mean score was for retention. From this, it can be concluded that the companies are very concerned with remuneration and rewards, while retention appeared to attach the least concern from the three case companies. The high mean score of compensation and rewards was supported

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by the high mean scores of remuneration and rewards' items. This might be due to a higher wage or salary comparing to the national minimum wage. The result also demonstrated that foreign earning is partially accounted for the establishment of the SEZs.

Although research outcomes regarding wages in SEZs were conflicting, this research confirmed that with sound backward linkages that included high-profile investors, Laos SEZ workers do not have to endure lower salaries. Like Shenzhen SEZ in China, which has become a model SEZs in great Mekong sub-region (GMS) including Laos, Cambodia, Thailand, and Burma, better wages provided by foreign-invested enterprises had lifted a small fishing village to into manufacturing hub of 8 million workers over the past 30 years (mekongmigration.org, 2018).

On top of that, it seems like all three cases focus on monetary benefits for employees, especially at the management levels. According to the 'Total Returns' framework presented by Newman et al. (2016), monetary rewards consist of base pay, the merit/cost of living, performance-related pay (i.e., short-term and long-term incentives) and employee benefits such as income protection, work-life arrangements, and allowances. Thus, those companies lack non-monetary rewards for employees, primarily operational employees such as recognition and status, learning opportunity, and employment security. This can impact the retention of operational employees.

Following remuneration and rewards, the high mean score for the recruitment and selection variable indicates that foreign-invested companies are also concerned with recruitment and selection practices. All items that measured recruitment and selection appeared to support the importance of recruitment and selection activities. Three case companies appeared to be concerned with formal recruitment practices such as advertising, interview, and job description. Nevertheless, word of mouth was found among operational employees based on operational interview employees.

Union and labor relations are an HR activity that the foreign-invested companies are moderately concerned. The result indicated that all case companies are following labor regulations and allow all workers to join the labor union. The average mean score of work relations was bolstered by the significant mean scores of work relations' things. Outside financial specialists utilizing a concession as speculation vehicle reports are ready to arrange the level of remote work to be utilized in the venture. By the way, work norms, for example, the lowest pay permitted by law and wellbeing and security issues, were applied to pay little heed to speculation vehicle or utilization of SEZs (Export.gov,2017).

Performance appraisals appeared to be of low significance compared to other HR activities. Based on survey and interview results, performance appraisals seem to establish pitfalls and failures due to psychometric errors. Appelbaum et al. (2011) inferred that psychometric blunders are one of the fundamental reasons why execution examinations are done inadequately inside partnerships. These mistakes, mercy, corona impact, confinement of range, recency, and complexity are ascribed to the mental inclination of the appraiser during the evaluation procedure.

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Employees in the case companies tend to believe that performance appraisals propose to spot their mistakes instead of aiming at personal development.

The mean score for training and development was within the range indicating the companies were concerned with training and development activities but did not put a lot of effort into them. Those companies appeared to focus on training for new managers during the initial period of the company establishment. Other trainings are for potential supervisors or team leaders in a vocational school or in-house training. Training for operational employees will last not more than three months in each case. Aggarwal (2011) indicates that training for the worker within SEZs are usually conducted in short duration and do not contribute much on knowledge formulation of the workers.

The low mean scores for retention appeared to be the smallest, indicating that foreign-invested companies had only a little concern with employees' retention. Items measuring concern for retention might not be fully agreed, such as flexible schedule, praise, and recognition, or other financial benefits to retain employees, career road map as expected by employees and employers like many countries during the initial stage of SEZs development. For instance, China's SEZs' retention is extraordinary for labor between 22 to 24 years of age (Ngai and Smith, 2007). The retention is gradually improving along with the establishment of zones' facilities such as dormitory and other infrastructure that support the livelihood of the whole family of the Chinese workers.

Apart from human resource policies and practices, the average mean of human resource development is considered very high from perceptions of management and non-management employees of three case companies. Interestingly, the lowest means score is the knowledge and skill formulation of the employees. This confirms the above result from descriptive analyses of HRM policies and practices did not put much effort into training and development of workers' operational employees. Most of the employees reported that they already have some skills in a related field, such as sewing or ironing from their vocational school. Most of the short training was conducted to help the employee familiar with the working environment.

6.7.1 Hypothesis testing and Multiple linear regression

Reacting to Research Question 5 included speculation testing and numerous direct relapse investigation. The speculation testing checked the connection between the reliant variable of the impression of human asset advancement with autonomous factors of the scope of HRM arrangements and practices. Every theory was tried utilizing the estimation of the connection. On the off chance that the relationship worth was sure and vast, the speculation was acknowledged and if the connection worth was non-huge, the theory was dismissed. Every one of the six speculations was acknowledged in the examination, which implies that HRM approaches and practices of remote contributed endeavors assumed a remarkable job on human asset improvement.

A standard various direct relapse performed between human asset improvement as the needy variable and the autonomous factors of enlistment and choice, training and advancement,

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remuneration and rewards, execution examinations, maintenance, and mechanical connection demonstrated that there were no multicollinearity issues in the relapse. In view of the R2 esteem, 45.2% of the fluctuation in the impression of human asset improvement could be clarified by enrollment and determination, preparing and advancement, pay, and reward, execution examinations, maintenance and mechanical relations (R2=.452, balanced R2=.404).

Information in the Sig. section of the coefficient table (see Table 27) in Chapter 5 demonstrated that three free factors had sig. values under 0.05. This shows related free factors fundamentally added to the relapse condition for human asset improvement. Besides, an assessment of the t-esteem shows that every one of the three autonomous factors, preparation and improvement (t=3.11, p=.003), maintenance (t=3.45., p=.001), an association and work connection (t=2.68, p=.009) altogether corresponded with human asset advancement and those three free factors interestingly added to the relapse condition. The other three free factors, for example, enrollment and determination (t=-0.929, p=.356), compensation and prizes (t=-0.272, p=.786) and execution examinations (t=0.188, p=.852) didn't make an extraordinary individual commitment to the relapse condition.

In spite of the fact that there were just three free factors remarkably adding to the relapse condition for human asset advancement, to investigate the connection between each of the six autonomous factors and human asset improvement, the six free factors were utilized in the accompanying condition.

The regression model was:

$$\text{The company's performance} = 2.206 + 0.062 \times \text{recruitment and selection} + 0.161 \times \text{Training and development} - 0.020 \times \text{Remuneration and rewards} + 0.008 \times \text{performance appraisals} + 0.096 \times \text{retention} + 0.096 \times \text{industrial relations}.$$

The model demonstrates that six autonomous factors all add to human asset advancement. The positive coefficient of preparing and improvement shows that preparation and advancement added to human asset improvement. This backing of the finding by Story (2002) demonstrates that instruction, preparation, and advancement are emphatically connected with better execution. It likewise bolsters the contextual investigation discoveries that all the remotely contributing organizations directed hands-on preparing for every new representative. It creates the impression that hands-on preparation has benefits as the new representatives got comfortable with the work environment, the assignments they were required to perform, and the organization's guidelines. This was probably going to prompt better occupation execution and efficiency of the employees.

The survey findings made sense that training and development might contribute to human resource development rather than recruitment and selection. The reason is that during the initial phases, SEZs are labor-intensive, use simple and low-cost technology, and require low-skilled workers (Aggarwal, 2007). Those low-skilled employees who usually enter formal careers for the first time do not have access to legal recruitment and selection and, therefore, relying on word of mouth from friends or relatives who are used to or are working within the zone. Thus, legal

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recruitment and selection might contribute very less on human resource development during the initial phase.

As discussed in the semi-structured interview, retention appears to be very high among young workers in SEZs, including Laos. Therefore, improving retention of firms significantly reduces unemployment and thus considerably contributes to human resource development. The high retention also means that employees within the zone shall have more experiences regarding their working field that enhances their career pathway in the future.

Various studies (Ding et al., 1997; Aggarwal, 2007) confirmed that employees that moved out of zones absorbed regular industrial working routines such as punctuality and discipline, and demonstrated entrepreneur capacities, among others. In the later stage, the zones illustrated a spillover effect on the rest economy. In case of Laos SEZs, although this survey showed that knowledge and skill formulation among workers at management and operational level is quite low due to low assembly types technology of SEZs firms, under constant improvement of investment climate in the zones when the firms move forward to higher technology, the skill and knowledge among workers might be higher also.

The positive coefficient of modern relations in the relapse model and the positive estimation of the connection of mechanical relations and view of human asset improvement implied that Hypothesis 6 was upheld. This end was likewise bolstered by the contextual investigation discoveries that all remotely contributing organizations enabled their workers to join associations. It gave the idea that most representatives comprehended that associations were there to shield their privileges and interests from the organization's out-of-the-line treatment. Albeit numerous representatives were not effectively associated with association exercises, they comprehended the advantages of the associations.

Moreover, upgrades to Laos work laws implied more opportunity for worker's guilds to support representatives through aggregate bartering. The improvement of association and mechanical relations practices helps organizations as far as interceding irreconcilable circumstances between the business and the workers and quickens the arranging procedure, implying that compromise can be quicker. This is bolstered by the theory testing on work relations, which demonstrates a positive and colossal connection worth. It is also supported by the qualitative findings of this study, in which case C company has a strong contribution to labor unions and is feeling safe and would contribute to the high retention of the company. Moreover, among others, a study of Hatcher (2017) revealed that emergent trends that membership size of labor union positive influence social values and employees' attitudes, which enhance retention and royalty of workers.

In conclusion, the regression model of the relationship between the dependent variable of the perception of human resource development and the independent variables of HRM policies and practices showed that the three variables of training and development, retention, and industrial relations appeared to contribute significantly to the perception of human resource development. This indicates that foreign-invested companies can improve human resource development by improving and formalizing these three aspects of their HRM policies and practices. The other three

variables of recruitment and selection, remuneration and rewards, and performance appraisals appeared to make no contribution to human resource development. This indicates that foreign-invested companies are not affected by these three practices.

6.8 Policies and framework implications: Discussion of research question 7

Chapter 6 discusses potential policies and incentives for SEZs in the Laos context to enhance human resource development. Chapter 6 answers the following research question 6:

Research Question 6: What incentives and policies can be recommended to strengthen human resource development in Laos SEZs as well as the best economy?

The results of the study revealed three significant findings from Macro and Micro-level analyses such as the way a Laos SEZ generated employment, the way HRM policies and practices of foreign enterprises were implemented, and the relationship between the HRM policies and practices and perceptions of human resource development. Furthermore, at macro-level analysis, an interview with the authorized representatives indicated that gap in skill is a challenge of SEZs development as well as human resource development in the country, and most of the policies and incentives are based on general policies in line with investment promotion policies and labor regulations. Accordingly, this research attempts to recommend policies and framework to enhance human resource accumulation in Laos SEZs. The following policies and framework implication can be drawn from the study:

- i. Enhance employment generation through investments:** Employment generation has thus far been the most important channel, through which SEZs have impacted on human development in Laos. The macro-finding of this research demonstrated that under sound investment climate, Laos SEZ such as Savan-Seno SEZ has a potential impact on Laotian employment. Even though their contribution to national employment has been somewhat limited, they have contributed to employment generation at the regional level and have had a two-fold increase every three years since 2012.

In general, employment generation depends on backward linkage (Farole, 2011; Zeng, 2015). To enhance employment within a zone, it is necessary for the zone to increase the numbers of investors through providing sound investment climate. SEZs can not only make procedures more efficient but, as “end-to-end” investment climate solutions, can provide a package of substantive policy reforms designed to address weaknesses in existing laws. Laos SEZs can enhance investment climate by providing below policies:

- Simplifying market entry and barriers to startup for investors. Along with the strong and long-term commitment of government, the SEZ Management and Development Office or any potential authority should have a right to act as a single management authority of Laos SEZs. The authority should have the power to independently satisfy all market-entry requirements for businesses (e.g., licensing, etc.). Requirements imposed by other

government authorities at both the national and provincial levels should be consolidated and/or replaced.

- SEZ regulations should establish clear, concise, and periodically updated negative lists that contain the only activities that can be denied. The review should be within the defined time frames, after which approval is deemed granted. Certain activities can also be subject to expedited/automatic approval. All market entry procedures should be carried out via One-Stop-Shop account executives, with SEZ Authority personnel carrying out back-office functions.

- Sector-specific investment restrictions and Non-Tariff Barriers or NTBs should also be removed to the greatest degree possible, including through the adoption of a negative list approach to determining whether investments should be allowed, with the list of prohibited investments as short, transparent, and non-discriminatory as possible, and subject to periodic review and lastly,

- To generate employment, instead of relying more on “ex-post” measures, such as compliance monitoring, inspections, and enforcement, a movement away from reliance on “ex-ante” measures is critical. For instance, requirements on entry, such as licensing, permits, documentary requirements, etc. This could be done by the following: *1. Substantially increasing the number of sectors eligible for automatic licensing and permits for establishment and/or operations; 2. reducing the space for discretion by government officials; 3. allowing denials to occur only for legitimate policy objectives based on a negative list; and 4. improving access to business regulatory information, through a full electronic data interchange system and risk-based approach that provides incentives for compliance.*

- Reducing time, cost, and procedures of getting access to water and electricity and ensuring consistent supply. Private-sector or public-private entities should have the clear right to develop and operate independent zone-related power infrastructure, as well as to charge tariffs for their services. Zone users should be able to use the one-stop-shop to activate service, pay bills, and deal with service interruptions promptly. The one-stop-shop should include on-site offices with authorized representatives from the developer/operator and any relevant government utilities, to ensure timely and responsive service. Complaint resolution mechanisms regarding utilities should also be implemented and facilitated through the one-stop-shop.

ii. **Created indirect jobs through backward and forward linkage.** To support indirect employment and for the contribution of SEZs to various aspects of human development to be realized, it is also important to forge linkages between the domestic economy and SEZs. Systematic efforts need to be made to help zone units forge links with the outside units. Most units are into cost-cutting by way of procuring inputs from local sources. Therefore, several policies should be introduced to support local-subcontract, such as:

- The government has also, in the new SEZ policy, relaxed the procedures for purchasing inputs from outside the zones. Yet, the policies only focus on raw materials input for the only agricultural industry. Therefore, incentives should be provided to support other raw or semi-raw material from local suppliers such as cement, cotton textile,

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plastic bottle, animal skin, and any other material support production activities of firms within SEZs. Along with that, rules relating to subcontracting also need to be standardized.

➤ As of now, firms think that it's hard to complete employment work outside the zone. Most firms are subcontracting inside the zone. During pinnacle seasons, it ends up hard for the organizations to keep uptime plans. A few guidelines might be formulated to unwind subcontracting standards in any event during pinnacle seasons. The organizations can't rival nearby makers in local markets on the off chance that they sell their items subsequent to paying full obligation in these business sectors. Some unwinding might be presented in the standards under certain extraordinary conditions. This may create learning overflow impacts just as a stream of physical merchandise leads to impersonation of new items and markets.

In terms of forwarding linkages, the FIEs who wish to sell their products in domestic market needs to pay general export tax rate like domestic companies. Currently, the forward linkage in Laos SEZs is rather limited only to agricultural products such as animal food. Part of the reason behind this is the small domestic market and no policies and incentives to support the linkage. Based on international experience in particular of which China SEZs, forward linkage played a crucial part in the country's imitation of export. The flow of physical goods from SEZs leads to imitation of the production and export of domestic companies. Additionally, FIEs are increasingly looking at Laos not only as a location for an export platform but also as an opportunity to tap into the local market.

- Several incentives can be provided to FIEs to enhance forward linkage. For instance, with less export tax, FIEs should be able to sell their products within the domestic industry where the type of products is an absence or is produced in a very small portion of domestic counterparts. However, the SEZ program should have prohibitive approaches set up, restricting nearby market deals up to 60 percent of creation. Most significantly, for farming organizations, who make up the main part of SEZs ventures, fewer neighborhood deals ought to be permitted. The nearby market confinement endeavors to secure against uncalled for rivalry, which is justifiable given the size of the neighborhood business and the significant motivating forces accessible to SEZ-based companies.

- iii. **Enhance human resource by reducing the costs of terminating employees.** The proposed SEZ Law and regulations should include a special labor regime, with specific exemptions from the national labor law. The special labor regime should allow for more flexible policies regarding dismissal. It should also include stronger enforcement mechanisms, such as dedicated labor compliance teams that regularly inspect workplaces, inform employers and employees of their rights and obligations, assist with compliance, and resolve complaints. Also, to improve skill levels, special training programs and partnerships with training institutions/universities should be put in place that train workers with the skills needed in the SEZs and connect them with potential employers.
- iv. **Enhance human resources through a standardized number of foreign management entries.** Bringing procedures and systems for Foreign Management entry authorization should more closely in line with more liberal international SEZ norms and streamlined. The number of Expatriate Management personnel eligible for entry, within zones regimes,

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should not be capped at 10% and then subject to discretion, but capped at a higher but more transparent 20% or even 30% level, with no discretion to increase expatriate numbers beyond the set threshold. Furthermore, the currently distinct Business Visas, Work Permits, and Residence Permits should be combined into a single SEZ Entry Permit.

- v. **Providing policies and incentives to encourage firms conduct training and development.** The substance and preparing modalities may shift depending on the various needs of various zones and divisions. No matter what, preparation must be consistently refreshed to keep pace with changing business and modern improvement needs. Certain strategy motivations can likewise be given to urge firms to give abilities preparing and retraining to their workers. At the point when certain gifts are not accessible locally, arrangements can be actualized to draw in these abilities from different pieces of the region or abroad.

At present, to guarantee information detailing of Laos laborers, the Labor Committee came up with an impediment of outside specialists inside a work unit. Furthermore, ideal strategies were additionally set up to pull in talented work, for example, the arrangement of lodging, subsidy exploration, instruction endowments, and so on. Furthermore, the SEZs (particularly the beginning time ones) were given more prominent political and financial self-sufficiency. They had the administrative position to create city laws and guidelines to administer these zones. Such abnormal circumspection permitted them more opportunities in seeking after new arrangements and improvement measures esteemed important to vitalize the economy.

- vi. **Establish specific policies to protect female workers within the zone.**

Zones have demonstrated to be especially helpful to businesses run by woman. SEZs have opened open doors for pay work for ladies in the proper part, in this manner expanding their employability just as improving their livelihood. This is a significant commitment of zones since female workers are essential for fair development. Pundits propose that work is feminized during the zones and that these ladies are youthful and can without much of a stretch be misused (Cling and Letilly, 2001, among others). Yet, little evidence supports these hypotheses. However, a certain framework should be adjusted to protect female workers. Zones and authorities concerned should coordinate with trade or women union to keep in touch with the women working within the zones. In each labor, a unit might have a female representative to act as a middle person between employees and employers.

- vii. **Forge linkage between SEZs and educational institutions.** The survey research on human resource development found a low score on entrepreneurial demonstration and knowledge formulation among SEZs workers. This might be due to weak linkages between the various actors (government, universities, industries, or firms) necessary to stimulate a culture of learning and innovation, especially where individual R&D capabilities are lacking. It is important for the government to play a pro-active role in resolving the issues. Effective measures are need to create R&D infrastructure, to forge linkages between institutions, universities, and the SEZ units, and to promote R&D funding. Most advocates of the development process consider education and acquisition of skills to be the most

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important weapon in the fight against poverty in the current era. It is argued that the productivity of labor forces in developing countries has failed to improve primarily since workforces in these countries are uncompetitive and lack the required skills. In this scenario, SEZs can be used as a policy instrument in upgrading skills and building human capital.

International experience suggests that an essential mechanism for achieving these ends is to consolidate regulatory functions over the SEZs into a single government agency, known as an “SEZ Authority.” The SEZ Authority should have the power and resources to perform most government actions on its own, such as all business licensing/registration, labor regulation, issuance of building permits and inspection, and complaint resolution. Laos’ NCSEZ appears well-positioned to take on this role if more authorities and resources are committed to it. It could also further improve the institutional governance of the SEZ program through:

- Improved monitor of compliance with SEZ laws
- Full and effective separation of regulatory and ownership functions (e.g., state ownership in zones and related infrastructure).
- Improving zone program administrative user-friendliness and transparency, for example by:
 - making investment laws and documents accessible online in a centralized location (e.g., on the Web);
 - adopting a more consistent and market-friendly approach to interacting with the private sector; and
 - establishing deadlines for processing approvals, after which approval is deemed granted, and publicizing those deadlines.

For their efficient delivery, all Government-Investor administrative interactions should also be further streamlined through an SEZ one-stop-shop mediation. While the SEZ Administrative Boards is already responsible for mediating these functions, their performance is inconsistent and the legislative basis for streamlining certain procedures is unclear.

Chapter 7: Conclusions

7.1 Summary of the Study

This examination manages to estimate the impact of SEZ in Laos on the improvement of the human assets at the macro and micro levels. The methodical estimation of the effect of Laos SEZs on human asset improvement at the two levels will be sorted and used to imply favorable incentives and rules to upgrade human assets in Laos SEZs and the rest economy. The design is to indicate how Laos SEZ made openings for work to the Laotian workforce and how HRM projects and exercises of overseas companies impact human asset advancement. The above 6 major chapters are summarized in the paragraphs below.

Chapter 1 represents the introduction of the thesis. Macroeconomic conditions of Laos selected as a case study country were analyzed to understand economic development proposals, challenges and opportunities, and the way SEZ can be an instrument to improve venture condition and update the human assets in the nation. In Laos, the human asset is required for the new economic structure, which transformed from the mining and agricultural sector to the industrial and service sector. Accordingly, SEZ was built up to bring remote capital, FDI in the form of MNEs, a source of skills, advance creation learning, and management.

Nonetheless, the problem is that not all SEZs succeed in all the expectations. While some countries such as China, Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines, and Ireland are experiencing a luminous economic transformation from SEZs establishment, several low-income countries in Africa and Asia, including Laos, are facing obstacles. SEZs can make a superior business condition in a geologically constrained zone, through an increasingly liberal legitimate and administrative system. This thesis aims to develop SEZs management policies, especially human asset accumulation of policies and incentives.

Chapter 2 was conducted to know the written works regarding the research context. This chapter included two major parts. The first part was reviewing the papers regarding human asset accumulation and MNEs' management, especially human asset management. In sum, human asset plays a crucial role on sustainable economic development in any place around the world and can be measured through several indicators such as quality of life, income earning, skill/knowledge formulation, working condition, and gender equality.

Furthermore, written works demonstrated that MNEs usually bring their production and management knowledge to their new overseas plants. Gradually, those advance skills and knowledge are transferred to local people and spill over to the rest economy. Moreover, its human asset management regulations and implementations such as recruitment, training, rewards, retention and labor union impact greatly on human assets accumulation. Yet, this depends on the standard of formality that the foreign companies have chosen based on their management strategy.

The second part of the chapter spoke about SEZs in the global and Laos context. In the global context, empirical researches were critically reviewed in order to define the means to measure the

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advantage of SEZs. There are two means that previous researchers used to evaluate the benefits of SEZs such as macro and micro measurement. Most of the economic literature focuses on estimating results of SEZs at the Macro level through the level of GDP, employment and export generation and diversifications. Meanwhile, Micro benefits of SEZs can be measured through the firms' performance and human asset management activities and rules.

Based on the above reviews, **Chapter 3** characterized the burdens of existing written works, research concept, questions and framework. There are three burdens of empirical studies about the SEZ's advantages; for example, based on anecdotal proof on precise assessment on effects of SEZs, very few and outdated researches put a spotlight on human asset advantages, and none of them use Laos SEZs as a contextual analysis. In view of those burdens, the concept of this investigation was to analyze the advantages of Laos SEZs at the macro and micro level.

At macro-level, zone advantages were inspected through the manners in which it impacts employment in three different ways, for example, direct employment, female employment, and sub-contract confirmations, or non-direct employment. Then again, the ways human asset management of foreign firms impacts human asset accumulation was inspected at the firm or Micro level. Research questions 1 to 3 were answered at the macro level, and question 4 and 5 were answered at the Micro level.

Results from both levels help the researcher to answer research question 6, which is the aim of this research to develop comprehensive policies for human asset accumulation in Laos SEZs. After research burdens, ideas, and frameworks were indicated, the chapter discussed the way research is conducted. In short, this research at the macro and micro level employed a mixed approach, including qualitative and quantitative methods. Chapter 3 presented the background of the following core chapters.

The first core, **Chapter 4** showed macro-level investigation or zone research. Optional information from the World Bank, ILO, Laos SEZs, the board office, Ministry of Planning and Investment, and Zone reports were assembled to look at the manner in which chose zone named Savanh-Seno SEZ impacted on jobs in three different ways, for example, immediate, roundabout and female employment. Furthermore, a semi-structured meeting was appointed to related specialists, for example, zone designers and SEZs senior staff to investigate current strategies, challenge, and chances of human asset improvement in Laos SEZs.

Results from the quantitative analysis showed that the zone contributes a very small fraction of provincial and national employment. However, a number of laborers inside the zone have been taking off-increment during the most recent couple of years and the vast majority of them are female. Also, sub-contract confirmations existed among remote undertakings inside the zone and local ventures outside the zone. This implies the zone may likewise produce work to local workers outside the zone. Sub-contract proves likewise demonstrated that local enterprises are Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Meeting results demonstrated that the absence of solid strategies focuses on advancing human asset improvement in Laos SEZs. Despite the fact that Laos SEZs are the second-third best policy to advance economic transformation, the zone could have some benefits to the local

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economy such as having diverse business activities, capturing regional value chain and improving human assets. In total, results from chapter 4 are too broad and can't portray all advantages of SEZs, and in this way, a micro-level investigation was led in the following chapter.

To lead an efficient assessment of SEZ benefits, **Chapter 5** displayed results from micro or firm-level examination. In this part, three organizations situated inside SEZs were chosen for meeting and poll review. At first, a semi-structured interview was conducted to investigate the way human asset management regulations of remote ventures were actualized. For each case, individual meetings were led for two to three chiefs and gathering meetings were selected for four to five non-administration staff. From that point forward, the cross-case investigation was created to compare the consequences of each case.

In brief, meeting results demonstrated that foreign venture implements formal human asset management activities. However, most non-management staff apply to SEZs occupations since verbal exchange from companions and relatives. Afterward, a survey study was conducted to look at the connection between human asset management regulations and the routine of foreign ventures and the impression of human asset advancement. The outcomes from the survey likewise bolster the results of meetings. Overall, it was discovered that human asset practice are identified with the employees' impression on human asset advancement, particularly training, maintenance, and worker's union where these played a noteworthy role in human asset improvement of representatives both at the operational and the executive level.

What's more, overseeing representatives who keep on becoming a significant test for outside put organizations in Laos just as Laos zones. While there has been next to no examination into the impacts of human resource, the board selection on the human resource, and the collection of the organizations, a consistent theme in the contentions exhibited in earlier investigations on human resource in outside ventures is that as the organizations develop unsophisticated individuals and the executive's methodologies become progressively lacking. When this occurs, the firm's owners and managers may come to realize the importance of culture. A working culture is associated with a worker's vision and norms towards their careers or jobs (Hofstead, 1995). Actually, national culture plays an important role on HRM in Laos since beliefs and norms of the Laotian are very strong. Foreign managers need to understand and adapt in order to work with Laos people.

Based on the results of chapters 4 and 5, **Chapter 6** presented policy recommendations for Laos SEZs. In total, a contextual investigation Laos zone demonstrated that under a sound investment atmosphere, jobs inside the zone had been generously expanded. However, it doesn't contribute to much national employment. Accordingly, approaches and motivations to upgrade the investment atmosphere are critical to creating job opportunities inside the zone. Besides, backward linkages with the local market are generally little since Laotian providers are limited and the strategies and motivators of the SEZ program are frail. With respect to the forward linkage, global experiences proved that forward linkages upgrade impersonation of local producers that lead to an increase in domestic export and modernization of the nation (World Bank, 2015).

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In this manner, incentives ought to be given to reinforce forward linkage, for example, import-trade charge impetuses for SEZ-based firms and domestic retail firms. Nonetheless, constraint ought to be applied for all sorts and sizes of the production industries to ensure in line rivalry. Aside from that, empowering human assets, strategies and motivations are ought to be given to firms to train and equip the skills of Laotian laborers as well as practice corporate social responsibility (CSR). However, the long-term responsibility depends on a greater extent on the host nation's administration and the level of opportunity of the SEZs program. The policy implications were addressed in this chapter to fulfill the aim of this study.

7.2 Thesis Contribution

This assessment has established a significant framework of global human asset management, human asset improvement, and free trade zones. This postulation seeks to establish several contributions to both theory and practice, which are considered underneath.

7.2.1 Contributions to change theory

- Contribution of research approach

This research contributes to the methods on measuring the benefits of special economic zones. Existing literary works demonstrated that not many examinations had been done efficiently of the impact of SEZs on the local economy. Few examinations are concentrating on estimating smaller scale or firms' advantages while most of the literature is tormented with concentrates that evaluate the full-scale advantages of SEZs. To evaluate if SEZs are an objective system, estimating large scale benefits alone isn't precise, as the degree of GDP, trade, or jobs isn't completely illustrative of the overall advantages of SEZs.

Subsequently, this research contributes to the written works. Especially, it adds micro or firm-level investigation to extend the study on the advantages of free trade zones. This examination hopes to provide insights on how overseas companies operate inside Laos zones and impact human asset advancement through their administrative practices, for example, enrollment, training, rewards, maintenance, and worker's union. The investigation speaks to a new estimation of the advantages of the free zones. The breakthrough theory showed the connection between human asset management exercises of foreign ventures on employees' views of human asset improvement.

- Creation of new theoretical model

A significant commitment of this exploration is a hypothetical model for human asset management of overseas firms to accomplish human asset headway. The direct

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relapse examination affirmed that each of the six free factors, for example, enrollment, preparation, rewards, maintenance, performance appraisal, and trade guild related to human resource development are analyzed through a degree of “quality of life, income, knowledge formulation, entrepreneurial capabilities, career prosperity, working condition, and gender equality.” Especially, preparation, maintenance, and trade guild affect the most to human asset development.

In other words, it can be said that this new model are derived from economic and business management literature such as human asset development, SEZs, and international human resource management. Therefore, the outcomes of this research added knowledge to both pieces of literature. The new model is practical to use, as portrayed in the succeeding sections.

7.2.2 Contributions to change practice

- The practices of human resource development policy in SEZs

The dissertation is the first systematic study regarding free trade zones’ benefits in Laos. It adds to the information and written works concerning human asset advancement approaches and impetuses of free zones. It will help strategise the producers and the Laos government to build up top to bottom comprehension in the way Laos zones impact human asset improvement. Also, the research aim is to concoct thorough human asset advancement regulations achieved in Laos zones . The producers and the government can adjust to and utilize the strategies to update Laos zone regulations later on. The policy implications were discussed in section 6.7.

- The practices of human resource management policies

The hypotheses of this research confirmed the connections between formal human resource management policies and practices of foreign firms on human resource development. Although there are several existing economic and business literatures that spoke about the transformation of local human resource practices through the establishment of foreign firms, very few literature centers on the procedures of the transformation and their presence. This means that current practitioners have the anecdotal resources to draw on as they face into the spectra of international human resource management. It is expected that this research can assist in influencing that idea and implementation of human resource management.

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For instance, the regression model discussed in Chapter 5 demonstrated the contribution of each predictor variable of human resource management practices to perceived human resource development. There were three variables, including “training & development, staff maintenance, and trade union that contribute positively and importantly to human resource development.” The other three variables, such as selection, bonuses, and performance assessment also played a role in human asset development but these are insignificant. Altogether, the model illustrated overseas enterprises in which implementations need to be amended or managed suitably to improve human assets and, therefore, encourage the firm’s performance.

Additionally, the finding from the regression analysis supported outcomes of macro-level analysis and focused on employment generation. The macro or zone level analysis indicated that 75 percent of local employees are female workers; it can be understood that those female workers might concern more on sustainable career development and working rights rather than rewards. Moreover, other aspects that should be of concern from the findings such as equal pay between women and men, sexual harassment, maternity or paternity leave, and other employee benefits while focusing on the rights of female workers should concern all practitioners.

What is more, the degree of formality of an organizational structure, the clarification of job description, and education levels of management and operational employees appeared to contribute to the degree of implementation of human resource management policies and practices. The findings regarding the human resource management practices of foreign firms have shown that some western-based practices have been introduced, but little effort has been made to introduce more sophisticated practices, especially in terms of recruitment and selection. Informal practices were used by some firms to make the recruitment process less complicated in order to reduce costs. In the short term, this can impact unequal opportunities and, therefore, hamper innovation in the long term (Agarwal, 2011⁹).

Accordingly, there is a possibility that foreign firms can change their recruitment practices that enable more people to access and improve the implementation of formal human resource management.

Regarding cultural perspectives, pieces of evidence demonstrated that national culture played a significant role on HRM of FIEs within the SEZs. HR managers need to understand characteristics of local workers. The best ways to prevent dilemma is to train local supervisors who are familiar with the Laotian working routine, speak the same language, and know the way to communicate with local employees. This shall help employees feel secure, start to open up their minds and enable them to follow directions.

7.3 Limitation of the Study and Direction Future Research

In conclusion, all objectives have been fulfilled in this research, but all researches have their strengths and weaknesses. This section discusses the limitation of this study and implied further research.

At the macro level, the assessment of job creation is centering on just the most developed zone (Savan-Seno SEZ) in terms of investment and employment. Each zone in Laos has a distinctive degree of advancement and strategy. In this manner, further research in different zones is required in knowing more about Laos zones. However, this investigation recommends that under a sound venture atmosphere, a Laos SEZ can possibly produce work in specific ways, for example, direct, indirect and female employment. Different zones may gain from the contextual analysis regarding the zone's guidelines and improvement in experience.

At the micro level, the utilization of few cases implies that the contextual analysis technique can't factually speak to the populace. In this investigation, a three-case configuration was actualized, in which each case was average regarding its ability to provide basic wellspring of data. Three cases may be viewed as not to be illustrative of the genuine condition in the remotely contributing organizations. Notwithstanding, by utilizing an enormous scale of poll overview which has the basic components that are developed specifically for this study was tried, the shortcomings of leading a little scale request were balanced.

Besides, the survey strategy is just expected to affirm the usage of formal human asset approaches and practices in foreign firms that had been found in the case study examination. Casualness isn't completely tested in the survey. The survey did not cover casual human practices and even though the contextual investigation examination did. This may imply that the discoveries about casual human asset approaches and practices in the organizations can't be applied more widely. As causality is related to the organizations' human asset activities, it may be worthwhile to quantify the findings by using a larger sample in a survey.

At its inception, this study did not attempt to separate different types of foreign-invested companies. However, the selected firms are located within Laos' zones and the representatives of high-profile companies are located within the zones. This might be an incomplete research. However, since the research aim was to explore the implementation of human assets management activities in a foreign venture, the finding that the venture had formal human asset practices led to the focus of this analysis.

Additionally, the respondents were employees at all levels in companies. Although the case study included all employees' opinions, the significant findings from the employees' side might contradict with their employers. Employers might have a more positive opinion towards formal policies and practice than their employees. Nevertheless, the study focusses on their "experiences" not on "opinions" on the implementing process on human assets, which are the six policies and practices (recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration rewards, performance appraisals, retention and union, and labor relations).

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In addition, preparation and advancement, maintenance, and labor relations seemed to have positive and noteworthy connections to human asset improvement. In the relapse model, these factors contributed altogether to human asset advancement. These discoveries may be tried in different organizations in different enterprises to examine how they practice these. Different organizations may have various practices. A 'positive' approach could be utilized to test the discoveries of this investigation in different ventures. The discoveries of this examination feature shared traits that are emerging when human resource principles and exercises are taken to remote ventures in the Laos zones and those shared traits might be advanced by applying them to contributing organizations outside the zones.

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Appendix 1: Information of the research (Interview at Macro and Micro level)

Thesis topic: Human resource management policies and practices in special economic zone: Case of Laos

Interview SEZs authorities concerned (research at Macro-level)

My name is Vilaty Keomahavong, a Doctor of Business Administration candidate at University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom. As a requirement of the study, I am conducting a research regarding to human resource management policies and practices of foreign invested enterprises in Laos SEZs.

I am establishing the research on human resource management policies and practices within Laos SEZs because I am currently working in the sector (Special Economic Zone Management and Development Office, Ministry of Planning and Investment). The research should enhance my understanding regarding to effect of SEZs on human resource development in Laos context and therefore, extend my career pathway. To come up with favorable policies and incentives to enhance human resource development within SEZs and the rest economy, the propose of the research is to explore current management policies and incentives in regarding to human resource development within Lao SEZs, and challenge and opportunity that the authorities faced during SEZs development. The methodology used for the research is case study. Accordingly, it shall use interviews and observation of the selected participants of the SEZs management authorities.

The research involved employees at operational and management level for the interview activities. You are invited to take part in this research by agreeing to participate in an interview, the details of which are provided below.

Interview procedures

The interview will mainly consist of open questions and will focus on two key topics:

- The HRM practices in your organization.
- Who conduct the HRM practices in your organization?

Each interview will take approximately 15-20 minutes of your time should you agree to participate and will take place in your company. Participation is purely voluntary, and no financial remuneration or incentive will be offered for taking part in this research. There are no travel expenses, nor are there any costs associated with participation in this research apart from your valuable time.

Responsibilities of the Researcher

To ensure the confidentiality of the information provided by you during the interview, your name and other identifying information will not be attached to data collected. Your name will only be used to enable an appointment to be made to conduct the interview. Your participation in this study is on a voluntary basis.

As an interviewee, you will be asked to sign an informed consent form, in which you give your permission that the information collected in the interview to be used in this study, without identifying your or your organization's name. All signed consent forms will be held in safe storage at the University for a period of five years before being destroyed. You are free to withdraw your consent and to discontinue participation at any time

The research findings may be submitted for publication. Unless agreed on otherwise, all data collected is anonymous and confidential. Other than your role or position within the organization, no personal data will be used in this research. All information collected will be presented as overall data. In the final research report, the participating organizations will only be referred to as cases with numbers. The results of the research will be made available to interested parties in final thesis format through University's library.

Responsibilities of the Participant and Possible Risks

The only requirement of you as part of this research, should you agree to participate, is a commitment of time and willingness to share your opinions and experience about the research topic. There are no foreseeable risks or discomforts involved for you in this research.

Inquiries

This form is yours to keep for future reference. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me any time:

Researcher: Vilaty Keomahavong, Doctoral candidate University of the West of Scotland, 235 Southwark Bridge Road, London, United Kingdom, SE1 6NP. Phone: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

The ethical aspects of this study have been approved by University of West of Scotland Human Research Ethics Committee. All complaints, in the first instance, should be in writing to the above address. All complaints are investigated fully and according to due process under the National Statement and this University. Any complaint you make will be treated in confidence and you will be informed of the outcome.

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

Interview employees in foreign invested enterprises (research at Micro-level)

My name is Vilaty Keomahavong, a Doctor of Business Administration candidate at University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom. As a requirement of the study, I am conducting a research regarding to human resource management policies and practices of foreign invested enterprises in Laos SEZs.

I am establishing the research on human resource management policies and practices within Laos SEZs because I am currently working in the sector (Special Economic Zone Management and Development Office, Ministry of Planning and Investment). The research should enhance my understanding regarding to effect of SEZs on human resource development in Laos context and therefore, extend my career pathway. The propose of the research is to examine human resource management policies and practices of foreign invested enterprises in Laos SEZs such as recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration and reward, performance appraisals, retention and union and labor relations. The methodology used for the research is case study. Accordingly, it shall use interviews and observation of the selected participants of the case study enterprises.

The research involved employees at operational and management level for the interview activities. You are invited to take part in this research by agreeing to participate in an interview, the details of which are provided below.

Interview procedures

The interview will mainly consist of open questions and will focus on two key topics:

- The HRM practices in your organization.
- Who conduct the HRM practices in your organization?

Each interview will take approximately 15-20 minutes of your time should you agree to participate and will take place in your company. Participation is purely voluntary, and no financial remuneration or incentive will be offered for taking part in this research. There are no travel expenses, nor are there any costs associated with participation in this research apart from your valuable time.

Responsibilities of the Researcher

To ensure the confidentiality of the information provided by you during the interview, your name and other identifying information will not be attached to data collected. Your name will only be used to enable an appointment to be made to conduct the interview. Your participation in this study is on a voluntary basis.

As an interviewee, you will be asked to sign an informed consent form, in which you give your permission that the information collected in the interview to be used in this study, without identifying your or your organization's name. All signed consent forms will be held in safe storage at the University for a period of five years before being destroyed. You are free to withdraw your consent and to discontinue participation at any time

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

The research findings may be submitted for publication. Unless agreed on otherwise, all data collected is anonymous and confidential. Other than your role or position within the organization, no personal data will be used in this research. All information collected will be presented as overall data. In the final research report, the participating organizations will only be referred to as cases with numbers. The results of the research will be made available to interested parties in final thesis format through University's library.

Responsibilities of the Participant and Possible Risks

The only requirement of you as part of this research, should you agree to participate, is a commitment of time and willingness to share your opinions and experience about the research topic. There are no foreseeable risks or discomforts involved for you in this research.

Inquiries

This form is yours to keep for future reference. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me any time:

Researcher: Vilaty Keomahavong, Doctoral candidate University of the West of Scotland, 235 Southwark Bridge Road, London, United Kingdom, SE1 6NP. Phone: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] **Personal details withheld.**

The ethical aspects of this study have been approved by University of West of Scotland Human Research Ethics Committee. All complaints, in the first instance, should be in writing to the above address. All complaints are investigated fully and according to due process under the National Statement and this University. Any complaint you make will be treated in confidence and you will be informed of the outcome.

Appendix 2: Consent form

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: **Human Resource Management Policies and practices in SEZs: Case of Laos**

Name of Researcher: **Vilaty Keomahavong**

Please initial all boxes

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study.
I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
3. I understand that relevant sections of my interview note, and data collected during the study, may be looked at by individuals from **the University of the West of the Scotland**, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.
4. I agree to my employer being informed of my participation in the study. And, some information regarding to company is approved by my employer to be shared during the interview.
5. I understand the data you are collecting from me, will only be used in UWS for academic purpose. But if you need to disclose outside the UWS you need to take my permission.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking consent

Date

Signature

Appendix 3: Study protocol

Thesis topic: Human resource management policies and practices in special economic zone: Case of Laos

This study was conducted at Macro and Micro level using mixed methods approach. At Macro-level, the propose of research is to investigate the way a Laos SEZ generated employment within and outside the zone including direct employment, indirect employment and female employment. To attain the study, secondary data from SEZs management and development office, World Bank, Laos Statistic Burau and Ministry of Labor and Social Welfare were analyzed. Additionally, to achieve aim of this research is to come up with comprehensive policies and incentives enhance human resource development in SEZs, semi-structed interview SEZs authorities concerned from SEZs management and development office, zone authorities and zone developers were conducted.

The interviews at Macro-level were meant to explore current policies and incentives, and challenges and opportunities regarding to human resource development within Laos SEZs. To establish the interview, approval letter was established to get approve from Head of SEZs management and development office (Appendix 4). The letter helped to ensure cooperation and coordination of interviewees, that working under the SEZs management authority. After receive approval letter, interview schedule was conducted based on participants' availability (Appendix 5). Before the actual interviews, information of the research (Appendix 1), consent (Appendix 2) and questionnaire (Appendix 8) were attached with appointment emails.

At Micro-level, the proposes of the study are to explore the way HRM policies of foreign firms located in Laos SEZs have been implemented. Additionally, examination on relationship between the implementations and policies of the foreign firms and perception of human resource development of the firms' employees were conducted. To succeed the proposes, semi-structed interviews and survey study were conducted at three selected case study A, B and C (two firms are operating in VITA Park located in Vientiane capital, and one firm is from Savan-Seno SEZ located in the Southern part of Laos).

Before the interviews, approval letter from economic board within zones where firms A, B and C are located was established (Appendix 6). After received approval, several government staffs working within the zone assisted researcher on coordination and conduct interview schedules (Appendix 7). After interview schedule was established researcher disseminated information of the research (Appendix 1), consent (Appendix 2) and questionnaire (Appendix 9 and 10) along with email so that researcher able to collect filled questionnaire during the interview day. Human resource manager played important role on selecting interviewees and disseminate questionnaires to employees at all level. Data collection at Micro-level was conducted within two days at VITA Park and one day in Savan-Seno SEZ. Below figure A3 illustrated research protocol.

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Figure A3: Research protocol

Appendix 4: Approval letter from Laos SEZs management and development office (for interviewing Laos SEZs authorities)

ສາທາລະນະລັດ ປະຊາທິປະໄຕ ປະຊາຊົນລາວ
ສັນຕິພາບ ເອກະລາດ ປະຊາທິປະໄຕ ເອກະພາບ ວັດທະນະຖາວອນ
ກະຊວງແຜນການ ແລະ ການວັງທຶນ
ຄະນະກຳມະການແຫ່ງຊາດລາວ ເພື່ອຄຸ້ມຄອງ
ເຂດເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ແລະ ເຂດເສດຖະກິດສະເພາະ
ກອງເລຂາ

ເລກທີ:...../ຄຂພສ
ນະຄອນຫຼວງວຽງຈັນ, ວັນທີ:.....

ເຖິງ: ພະແນກແຮງງານ, ພະແນກນິຕິກຳ ແລະ ກົດໝາຍ ແລະ ສະພາບໍລິຫານເຂດ
ເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ສະຫວັນ-ເຊໂນ

ເລື່ອງ: ຕັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນຂອງນັກຄົ້ນຄວ້າ-ພະນັກງານ ຫ້ອງການ ກຄຂພສ

- ອີງຕາມຂໍ້ຕົກລົງວ່າດ້ວຍການຈັດຕັ້ງ ແລະ ການເຄື່ອນໄຫວຂອງ ກຄຂພສ ສະບັບເລກທີ 01/ຄຂພສ, ວົງວັນທີ 13 ທັນວາ 2010.
- ອີງໃສ່ການປະສານງານລະຫວ່າງພະແນກພົວພັນ ແລະ ຮ່ວມມືສາກົນ, ກຄຂພສ ຄັ້ງວັນທີ 04 ສິງຫາ 2016.

ກອງເລຂາ ຄະນະກຳມະການແຫ່ງຊາດລາວ ເພື່ອຄຸ້ມຄອງເຂດເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ແລະ ເຂດ ເສດຖະກິດສະເພາະ (ກຄຂພສ) ຂໍແຈ້ງມາຍັງທ່ານຊາບຸກຽວກັບການຕັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນກ່ຽວກັບແນວທາງນະໂຍບາຍພັດທະນາຊັບພະຍາກອນມະນຸດ ເວົ້າລວມ ເວົ້າສະເພາະໃນຂົງເຂດຂອງທ່ານ ໃນວັນທີ 11-15 ມິຖຸນາ 2018.

ຈຸດປະສົງໃນການຕັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນຄັ້ງນີ້ເພື່ອນຳໃສ່ເຂົ້າບົດປະລິນຍາເອກ ຂອງ ນາງ ວິວະຕິ ແກ້ວມະຫາວົງ ປະຈຸບັນສຶກສາ ຢູ່ University of the West of Scotland, ປະເທດອັງກິດ ແລະ ຕຸ້ນຮຽນທົ່ວໜ້າພະແນກ ພົວພັນ ແລະ ຮ່ວມມືສາກົນ ກຄຂພສ. ດັ່ງນັ້ນ, ຈຶ່ງຮຽນມາຍັງທ່ານ ເພື່ອແຈ້ງໃຫ້ຊາບ ແລະ ໃຫ້ຄວາມຮ່ວມມືປະສານງານກັບພາກສ່ວນທີ່ກ່ຽວຂ້ອງດ້ວຍ.

ດ້ວຍຄວາມເຄົາລົບ ແລະ ນັບຖື,
ຫົວໜ້າກອງເລຂາ ຄຂພສ

Personal details withheld.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

(Translated)

To: SEZ Labor Division, and Law and Regulation Division of SEZ Management and Development Office; Economic Board of Savan-Seno Special Economic Zone

Topic: Data collection

Special Economic Zone Management and Development Office would like to inform you regarding to data collection of Miss. Vilaty Keomahavong, PhD candidate of University of the West of Scotland, a Deputy Director of International Relation Division, SEZ Management and development Office, Ministry of Planning and Investment. The objectives for the data collection are to interview representative of your organization, regarding to human resource development policies and challenge or opportunity of the human resource development. The acquired data and information will be used on Vilaty's thesis as a requirement of her PhD program. The data collection was planned to conduct between 11-15 June 2018 (See attached).

Therefore, this letter is established to request for your kind coordination on the data collection process.

Best Regards,
Head of SEZ Management and development Office

Appendix 6: Approval letter from zone authorities (for interview and survey case A, B and C)

ສາທາລະນະລັດ ປະຊາທິປະໄຕ ປະຊາຊົນລາວ
ສັນຕິພາບ ເອກະລາດ ປະຊາທິປະໄຕ ເອກະພາບ ວັດທະນະຖາວອນ
ກະຊວງແຜນການ ແລະ ການວັງທຶນ
ຄະນະກຳມະການແຫ່ງຊາດລາວ ເພື່ອຄຸ້ມຄອງ
ເຂດເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ແລະ ເຂດເສດຖະກິດສະເພາະ
ກອງເລຂາ

ເລກທີ:...../ຄຂພສ
ນະຄອນຫຼວງວຽງຈັນ, ວັນທີ:.....

ເຖິງ: ສະພາບໍລິຫານເຂດ ເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ສະຫວັນ-ເຈດີ
ສະພາບໍລິຫານເຂດ ເສດຖະກິດສະເພາະ ວຽງຈັນ-ໂນນທອງ

ເລື່ອງ: ເກັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນຂອງນັກຄົ້ນຄ້ວາ-ພະນັກງານ ຫ້ອງການ ກຄຂພສ

- ອີງຕາມຂໍ້ຕົກລົງວ່າດ້ວຍການຈັດຕັ້ງ ແລະ ການເຄື່ອນໄຫວຂອງ ກຄຂພສ ສະບັບເລກທີ 01/ຄຂພສ, ວົງວັນທີ 13 ທັນວາ 2010.
- ອີງໃສ່ການປະສານງານລະຫວ່າງພະແນກພົວພັນ ແລະ ຮ່ວມມືສາກົນ, ກຄຂພສ ຄັ້ງວັນທີ 04 ສິງຫາ 2016.

ກອງເລຂາ ຄະນະກຳມະການແຫ່ງຊາດລາວ ເພື່ອຄຸ້ມຄອງເຂດເສດຖະກິດພິເສດ ແລະ ເຂດ ເສດຖະກິດສະເພາະ (ກຄຂພສ) ຂໍແຈ້ງມາຍັງຜູ້ບັນຊາບກ່ຽວກັບການເກັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນກ່ຽວ ກັບການບໍລິຫານບຸກຄະລາກອນຂອງບັນດາບໍລິສັດທີ່ຕັ້ງຢູ່ ໃນເຂດທ່ານ ໃນວັນທີ 25-29 ມິຖຸນາ 2018.

ຈຸດປະສົງໃນການເກັບກຳຂໍ້ມູນຄັ້ງນີ້ເພື່ອນຳໃສ່ເຂົ້າບົດປະລິນຍາເອກ ຂອງ ນາງ ວິລະຕີ ແກ້ວມະຫາວົງ ປະຈຸບັນສຶກສາ ຢູ່ University of the West of Scotland ປະເທດອັງກິດ ແລະ ເປັນຮອງຫົວໜ້າພະແນກ ພົວພັນ ແລະ ຮ່ວມມືສາກົນ ກຄຂພສ. ດັ່ງນັ້ນ, ຈຶ່ງຮຽນມາຍັງທ່ານ ເພື່ອແຈ້ງໃຫ້ຊາບ ແລະ ໃຫ້ຄວາມຮ່ວມມືປະສານງານກັບພາກສ່ວນທີ່ກ່ຽວຂ້ອງດ້ວຍ.

ດ້ວຍຄວາມເຄົາລົບ ແລະ ນັບຖື,
ຫົວໜ້າກອງເລຂາ ຄຂພສ

Personal details withheld.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

(Translated)

To: Economic Board of Savan-Seno Special Economic Zone
Economic Board of Vientiane-Nonethong Special Economic Zone
Topic: Data collection

Special Economic Zone Management and Development Office would like to inform you regarding to data collection of Miss. Vilaty Keomahavong, PhD candidate of University of the West of Scotland, a Deputy Director of International Relation Division, SEZ Management and development Office, Ministry of Planning and Investment. The objectives for the data collection are to interview and conduct survey regarding to their human resource management policies and practices of foreign invested enterprises within your zone. The acquired data and information will be used on Vilaty's thesis as a requirement of her PhD program. The data collection was planned to conduct between 25-29 June 2018 (See attached).

Therefore, this letter is established to request for your kind coordination on the data collection process.

Best Regards,
Head of SEZ Management and development Office

----- Forwarded Message -----

From: [Redacted]
[Redacted]
[Redacted]
[Redacted]

Dear Vilatry,

Based on interview request letter, one company located in our zone have agreed to be interviewed and completed questionnaire in the morning of 28th June 2018. Please feel free to contact the [Redacted]
[Redacted]

Please do not hesitate to contact me if you need further assistance.

Kind regards,

[Redacted]
[Redacted]
[Redacted]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 8: Interview questions for Laos SEZs authorities

SECTION 1:

Interviewees: Government officers from central government

1. What is the main propose of government on establishing SEZs in Lao?
2. How 12 SEZs have been contributing to human resources development so far?
3. What are current government policy in enhancing human resources development in the SEZs?
4. What are challenges and opportunities to the development of human resources in Laos SEZs?

SECTION 2:

Interviewees: Government officers from selected zone and zone developer (Economic Board)

5. What is the main propose of developing this zone (Savanh-seno SEZ)? What is the background of the SEZ?
6. What sort of the HRD policy and incentive that enterprises within the zone have?
7. What is the future challenge and opportunity in terms of the HRD for the zone?

Appendix 9: Interview questions for employees at management level (English version only)

Section A:

Section A aims to explore the history and the profile of enterprises including the company's goals, vision and mission.

Question 1: Can you tell me about your company? Why do you choose to invest in Laos especially in this zone?

Question 2: What is the vision and mission of this company?

Question 3: What are challenge and opportunity of your business in Laos?

Section B:

Section B aims to explore the HRM policies and practices in the company?

Question 4: What do you think about the employees as human resource capital of the organization?

Question 5:

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- a. Would you explain the recruitment processes in this company?
- b. Do you make a plan before recruitment takes place?
- c. Do you do recruitment formally? Why?
- d. If you recruited formally, did you advertise the vacancy?
- e. If you recruited informally, what source of recruitment did you use?
- f. What recruitment sources does this company select for managerial and non-managerial positions? (relatives, friends, word of mouth, advertisement)
- g. Do the recruitment sources differ between managerial and nonmanagerial position?
- h. What are the selection criteria for the recruitment of managerial and non-managerial positions?
- i. Is there any test or interview for the selection processes?
- j. Do you have any strategy to get the right employees?
- k. Is there any relatives, family or friends who work here? If yes, how they recruited?

Question 6

- a. Do you perform training and development in your company? If yes why?
- b. Does this company have a training plan?
- c. What kind of trainings does your company usually conduct?
- d. How many times does the training take place in a year?
- e. Where does the training usually take place?
- f. How do you select employees for training?
- g. Is training seen as a reward for good performance or a punishment for a poor performance?
- h. Do you make evaluation on the employees after training?
- i. Do you have any strategy on training that will match with its cost?

Question 7:

- a. How do you compensate the employees?
- b. Do you have a plan on compensation for each employee?
- c. Do you follow government policy on wage standard?
- d. How do you determine employees' wages?
- e. Are there any criteria for compensation rate/pay level?
- f. Do you have a fixed plan for pay increase? at every how many yrs?

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- g. Are there any complaints about the pay rates?
- h. Is your compensation system competitive with other similar companies?
- i. Do you provide other rewards to the employees? j. Do you have any strategy on compensation?

Question 8:

- a. How do you conduct performance appraisal to your employees?
- b. Do you conduct performance appraisal to your employees on a regular basis?
- c. What are the criteria for employees' performance appraisal?
- d. What are your objectives in conducting performance appraisal?
- e. How do you give feedback on good performance?
- f. How do you give feedback on poor performance?
- g. Do you have a plan for employee's promotion?
- h. Are there any criteria for promotion?

Question 9: Do you encounter retention's challenge? How do you retain employees?

Question 10: Is there any union organization in your organization? If yes is it formal or informal? How do you feel about this union?

Appendix 10: Interview questions for employees at non-management level

Section A

Section A aims to explore the employee's background ພື້ນຖານຂອງ ພາ

Question 1: Why did you apply for this job in this company?

ຄໍາຖາມ 1: ເປັນຫຍັງເຈົ້າຈຶ່ງມາສະໜັມກວຽກນີ້

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Question 2: Did you have any relationship (such as family, relatives or friends) with the owner or manager or one of the employees before you applied this job?

ຄໍາຖາມ 2: ເຈົ້າເປັນຄົນທີ່ພົວພັນກັບຜູ້ເຮັດວຽກໃນ ບໍລິສັດ ບໍ່?

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c. When was the training provided? ການເຝິກອົບຮົມຈັດຕັ້ງຂຶ້ນຕອນໃດ?

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d. What was the duration of the training? ການເຝິກອົບຮົມດົນບານໃດ?

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e. Where did the training take place? ຈັດຢູ່ໃສ?

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f. Were you trained individually or in group? ເປັນການເຝິກຕໍ່ບຸກຄົນ ຫຼື ກຸ່ມ?

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g. Were your knowledge and skill improved by that training? ຄວາມຮູ້ ແລະ ສາມາດຈາກການເຝິກອົບຮົມເພີ່ມຂຶ້ນບໍ່?

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h. Do you know how you were selected for training? ເຈົ້າຮູ້ບໍ່ວ່າເຈົ້າຖືກເລືອກໄປເຝິກອົບຮົມດ້ວຍວິທີໃດ?

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i. Do you know why you were selected for training? ເຈົ້າຮູ້ບໍ່ວ່າເປັນຫຍັງຈຶ່ງຖືກໄປເຝິກອົບຮົມ?

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Question 7: ຄໍາຖາມ 7:

a. What do you think about your current wage? ເຈົ້າຄິດແນວໃດກ່ຽວກັບຄ່າແຮງງານໃນປະຈຸບັນ?

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b. Is your wage under, same or above national minimum wage? ເຈົ້າໄດ້ຮັບຄ່າແຮງງານຕາມກຳນົດຂັ້ນຕໍ່າບໍ່?

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c. Are you satisfied with your current wage? If not have you ever complaint? ເຈົ້າພໍໃຈຕໍ່ຄ່າຈ້າງທີ່ໄດ້ຮັບບໍ່? ເຄີຍຈົມບໍ່?

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d. Do you think your wage match with your skills and experience? ເຈົ້າຄິດວ່າຄ່າຈ້າງເໝາະສົມກັບຄວາມຮູ້ຂອງເຈົ້າບໍ່?

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c. Do you think the company has fair promotion policy? ເຈົ້າຄິດວ່າ ບສ ຍຸດຕິທຳໃນການເລື່ອນຂຶ້ນບໍ່?

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d. Does your company provide performance appraisal for its employees? ທາງ ບສ ມີການສ່ອງແສງປະເມີນຜົນບໍ່?

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e. If yes is there any feedback on your performance appraisal result? ຖ້າມີ ເຈົ້າຮູ້ຜົນຂອງການປະເມີນບໍ່?

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f. How is your supervisor giving feedback to your performance? ຫົວໜ້າເຈົ້າໃຫ້ຄຳເຫັນຕໍ່ການເຮັດວຽກຂອງເຈົ້າບໍ່?

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g. How is your supervisor performing his/her job? ຫົວໜ້າເຈົ້າເຮັດວຽກດີບໍ່?

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Question 9: Do you feel attach with the company? Do you have plan to stay in the company for a long time? ຄຳຖາມ 9: ເຈົ້າຮູ້ສຶກຕິດພັນກັບ ບສ ບໍ?

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Question 10: Have you joined any unions? If ‘yes’ is it formal or informal? Why have you joined it? ເຈົ້າເປັນ ສະມາຊິກ ສະມາຄົມແຮງງານບໍ?

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Appendix 11: Observation photos of Macro-level study: Savan-Seno SEZ

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Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

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Appendix 12: Observation photos of Micro-level study: Case A, B and C

Case A

The company provided uniform to employees and different divisions have dissimilar cab colour

Unpublished photographs without informed consent from photographed subjects. Please contact author for more information.

Unpublished photographs without informed consent from photographed subjects. Please contact author for more information.

Clean and tidy working environment

Unpublished photographs without informed consent from photographed subjects. Please contact author for more information.

Case B

No Uniform provide in sewing sector

Clean working environment with plenty of lights

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Case C

Unif

Clean environment with special bin provided in each production unit

Appendix 13: The survey form after adjustment (Laos and English version)

Section A	HRM policy and practice in your company ນະໂຍບາຍ ແລະ ການປະຕິບັດ ໃນການບໍລິຫານຊັບພະຍາກອນມະນຸດໃນ ບສ ຂອງທ່ານ					
No		Strongly disagree ບໍ່ເຫັນດີທີ່ສຸດ	Disagree ບໍ່ເຫັນດີ	Undecided ບໍ່ແນ່ໃຈ	Agree ເຫັນດີ	Strongly agree ເຫັນດີທີ່ສຸດ
	Score ຄະແນນ	1	2	3	4	5
	Description ເນື້ອໃນ					
	Recruitment and selection ການຮັບສະຫັມກງານ ແລະ ຄັດເລືອກ					
1	The company conducts formal recruitment and selection process ບສ ປະຕິບັດການຮັບສະຫັມກງານ ແລະ ຄັດເລືອກຢ່າງເປັນທາງການ					
2	The company uses external sources for recruitment ບສ ຮັບສະຫັມກຳລັງຈາກພາກພາຍນອກ					
3	The company uses advertisements (e.g media or online) as a recruitment source ບສ ນຳໃຊ້ສື່ໂຄສະນາ					
4	The company applies criteria for recruitment and selection ບສ ມີຂໍ້ກຳນົດຄຸນສົມບັດຂອງບຸກຄະລາກອນຢ່າງຄັກແນ່					
5	The company conducts individual interviews with all candidates ບສ ມີການສຳພາດງານຕໍ່ບຸກຄົນ					
6	The company conducts tests to ascertain candidate's skill and capabilities ບສ ມີການເຮັດເຂົ້າ					
	Training and development ການເຜີຍກຳລັງ ແລະ ພັດທະນາສີມືແຮງງານ					
7	The company conducts training on regular basis ບສ ມີການເຜີຍກຳລັງ ແລະ ພັດທະນາສີມືແຮງງານ					
8	The company conducts on-the-job training for the new employees ບສ ມີການເຜີຍກຳລັງພາກປະຕິບັດ					
9	The duration of on-the-job training is at least 2 months ບສ ມີການເຜີຍກຳລັງພາກປະຕິບັດຢ່າງໜ້ອຍສອງເດືອນ					
10	The company conducts other training (e.g management training) based on need ບສ ມີການເຜີຍກຳລັງອື່ນໆ					
11	The company conducts training for skills improvement purpose ບສ ຈັດຕັ້ງເຜີຍກຳລັງເພື່ອສຸມໃສ່ການພັດທະນາທັກສະການເຮັດວຽກ					
12	The manager makes an evaluation before and after training ຜູ້ຈັດການມີການຕີລາຄາກ່ອນ ແລະ ຫຼັງການເຜີຍກຳລັງ					
	Reward, compensation ການໃຫ້ລາງວັນ ແລະ ຊົດເຊີຍ					
15	The company has a fair compensation system ບສ ມີການຊົດເຊີຍສົມເຫດສົມຜົນ					

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16	The company follows national minimum wage ບສ ປະຕິບັດຕາມແຮງງານຂັ້ນຕໍ່າທີ່ລັດວາງອອກ				
17	The company uses criteria in determining the pay rate for each employee ບສ ກຳນົດຄຸນສົມບັດຂອງຜູ້ທີ່ໄດ້ເງິນເດືອນ				
18	The company increases the wage every year. ບສ ເພີ່ມຄ່າຈ້າງງານໃຫ້ພະນັກງານແຕ່ລະປີ				
19	The company pays higher wage compared with other similar companies ບສ ຈ່າຍຄ່າຈ້າງງານຫລາຍກ່ວາ ບສ ອື່ນໆ ທີ່ຄ້າຍຄືກັນ				
20	The company provides other rewards and benefit ບສ ມີການໃຫ້ລາງວັນ ແລະ ຜົນປະໂຫຍດອື່ນໆ				
21	The company provide decent wage ບສ ຈ່າຍຄ່າແຮງງານຢ່າງສົມເຫດສົມຜົນ				
	Appraisals ການປະເມີນຜົນ				
22	The company conducts performance appraisal of all employees ບສ ມີການປະເມີນຜົນຕໍ່ ພງ ທຸກຄົນ				
23	The company conducts performance appraisal on a regular basis ບສ ມີການປະເມີນຜົນຕໍ່ ພງ ເປັນປະຈຳ				
24	The company uses criteria for the performance appraisal ບສ ກຳນົດຄຸນສົມບັດໃນການປະເມີນຜົນ				
25	The company uses performance appraisal for career development purpose ບສ ຈັດຕັ້ງປະເມີນຜົນເພື່ອການພັດທະນາອາຊີບ				
26	The company uses performance appraisal for wage increment purpose ບສ ຈັດຕັ້ງປະເມີນຜົນເພື່ອການເພີ່ມຄ່າຈ້າງງານ				
27	The company informs the employees about the result of the appraisal ບສ ແຈ້ງຜົນການປະເມີນຜົນຕໍ່ ພງ				
	Retention ການຮັກສາພະນັກງານ				
28	The company provide fiscal benefits to enhance retention every year ບສ ໃຫ້ຜົນປະໂຫຍດດ້ານການເງິນໃນການຮັກສາພະນັກງານ				
29	The company provide comfortable work environment and cultural ບສ ມີອັດທະນະທຳ ແລະ ສິ່ງແວດລ້ອມການເຮັດວຽກທີ່ດີ				
30	The company generous with praise and recognition ບສ ມີການຊົມເຊີຍ ພະນັກງານພໍສົມຄວນ				
31	The company offer flexible working task and schedule ບສ ມີຕາຕະລາງເຮັດວຽກທີ່ຫລາກຫລາຍ				
32	The company provide basic needs and facilities ບສ ມີສິ່ງອ່ານວຍຄວາມສະດວກພື້ນຖານທີ່ພຽງພໍ				
33	The company provide career road map ບສ ມີແບບແຜນການເລື່ອນຊັ້ນຢ່າງຄັກແນ່				
	Union and employee relation ສະມາຄົມແຮງງານ				
34	The company allows employees to join union ບສ ອະນຸຍາດໃຫ້ ພງ ຂອງຕົນເປັນສະມາຊິກສະມາຄົມແຮງງານ				
35	The company allows employees to participate actively in the union activities ບສ ອະນຸຍາດໃຫ້ ພງ ມີການເຄື່ອນໄຫວໃນສະມາຄົມແຮງງານ				
36	The union has function properly ບສ ມີການຈັດຕັ້ງສະມາຄົມແຮງງານຢ່າງເປັນລະບົບ				
37	Employees receive benefit from the union's existence ພງ ໄດ້ຮັບຜົນປະໂຫຍດຈາກສະມາຄົມແຮງງານ				
38	Employees satisfy to join union				

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	ພາ ພໍໃຈໃນການເຂົ້າໃນສະມາຄົມແຮງງານ					
39	Joining union enhance bargaining power ການເຂົ້າເປັນສະມາຄົມຂອງສະມາຄົມເສີມສ້າງຄວາມສາມາດ ໃນການຕໍ່ລອງກັບ ບສ					

Section B	Perception on human resource development ທັກສະນະຕໍ່ການພັດທະນາຊັບພະຍາກອນມະນຸດ					
		Very low ຕໍ່າຫລາຍ	Low ຕໍ່າ	Neither low nor high ທຳມະດາ	High ສູງ	Very high ສູງຫລາຍ
	Score ຄະແນນ	1	2	3	4	5
No	Description ເນື້ອໃນ					
37	Quality of life ຄຸນນະພາບການດຳລົງຊີວິດ					
38	Income earning ລາຍຮັບ					
39	Skill and Knowledge formulation ການພັດທະນາຄວາມຮູ້ສາມາດ					
40	Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities ມີຄວາມສາມາດໃນການສ້າງທຸລະກິດຂອງຕົນເອງ					
41	Working/Living condition ຊີວິດການເປັນຢູ່ ແລະ ວຽກງານ					
42	Career prosperity ອານາຄົດອາຊີບຂອງຕົນ					
43	Gender equality ຄວາມເທົ່າທຽມທາງເພດ					

Section C	Demographic information ຂໍ້ມູນພື້ນຖານສ່ວນຕົວ						
	No	Description ເນື້ອໃນ					
45	Gender ເພດ	Male 1 ຊາຍ	Female 2 ຍິງ				
46	Age ອາຍຸ	18-25 (1)	25-35 (2)	35-45 (3)	45-55 (4)	55-65 (5)	
47	Position in the company ຕຳແໜ່ງ	Management position (1)	Non-management position (2)				
48	Working experience in the current position ປະສົບ	Less than 1 years (1)	1-5 years (2)	5-10 years (3)	More than 10 years (4)		

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	ການເຮັດວຽກ ແລະ ຕໍາແໜ່ງ ປະຈຸບັນ							
49	Highest education achieved ການສຶກສາສູງສຸດທີ່ໄດ້ຮັບ	Primary school (1) ປະຖົມ	Secondary school (2) ມັດທະຍົມຕອນຕົ້ນ	High school (3) ມັດທະຍົມຕອນປາຍ	Diploma (4) ຊັ້ນສູງ	Bachelor degree (5) ປະລິນຍາຕີຣ	Master degree (6) ປະລິນຍາໂທ	Other, please specify ລະດັບອື່ນໆ

Appendix 14: Demographic of survey sample

FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Gender Experience Age Position Education
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.

Frequencies		
Notes		
Output Created		12-FEB-2019 22:00:51
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Desktop\Demography.sav
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	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.
Syntax		FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Gender Experience Age Position Education /ORDER=ANALYSIS.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.02

Statistics						
		Gender	Working experience in the current position	Age	Position in the company	Highest Education Achieved
N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0

**Frequency Table
Gender**

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		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	15	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Female	60	80.0	80.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Working experience in the current position

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 year	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	1-5 years	42	56.0	56.0	62.7
	5-10 years	24	32.0	32.0	94.7
	More than 10 years	4	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	26	34.7	34.7	34.7
	25-35	33	44.0	44.0	78.7
	35-45	12	16.0	16.0	94.7
	45-55	3	4.0	4.0	98.7
	55-65	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Position in the company

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Management	14	18.7	18.7	18.7
	Non-management	61	81.3	81.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Highest Education Achieved

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		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Secondary school	16	21.3	21.3	21.3
	High school	31	41.3	41.3	62.7
	Diploma	18	24.0	24.0	86.7
	Bachelor	6	8.0	8.0	94.7
	Master	3	4.0	4.0	98.7
	Others (PhD)	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

CROSSTABS

/TABLES=Gender BY Position
 /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
 /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
 /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
 /COUNT ROUND CELL.

Crosstabs

Notes

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Comments			
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	Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
Cases Used		Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.	

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Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=Gender BY Position /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.01
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Position in the company	75	100.0%	0	0.0%	75	100.0%

Gender * Position in the company Crosstabulation

		Position in the company			
		Management	Non-management	Total	
Gender	Male	Count	4	11	15
		Expected Count	2.8	12.2	15.0
		% within Gender	26.7%	73.3%	100.0%
Female	Count	10	50	60	
	Expected Count	11.2	48.8	60.0	
	% within Gender	16.7%	83.3%	100.0%	
Total	Count	14	61	75	
	Expected Count	14.0	61.0	75.0	
	% within Gender	18.7%	81.3%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

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	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.790 ^a	1	.374		
Continuity Correction ^b	.269	1	.604		
Likelihood Ratio	.738	1	.390		
Fisher's Exact Test				.460	.291
Linear-by-Linear Association	.780	1	.377		
N of Valid Cases	75				

a. 1 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.80.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.103	.374
	Cramer's V	.103	.374
N of Valid Cases		75	

End of job: 25 command lines 1 errors 0 warnings 2 CPU seconds

Appendix 15: Abbreviation

Notes		
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Comments		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.
Syntax		CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=Mean VAR00008 /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.

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Cases Used		Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.
Syntax		CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=Mean VAR00009 /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.
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```
CORRELATIONS
/VARIABLES=HRD Recruit
/PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG
/MISSING=PAIRWISE.
```

Correlations

Notes		
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Comments		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD Recruit /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
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	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.03

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Recruitment and Selection
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.262*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.023
	N	75	75
Recruitment and Selection	Pearson Correlation	.262*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.023	
	N	75	75

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Notes

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Comments		
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	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD Training /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.06
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.11

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Training and Development
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.473**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	75	75
Training and Development	Pearson Correlation	.473**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Notes

Output Created	14-FEB-2019 15:27:35	
Comments		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD reward /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.05

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Remuneration and Rewards
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.310**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007
	N	75	75
Remuneration and Rewards	Pearson Correlation	.310**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Notes

Output Created	14-FEB-2019 15:36:53	
Comments		
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	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD appraisals /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.05

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Appraisals
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.344**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	75	75
Appraisals	Pearson Correlation	.344**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Notes

Output Created	14-FEB-2019 15:47:14	
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilaty\Desktop\HRD.sav
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	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD Retention /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.06
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.06

Correlations

		Human Resource Development	Retention
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.471**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	75	75
Retention	Pearson Correlation	.471**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Notes

Output Created	14-FEB-2019 15:56:14	
Comments		
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	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD union /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.06

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DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet7.
COMPUTE mean=MEAN(VAR00001,VAR00002,VAR00003,VAR00004).
EXECUTE.
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CORRELATIONS
/VARIABLES=HRD union
/PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG
/MISSING=PAIRWISE.

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Correlations

Notes		
Output Created	14-FEB-2019 16:06:01	
Comments		
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	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.
Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=HRD union /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.06

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

		Human Resource Development	Union and Labor Relation
Human Resource Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.228*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.049
	N	75	75
Union and Labor Relation	Pearson Correlation	.228*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049	
	N	75	75

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet7.

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet7.

SAVE OUTFILE='C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Desktop\unions.sav'
/COMPRESSED.

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.

DATASET CLOSE DataSet7.

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.

SAVE OUTFILE='C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Desktop\HRD.sav'
/COMPRESSED.

FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Recruit Training reward appraisals retention union
/STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Frequencies

Notes		
Output Created		14-FEB-2019 16:08:58
Comments		
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	Filter	<none>
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	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.
Syntax		FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Recruit Training reward appraisals retention union /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN /ORDER=ANALYSIS.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.02

		Statistics					
		Recruitment and Selection	Training and Development	Remuneration and Rewards	Appraisals	Retention	Union and Labor Relation
N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.2867	4.1289	4.4762	4.1844	4.1022	4.2267
Minimum		3.67	3.33	3.71	3.00	2.83	3.25
Maximum		4.83	4.83	4.86	5.00	5.00	5.00

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Frequency Table

Recruitment and Selection					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.67	2	2.7	2.7	2.7
	3.83	5	6.7	6.7	9.3
	4.00	10	13.3	13.3	22.7
	4.17	11	14.7	14.7	37.3
	4.33	22	29.3	29.3	66.7
	4.50	18	24.0	24.0	90.7
	4.67	6	8.0	8.0	98.7
	4.83	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Training and Development					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.33	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	3.83	12	16.0	16.0	22.7
	4.00	10	13.3	13.3	36.0
	4.17	28	37.3	37.3	73.3
	4.33	6	8.0	8.0	81.3
	4.50	9	12.0	12.0	93.3
	4.67	2	2.7	2.7	96.0
	4.83	3	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Remuneration and Rewards					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.71	3	4.0	4.0	4.0
	4.00	5	6.7	6.7	10.7
	4.14	7	9.3	9.3	20.0
	4.29	6	8.0	8.0	28.0

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

4.43	12	16.0	16.0	44.0
4.57	18	24.0	24.0	68.0
4.71	15	20.0	20.0	88.0
4.86	9	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

		Appraisals			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	3.00	6	8.0	8.0	8.0
	3.17	5	6.7	6.7	14.7
	3.33	6	8.0	8.0	22.7
	3.67	3	4.0	4.0	26.7
	4.00	4	5.3	5.3	32.0
	4.17	9	12.0	12.0	44.0
	4.33	8	10.7	10.7	54.7
	4.50	7	9.3	9.3	64.0
	4.67	8	10.7	10.7	74.7
	4.83	18	24.0	24.0	98.7
	5.00	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

		Retention			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	2.83	10	13.3	13.3	13.3
	3.00	1	1.3	1.3	14.7
	3.17	4	5.3	5.3	20.0
	3.33	13	17.3	17.3	37.3
	3.50	1	1.3	1.3	38.7
	4.17	3	4.0	4.0	42.7
	4.33	4	5.3	5.3	48.0
	4.50	5	6.7	6.7	54.7
	4.67	10	13.3	13.3	68.0
	4.83	13	17.3	17.3	85.3

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

5.00	11	14.7	14.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Union and Labor Relation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.25	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	3.50	6	8.0	8.0	14.7
	3.75	14	18.7	18.7	33.3
	4.00	4	5.3	5.3	38.7
	4.25	10	13.3	13.3	52.0
	4.50	13	17.3	17.3	69.3
	4.75	19	25.3	25.3	94.7
	5.00	4	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=VAR00001 VAR00002 VAR00003 VAR00004 VAR00005 VAR00006
 VAR00007
 /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN
 /ORDER=ANALYSIS.

Frequencies

Notes		
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Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.
Syntax		<pre> FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=VAR00001 VAR00002 VAR00003 VAR00004 VAR00005 VAR00006 VAR00007 /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN /ORDER=ANALYSIS. </pre>
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.05

		Statistics						
		Income earning	Skill and Knowledge formulation	Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities	Working/Living condition	Gender equality	Bargaining power	Career Prosperity
N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.3733	4.2667	4.3333	3.7867	4.3600	4.4933	4.3600
Minimum		3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Maximum		5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

Frequency Table

		Income earning			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	3.00	9	12.0	12.0	12.0
	4.00	29	38.7	38.7	50.7
	5.00	37	49.3	49.3	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Skill and Knowledge formulation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	4.00	45	60.0	60.0	66.7
	5.00	25	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	6	8.0	8.0	8.0
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	58.7
	5.00	31	41.3	41.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Working/Living condition

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.00	3	4.0	4.0	4.0
	3.00	22	29.3	29.3	33.3
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	84.0
	5.00	12	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Gender equality

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	9	12.0	12.0	12.0
	4.00	30	40.0	40.0	52.0
	5.00	36	48.0	48.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

		Bargaining power			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	3.00	4	5.3	5.3	5.3
	4.00	30	40.0	40.0	45.3
	5.00	41	54.7	54.7	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

		Career Prosperity			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	3.00	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	57.3
	5.00	32	42.7	42.7	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=VAR00001 VAR00002 VAR00003 VAR00004 VAR00005 VAR00006
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Frequencies

Notes		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

Syntax	FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=VAR00001 VAR00002 VAR00003 VAR00004 VAR00005 VAR00006 VAR00007 /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN /ORDER=ANALYSIS.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
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		Statistics						
		Income earning	Skill and Knowledge formulation	Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities	Working/Living condition	Gender equality	Bargaining power	Career Prosperity
N	Valid	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.3733	4.2667	4.3333	3.7867	4.3600	4.4933	4.3600
Minimum		3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Maximum		5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

Frequency Table

		Income earning			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	3.00	9	12.0	12.0	12.0
	4.00	29	38.7	38.7	50.7
	5.00	37	49.3	49.3	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

Skill and Knowledge formulation

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	4.00	45	60.0	60.0	66.7
	5.00	25	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Demonstrated entrepreneur capabilities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	6	8.0	8.0	8.0
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	58.7
	5.00	31	41.3	41.3	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Working/Living condition

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.00	3	4.0	4.0	4.0
	3.00	22	29.3	29.3	33.3
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	84.0
	5.00	12	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Gender equality

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	9	12.0	12.0	12.0
	4.00	30	40.0	40.0	52.0
	5.00	36	48.0	48.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Bargaining power

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	4	5.3	5.3	5.3
	4.00	30	40.0	40.0	45.3
	5.00	41	54.7	54.7	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Career Prosperity

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3.00	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
	4.00	38	50.7	50.7	57.3
	5.00	32	42.7	42.7	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

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 /ORDER=ANALYSIS.

Frequencies

Notes		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax		FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=HRD /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN /ORDER=ANALYSIS.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.03

Statistics

Human Resource Development

N	Valid	75
	Missing	0
Mean		4.2819
Minimum		4.00
Maximum		4.71

Human Resource Development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	4.00	8	10.7	10.7	10.7
	4.14	19	25.3	25.3	36.0
	4.29	25	33.3	33.3	69.3
	4.43	14	18.7	18.7	88.0
	4.57	8	10.7	10.7	98.7
	4.71	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total		75	100.0	100.0	

GET

FILE='C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Deskto\HRD.sav'.
 DATASET NAME DataSet1 WINDOW=FRONT.
 DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Recruit Training reward apprais retention union
 /STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV MIN MAX.

Topic of thesis: The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone

Descriptives

Notes		
Output Created		14-FEB-2019 16:22:09
Comments		
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	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	All non-missing data are used.
Syntax		DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Recruit Training reward apprais retention union /STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV MIN MAX.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.05
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.03

[DataSet1] C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Deskto\HRD.sav

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Recruitment and Selection	75	3.67	4.83	4.2867	.25492
Training and Development	75	3.33	4.83	4.1289	.32831
Remuneration and Rewards	75	3.71	4.86	4.4762	.28987
Appraisals	75	3.00	5.00	4.1844	.63528
Retention	75	2.83	5.00	4.1022	.81276
Union and Labor Relation	75	3.25	5.00	4.2267	.51853
Valid N (listwise)	75				

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

```

GET
FILE='C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilaty\Desktop\HRD.sav'.
DATASET NAME DataSet1 WINDOW=FRONT.
REGRESSION
/DESCRIPTIVES MEAN STDDEV CORR SIG N
/MISSING PAIRWISE
/STATISTICS COEFF OUTS R ANOVA COLLIN TOL CHANGE ZPP
/CRITERIA=PIN(.05) POUT(.10)
/NOORIGIN
/DEPENDENT HRD
/METHOD=ENTER Recruit Training reward appraisals retention union
/SCATTERPLOT=(*ZRESID ,*ZPRED)
/RESIDUALS NORMPROB(ZRESID)
/CASEWISE PLOT(ZRESID) OUTLIERS(3)
/SAVE COOK.

```

Regression

Notes		
Output Created		15-FEB-2019 18:25:13
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilaty\Desktop\HRD.sav
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	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	75
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Correlation coefficients for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair. Regression statistics are based on these correlations.

Topic of thesis: *The Impact of Human Resource Management Regulations and Activities of Foreign Invested Enterprises on Human Resource Development: A Case of Laos Special Economic Zone*

Syntax	REGRESSION /DESCRIPTIVES MEAN STDDEV CORR SIG N /MISSING PAIRWISE /STATISTICS COEFF OUTS R ANOVA COLLIN TOL CHANGE ZPP /CRITERIA=PIN(.05) POUT(.10) /NOORIGIN /DEPENDENT HRD /METHOD=ENTER Recruit Training reward appraisals retention union /SCATTERPLOT=(*ZRESID ,*ZPRED) /RESIDUALS NORMPROB(ZRESID) /CASEWISE PLOT(ZRESID) OUTLIERS(3) /SAVE COOK.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:05.17
	Elapsed Time	00:00:03.72
	Memory Required	3572 bytes
	Additional Memory Required for Residual Plots	528 bytes
Variables Created or Modified	COO_1	Cook's Distance

[DataSet1] C:\Users\Nou Nou Vilyat\Desktp\HRD.sav

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Human Resource Development	4.2819	.17093	75
Recruitment and Selection	4.2867	.25492	75
Training and Development	4.1289	.32831	75
Remuneration and Rewards	4.4762	.28987	75

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Appraisals	4.1844	.63528	75
Retention	4.1022	.81276	75
Union and Labor Relation	4.2267	.51853	75

		Correlations			
		Human Resource Development	Recruitment and Selection	Training and Development	Remunerat Rewar
Pearson Correlation	Human Resource Development	1.000	.262	.473	
	Recruitment and Selection	.262	1.000	.064	
	Training and Development	.473	.064	1.000	
	Remuneration and Rewards	.310	.353	.313	
	Appraisals	.344	.351	.190	
	Retention	.471	.317	.189	
	Union and Labor Relation	.228	.021	.263	
Sig. (1-tailed)	Human Resource Development	.	.012	.000	
	Recruitment and Selection	.012	.	.293	
	Training and Development	.000	.293	.	
	Remuneration and Rewards	.003	.001	.003	
	Appraisals	.001	.001	.051	
	Retention	.000	.003	.052	
	Union and Labor Relation	.025	.427	.011	
N	Human Resource Development	75	75	75	
	Recruitment and Selection	75	75	75	
	Training and Development	75	75	75	
	Remuneration and Rewards	75	75	75	
	Appraisals	75	75	75	
	Retention	75	75	75	
	Union and Labor Relation	75	75	75	

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
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1	Union and Labor Relation, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Remuneration and Rewards, Retention, Appraisals ^b	.	Enter
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a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Change Statistics		Sig. F Change
							df1	df2	
1	.672 ^a	.452	.404	.13200	.452	9.348	6	68	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Union and Labor Relation, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Remuneration and Rewards, Retention, Appraisals

b. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

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ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.977	6	.163	9.348	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.185	68	.017		
	Total	2.162	74			

a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Union and Labor Relation, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Remuneration and Rewards, Retention, Appraisals

Coefficients^a											
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Correlations		Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.606	.341		7.637	.000					
	Recruitment and Selection	.062	.067	.092	.929	.356	.262	.112	.083	.814	1.228
	Training and Development	.161	.052	.309	3.111	.003	.473	.353	.279	.817	1.224
	Remuneration and Rewards	-.020	.074	-.034	-.272	.786	.310	-.033	-.024	.512	1.952
	Appraisals	.008	.042	.029	.188	.852	.344	.023	.017	.327	3.055
	Retention	.096	.028	.458	3.465	.001	.471	.387	.311	.462	2.164
	Union and Labor Relation	.096	.036	.293	2.681	.009	.228	.309	.241	.676	1.479

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a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	(Constant)	Variance Proportions					
					Recruitment and Selection	Training and Development	Remuneration and Rewards	Appraisals	Retention	Union and Labor Relation
1	1	6.935	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	2	.042	12.835	.00	.00	.00	.00	.03	.19	.07
	3	.009	27.541	.00	.01	.00	.01	.29	.70	.19
	4	.006	34.000	.05	.07	.08	.00	.29	.01	.61
	5	.005	38.663	.01	.16	.74	.00	.02	.02	.02
	6	.002	62.291	.03	.38	.09	.73	.25	.08	.09
	7	.001	71.978	.90	.39	.09	.25	.13	.00	.02

a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	3.9855	4.5452	4.2819	.11492	75
Std. Predicted Value	-2.579	2.291	.000	1.000	75
Standard Error of Predicted Value	.025	.069	.039	.009	75
Adjusted Predicted Value	3.9825	4.5619	4.2838	.11645	75
Residual	-.33720	.29644	.00000	.12654	75
Std. Residual	-2.555	2.246	.000	.959	75
Stud. Residual	-2.658	2.320	-.007	1.003	75
Deleted Residual	-.36510	.31625	-.00186	.13869	75
Stud. Deleted Residual	-2.787	2.399	-.006	1.020	75
Mahal. Distance	1.589	18.995	5.920	3.154	75

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Cook's Distance	.000	.150	.014	.024	75
Centered Leverage Value	.021	.257	.080	.043	75

a. Dependent Variable: Human Resource Development

Charts

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